

**BUNDESMINISTERIUM
FÜR GESUNDHEIT**

Report 2008

**Trends and Sources of
Zoonoses and Zoonotic Agents
in Humans, Foodstuffs, Animals and
Feedingstuffs**

Austria

**Including information on foodborne outbreaks,
antimicrobial resistance in zoonotic agents and some
pathogenic microbiological agents**

AUSTRIA

The Report referred to in Article 9 of Directive 2003/99/EC

**TRENDS AND SOURCES OF ZONOSSES AND ZONOTIC AGENTS
IN HUMANS, FOODSTUFFS, ANIMALS AND FEEDINGSTUFFS**

**Including information on foodborne outbreaks, antimicrobial
resistance in zoonotic agents and some pathogenic microbiological
agents**

IN 2008

1. Information on the Reporting and Monitoring System

Country: Austria

Reporting Year: 2008

Institutions and laboratories involved in monitoring

Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
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Authorities

Central Veterinary Services	Federal Ministry of Health	Data concerning notifiable zoonoses in animals; Revision of the draft of the Trend Report; Approval of the Trend Report for Submission
Food Office	Federal Ministry of Health	Revision of the draft of the Trend Report
DG Public Health	Federal Ministry of Health	Revision of the draft of the Trend Report
Feed Office	Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, the Environment and Watermanagement	Revision of the draft of the Trend Report
Provincial Veterinary Services	9 provinces, one Veterinary Service per province	Data concerning notifiable zoonoses in animals
Regional Health Boards	One Regional Health Board per province	Collection of the data concerning food borne outbreaks

Institutes

Statistics Austria	The independent and non-profit-making federal institution, Statistics Austria, provides data on the economy, demography, environment and social and cultural situation in Austria to federal bodies. Federal agencies can then implement controlling measures in the scientific community, business and public institutions.	Demographic and livestock census data
Competence Centre for Infectious Disease Epidemiology (CC-INFE)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Compilation, validation, data entry and submission of the Zoonoses Trend Report

Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Analysis of laboratory results for antimicrobial resistance of <i>Campylobacter</i> spp. <i>Enterococcus faecalis/faecium</i> and <i>E. coli</i>

Human Medicine

Human Medicine	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data entry into internal data base concerning all cases notified as foodborne disease
National Reference Centre for Salmonella Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans
National Reference Laboratory for <i>Campylobacter</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Medical University of Graz	Data concerning campylobacteriosis in humans
National Reference Centre for Tuberculosis, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning mycobacteriosis in humans
National Reference Center for EHEC (VTEC) Department of Hygiene, Microbiology and Social Medicine, Division of Hygiene & Medical Microbiology	Innsbruck Medical University	Data concerning VTEC and listeriosis in humans
National Reference Centre for Listeria Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning listeriosis in humans
National Reference Laboratory for <i>Yersinia</i> , analyse BioLab limited company (GmbH)	Limited Liability Corporation of Elisabethinen Linz, MBB BioLab limited company (GmbH) and AGES	Data concerning yersiniosis in humans

Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
National Reference Laboratory for Toxoplasmosis, Echinococcosis, Toxocarosis and other Parasitic Diseases, Clinical Institute for Hygiene and Medical Microbiology	Medical University of Vienna	Data concerning parasitic diseases in humans
National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, (IVET), Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning brucellosis in animals and humans
National Reference Laboratory for Rabies, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning rabies

Food Control Institutes

Official Food Control Laboratories (ILMU)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES; Laboratories in Graz, Innsbruck, Linz, Salzburg and Vienna	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Food Safety Department of the City of Vienna	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Institute for Environment and Food Safety of the State of Vorarlberg	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Carinthian Institute for Food Analysis and Quality Control	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs

Veterinary Medicine

National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning tuberculosis in animals
National Reference Laboratory for Trichinellosis in Animals, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, (IVET), Innsbruck	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning trichinellosis in animals

Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Institutes for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES; Laboratories in Graz, Innsbruck, Linz and Moedling	Data concerning investigations in animals; bacteriological investigation in slaughtered animals
Carinthian Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Ehrental	Regional Veterinary Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in animals
Austrian Poultry Health Service (QGV)	Association installed by law, running different programs e.g. salmonella control and hygiene programs, Control of veterinarians and poultry farmers	Data concerning the Austrian poultry industry

Feed Control Institute

Institute for Agricultural Analysis, Linz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning feeding stuff
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PREFACE

This report is submitted to the European Commission in accordance with Article 9 of Council Directive 2003/99/EC. The information has also been forwarded to the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).

The report contains information on trends and sources of zoonoses and zoonotic agents in Austria during the year 2008. The information covers the occurrence of these diseases and agents in humans, animals, foodstuffs and in some cases also in feedingstuffs. In addition the report includes data on antimicrobial resistance in some zoonotic agents and commensal bacteria as well as information on epidemiological investigations of foodborne outbreaks. Complementary data on susceptible animal populations in the country is also given.

The information given covers both zoonoses that are important for the public health in the whole European Community as well as zoonoses, which are relevant on the basis of the national epidemiological situation.

The report describes the monitoring systems in place and the prevention and control strategies applied in the country. For some zoonoses this monitoring is based on legal requirements laid down by the Community Legislation, while for the other zoonoses national approaches are applied.

The report presents the results of the examinations carried out in the reporting year. A national evaluation of the epidemiological situation, with special reference to trends and sources of zoonotic infections, is given. Whenever possible, the relevance of findings in foodstuffs and animals to zoonoses cases in humans is evaluated.

The information covered by this report is used in the annual Community Summary Report on zoonoses that is published each year by EFSA.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AGES	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety
BMG	Federal Ministry of Health
BMSK	Federal Ministry for Social Security, Generations and Consumer Protection
CC-INFE	Competence Centre for Infectious Disease Epidemiology
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
ILMU	Official Food Control Laboratories, AGES
IMED	Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, AGES
IVET	Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, AGES
NRC Salmonella	National Reference Centre for Salmonella, AGES
OIE	World organisation for animal health
VIS	Veterinary Information System

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3. Animal Populations

The relevance of the findings on zoonoses and zoonotic agents is related to the size and nature of the animal population in the country.

3.1. Information on susceptible animal population

Sources of information

The independent and non-profit-making federal institution, Statistics Austria, provides data on the economy, demography, environment and social and cultural situation in Austria to federal bodies. Federal agencies can then implement controlling measures in the scientific community, business and public institutions. The data for this report are available from an online database established by Statistics Austria.

Herds, flocks, holdings, stocks

Cattle: The number of holdings and animals is based on the official database for cattle.

Equids, Pigs, Sheep, Goats and Farmed Deer: The number of holdings and animals is based on the yearly full survey of the Veterinary Information System (VIS).

Poultry: The number of holdings and animals is based on a random sample survey performed by Statistics Austria (farm structure survey). The last random sample survey was performed 2007.

Slaughters

Cattle, Equids: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly statistic of all examined slaughters (reported by veterinarians), performed by Statistics Austria.

Pigs: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly statistic of all examined slaughters (reported by veterinarians), combined with not-examined slaughters (out of pig-random-sample-surveys) performed by Statistics Austria.

Sheep & Goats: The number of slaughters is based on an expert-model carried out by Statistics Austria.

Poultry: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly full survey in poultry-slaughterhouses (only) performed by Statistics Austria.

Dates the figures relate to and the content of the figures

All data are received from Statistics Austria.

Definitions used for different types of animals, herds, flocks and holdings as well as the types covered by the information

Cattle: BGBl. II Nr. 391/2008 (Statistik über den Viehbestand im Jahr 2008)

Swine, Sheep and Goats: BGBl. II Nr. 166/2007 (Tierkennzeichnungs- und Regestrierungsverordnung 2007)

Poultry: BGBl. II Nr. 310/2007 (Erstellung der Statistik über die Agrarstruktur und den Viehbestand im Jahr 2007)

Geographical distribution and size distribution of the herds, flocks and holdings:

Pigs: 96.7% of all pigs are kept in 84.5% of the holdings that are located in the 4 provinces Carinthia, Lower Austria, Upper Austria and Styria;

Sheep: 72,7 % of the sheep holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 74.7% of the sheep are kept there.

Goats: 71,5 % of the goat holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 77.4% of the goats are kept there.

Additional information:

Nil

Table 1 Susceptible animal populations: number of herds and holdings rearing animals

Animal species	Category of animals	Number of holdings		Livestock numbers (live animals)		Number of slaughtered animals	
			Year*		Year*		Year*
Bovine animals	In total	75194	01.12.2008	1997209	01.12.2008	690974	2008
	LS: cattle under one year (incl. Calves for slaughter); Slaughters: calves only			636469	01.12.2008	80670	2008
	Cows and heifers not for slaughtering purposes			1098847	01.12.2008	610304	2008
	(mostly) Meat production animals (not incl. Calves for slaughter)			261893	01.12.2008		
	Mixed herds						
Sheep	In total	15276	01.04.2008	389379	01.04.2008	318921	2008
	Milk ewes	989	01.04.2008	20816	01.04.2008		
	Meat production animals						
	Animals over 1 year	15274	01.04.2008	224341	01.04.2008	63515	2008
	Animals under 1 year (lambs)	13486	01.04.2008	165371	01.04.2008	255406	2008
	Mixed herds						
Goats	In total	10278	01.04.2008	77655	01.04.2008	45036	2008
	Milk goats	3204	01.04.2008	23671	01.04.2008		
	Meat production animals						
	Animals over 1 year	8514	01.04.2008	51366	01.04.2008	9249	2008
	Animals under 1 year	4816	01.04.2008	26330	01.04.2008	35787	2008
	Mixed herds						
Pigs	In total	39993	01.04.2008	3172736	01.04.2008	5556508	2008
	Sows and gilts (slaughters: only sows)	9470	01.04.2008	300645	01.04.2008	111763	2008
	Fattening pigs	30380	01.04.2008	1129324	01.04.2008	5444745	2008
	Breeding animals						
	Multiplication animals						
	Mixed herds						
Gallus gallus	In total (slaughters: in slaughterhouses only)	58998	01.12.2007	13570372	01.12.2007	65909719	2008
	Breeding animals in total						
	Breeding animals for egg production line in total						

Animal Populations

Animal species	Category of animals	Number of holdings		Livestock numbers (live animals)		Number of slaughtered animals	
			Year*		Year*		Year*
	Breeding animals for meat production line in total						
	Elite birds in total	0		0		0	
	Elite birds for egg production line						
	Elite birds for meat production line						
	Grandparent birds in total	0		0		0	
	Grandparent birds for egg production line						
	Grandparent birds for meat production line						
	Parent birds in total						
	Parent birds for egg production line						
	Parent birds for meat production line						
	Laying hens	56403	01.12.2007	4994197	01.12.2007		
	Broilers	1367	01.12.2007	6845275	01.12.2007		
	Mixed flocks/ holdings						
Turkey	In total (slaughters: in slaughterhouses only)	1203	01.12.2007	568364	01.12.2007	1899503	2008
	Breeding animals in total	0		0		0	
	Elite birds	0		0		0	
	Grandparent birds	0		0		0	
	Parent birds	0		0		0	
	Meat production birds						
	Mixed flocks/ holdings						
Geese	In total (slaughters: in slaughterhouses only; incl. ducks)	1971	01.12.2007	21877	01.12.2007	25379	2008
	Breeding animals in total						
	Elite birds	0		0		0	
	Grandparent birds	0		0		0	
	Parent birds	0		0		0	
	Meat production animals						
	Mixed flocks/ holdings						
Ducks	In total (slaughters: part of geese)	9864	01.12.2007	55765	01.12.2007		

Animal Populations

Animal species	Category of animals	Number of holdings		Livestock numbers (live animals)		Number of slaughtered animals	
			Year*		Year*		Year*
	Breeding animals in total						
	Elite birds	0		0		0	
	Grandparent birds	0		0		0	
	Parent birds	0		0		0	
	Meat production animals						
	Mixed flocks/ holdings						
Equids		18845	01.04.2008	70008	01.04.2008	903	2008
Farmed deer		1794	01.04.2008	34443	01.04.2008		
Farmed reindeers							
Farmed wild boars							

4. Information on Specific Zoonoses and Zoonotic Agents

The World Health Organization defines zoonoses as “those diseases and infections which are naturally transmitted between vertebrate animals and man.” Foodstuffs often serve as vehicles of zoonotic infections. Zoonotic agents include viruses, bacteria, fungi, parasites or other biological entities that are likely to cause zoonoses.

Collection of human cases

Numbers of human cases are reported or notified by three different data-collection systems in Austria. **Aggregated notified cases on a monthly basis:** In Austria, physicians report all notifiable infectious diseases to the appropriate authorities. Reported cases are collected nationwide and published monthly by the Federal Ministry of Health online on the BMG-homepage:

(www.bmg.gv.at/cms/site/thema.html?channel=CH0745). Although the preliminary case numbers are available all year, they must be validated before the final report is published. These data only contain month and province of a notified case, no information is given concerning age and sex of the patient, or results of the differentiation of the causative agent (species or serotype etc.).

Notification of single cases: Therefore a new notification standard form has been created and each single case of a selected notifiable diseases (salmonellosis, campylobacteriosis, yersiniosis, shigellosis, VTEC-case, and staphylococcosis). These forms containing essential and anonymised information on each patient compatible with the needs for TESSy are sent to the AGES. The AGES is responsible for entering and evaluating these data into the database. The final version of these dataset is transmitted to the BMG and further to TESSy. Although these figures may differ from the case numbers notified monthly to the Federal Ministry of Health.

Primary isolates from patients typed in the national reference centres: The responsible reference centres publish the numbers of microbiologically confirmed cases; these figures may also differ from the case numbers notified to the Federal Ministry.

In this report it is clearly indicated which source of data has been used for the respective zoonosis.

General Information about the Food Sampling Strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the decree „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2008 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2008“ (BMGFJ-75500/0247-IV/B/7/2007 von 08.01.2008) of the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2007-2010) according to Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every food business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2008, approximately 40,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 60% (24,000) of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc.

There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a given period of time. In 2008, eight food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2008 BMGFJ-75500/0242-IV/B/7/2007). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

4.1. Salmonellosis

4.1.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Human salmonellosis remains a major health problem in Austria. In 2008, the number of notified salmonellosis cases was the second highest reported pathogen after campylobacteriosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The incidence of human salmonellosis has significantly declined since the peak in 1998/1999. The salmonella-contamination of raw poultry meat has declined from 30% in 1999 to less than 7% in 2008. The consumption of eggs that are contaminated with Salmonella is presently the main source of human infection.

The number of salmonellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of primary human isolates and respectively the number of laboratory confirmed cases sent to the National Reference Centre for Salmonella, n = 3,196. This number shows a reduction of 21% compared to the year 2007 and reflects the success of interventions aimed at combating salmonella. According to the Federal Ministry of Health, the official number of notified cases is 2,790 (aggregated cases, vorläufiger Jahresausweis über angezeigte Fälle übertragbarer Krankheiten 2008). 2,328 cases have been notified as single cases (see chapter 2. collection of human cases).

As compared to the number of notified cases of campylobacteriosis (see chapter campylobacteriosis), salmonella is the second most important cause for enteric diseases in Austria.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

In 2008, data from feedingstuffs indicate that the prevalence of salmonella (<1%) is decreasing compared to previous years. The number of cases which test positive for Salmonella is highest in poultry. Therefore, poultry is considered the main source for human infection. Although only few eggs were positive for salmonella (1.2% of the total number of tested eggs), infected eggs pose the main source of human infections.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

There were various programs implemented to control the contamination of Salmonella in poultry, most programs involved meat and egg production. The main effort of the intervention is directed toward improving the sanitation of breeding flocks and laying flocks according to EU legislation.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Continue the efforts already started, especially to improve harmonization of monitoring and control programs along the food chain.

4.1.2. Salmonellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

Human cases are reported to the Austrian Federal Ministry of Health from the Health Authorities. The system distinguishes between domestic and imported cases.

The number of salmonellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of primary human isolates and respectively the number of laboratory confirmed cases sent to the National Reference Centre for Salmonella. Both numbers differ due to different sources.

Case definition

Clinical picture compatible with salmonellosis, e. g. diarrhoea, abdominal pain, nausea and sometimes vomiting. The organism may cause extraintestinal infections.

Laboratory criteria for diagnosis: Isolation of *Salmonella* spp. (non-typhi, non-paratyphi) from a clinical specimen.

Case classification

- Probable case: A laboratory confirmed isolate without clinical information or, a case with clinical symptoms that has an epidemiological link
- Confirmed case: A clinically compatible case that is laboratory confirmed

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriology: Sample material is processed as described in Richtlinien für die Diagnostik von Salmonellen (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 11-12).

At the National Reference Centre for Salmonella (NRC Salmonella), all isolates are serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. And further all *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are phage typed according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK. Additionally the antimicrobial resistance testing by disk diffusion method is performed with each isolate.

Notification system in place

Specialists in Laboratory Diagnosis or Microbiology and Hygiene and the attending physicians are required to report all *Salmonella* cases. Notification of salmonellosis according to the epidemic act has been mandatory since 1950 (BGBl. 1950/186 Epidemiegesetz, as amended). Since 2002, a note of the Federal Ministry for Social Security, Generations and Consumer Protection (BMSK) has been implemented (Meldepflicht infektiöser Erkrankungen für Labors GZ: 21.700/5- VIII/D/5/02), in which medical doctors specialised in Laboratory Diagnosis or Microbiology and Hygiene are required to report all cases of *Salmonella* which are clinically verified.

The number of salmonellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of primary human isolates and respectively the number of laboratory confirmed cases sent to the National Reference Centre for Salmonella.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 1989 and 1990, human infections with salmonella increased markedly in Austria. After a peak in 1992, the incidence of salmonella illness decreased, but the number of infections has remained at a high level until 2002. Since that year the number of laboratory confirmed cases of human *Salmonella* infections has decreased by 62% (2002: 8,405 primary isolates, 2008: 3,196 primary isolates).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2008, the number of laboratory confirmed cases of human *Salmonella* infections again decreased compared to the year before.

The proportion of *S. Enteritidis*, out of all *Salmonella* isolates, decreased in 2008 slightly to 68,5% (compared to 77% in 2007). The distribution and order of the three most common phage types (in 2007: PT8 (34%), PT4, (30%) and PT21 (15%)) are very similar, 2008, PT4 has been the most frequently (35%) identified, followed by PT8 (24%) and PT21 (19%). In 2007, the three most common phage types account for 78% of all *S. Enteritidis* strains, compared to 79% in 2007. The number of *S. Typhimurium* isolates reported remained more or less the same (n=374) compared to 2007 (n=354). This represents 11.6% of all *Salmonella* spp. isolates from human stool samples.

In 2008, an increase of resistant isolates had been observed (see chapter 2.1.7.).

Table eggs are probably still the main source of human infections of *S. Enteritidis*.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In 2008, the number of notified human cases of campylobacteriosis again exceeded the number of salmonellosis cases. It is believed that the reduction in the number of human salmonellosis cases is due to EU wide control programs and establishment of goals for the reduction of prevalences of salmonella in laying hen flocks and broilers.

Additional information

Annual report of the National Reference Center:

http://www.bmg.gv.at/cms/site/attachments/4/6/2/CH0954/CMS1237532383420/jb_salmonellen_2008.pdf

Data Source of Tables 2 to 4: Primary isolates from patients typed in the national reference centre for salmonella

Table 2 Salmonellosis cases in humans - species/serotype distribution

	Cases	Incidence/ 100,000	Imported cases	Unknown status
Salmonellosis	3196	38,4	170	3026
S. Enteritidis	2200	26,4	131	2069
S. Typhimurium	374	4,5	6	368
of these: DT 104L MR	70	0,8		70
monophasic S. Group B (1,4,5,12 : i : -)	95	1,1	4	91
S. Infantis	55	0,7	1	54
S. Saintpaul	36	0,4		36
S. Hadar	26	0,3	1	25
S. Agona	24	0,3	3	21
S. Newport	23	0,3	2	21
S. Thompson	23	0,3		23
S. Abony	17	0,2		17
S. Napoli	16	0,2	1	15
S. Virchow	16	0,2	1	15
S. Paratyphi B var. Java	15	0,2	1	14
S. Montevideo	13	0,2		13
S. Oranienburg	13	0,2	1	12
S. Kentucky	12	0,1	2	10
S. Muenchen	11	0,1		11
S. Rissen	11	0,1		11
S. Senftenberg	10	0,1	2	8
other Serotypes	206	2,5	14	192

Table 3 Salmonellosis cases in humans - age distribution

Age group	Salmonellosis			S. Enteritidis			S. Typhimurium			other serotypes		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	75	43	26	32	17	14	11	7	3	32	19	9
1 to 4 years	470	240	230	340	173	167	62	32	30	68	35	33
5 to 14 years	549	304	245	393	209	184	66	44	22	90	51	39
15 to 24 years	442	248	194	300	178	122	47	21	26	95	49	46
25 to 44 years	695	352	343	455	227	228	81	40	41	159	85	74
45 to 64 years	466	240	226	308	159	149	53	31	22	105	50	55
65 years and older	451	208	243	336	159	177	50	20	30	65	29	36
Age unknown	48	15	25	36	9	21	4	2	2	8	4	2
All age groups	3196	1650	1532	2200	1131	1062	374	197	176	622	322	294

Table 4 Salmonellosis cases in humans – seasonal distribution

Month	Salmonella sp.	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	other serotypes
	Cases	Cases	Cases	Cases
January	132	96	17	19
February	94	54	13	27
March	100	54	18	28
April	168	97	22	49
May	162	104	25	33
June	281	208	32	41
July	483	370	45	68
August	469	316	73	80
September	580	395	47	138
October	307	214	36	57
November	215	145	22	48
December	205	147	24	34
not known				0
Total	3196	2200	374	622

4.1.3. Salmonella spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2008 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2008“ (BMGFJ-75500/0247-IV/B/7/2007 von 08.01.2008) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2007-2010) according to Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2008, approximately 40,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 60% (24,000) of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2008, eight relevant food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria (Schwerpunktprogramm 2008 BMGFJ-75500/0242-IV/B/7/2007). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Campaign A-804-08: Salmonella spp. in food - Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - chilled - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: April - June

Type of specimen taken

Other processed food products and prepared dishes

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Salmonella spp. in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

105 samples tested, 0-times positive for Salmonella spp.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for L. monocytogenes

Campaign A-029-08: Salmonella spp. in food - Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream - made from pasteurised milk - at catering - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September – November

Type of specimen taken

Cream, made from pasteurised milk

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Salmonella spp. in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

96 samples tested, 0-times positive for Salmonella spp.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for L. monocytogenes

Campaign A-010-08: Salmonella spp. in food - Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - made from pasteurised milk - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: April - May

Type of specimen taken

Ice-cream, made from pasteurised milk

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* spp. in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

130 samples tested, 0-times positive for *Salmonella* spp.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to ISO 6579: 1999, with modifications: After preenrichment, selective enrichment in modified semisolid Rappaport-Vassiliadis or Diasalm, 18-24 hours at 42°C. Subsequently plating on XLD agar, Brilliant green-Phenolred-Lactose-Saccharose agar (BPLS), *Salmonella* Detection and Identification Medium (SMID) or Rambach agar.

25 g of raw material for egg products or 25 g of pooled content of 5 table eggs are either incubated directly or preenriched in peptone water. Further steps are performed as described above.

All isolates are sent to the NRL *Salmonella* and serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are phage-typed according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections:

Salmonella spp. was detected in fresh single broiler meat samples in 6.4 % (23 out of 359), in 15% of fresh turkey meat samples (5/34), and in 1 out of 46 samples (2.2 %) of unspecified poultry meat fresh samples. In 2007, there was no *Salmonella* spp. sample found positive in 45 samples of cooked meat products of broilers, ready-to-eat. However, in 2008, 5.6% (10 out of 180) were found positive. None of the tested bovine meat samples (0/127) tested positive. In all the pig meat samples (fresh and cooked), one of the 289 tested single samples (0.3 %) was found positive. In mixed meat samples (minced pig and bovine meat) 2 of the 130 samples tested were found positive (1.5%). In 2008, 2,204 samples from milk, milk products and cheeses (all from cows', sheeps' or goats' milk) were tested for *Salmonella* spp. and no sample was found positive as in the year 2007. Out of the 89 sample units, each containing 25g of table eggs that were sampled and examined at packing centres or at retail level, no sample was tested positive for salmonella. 2 out of 49 (4%) samples from liquid egg products, were found positive (both *S. Enteritidis*).

Table 5 Salmonella spp. in poultry meat and meat products

Categories	Sampling stage	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	S. Hadar	S. Infantis	S. Kentucky	S. Kottbus	S. Montevideo	S. Newport	S. Ohio	S. Saintpaul	S. Senftenberg	S. Agona	S. Derby	S. Indiana	
Meat from broilers - carcass - spent hens	at slaughterhouse	single	100 cm ² skin	10	10	10														
Meat from broilers - carcass (EU baseline survey)	at slaughterhouse	single	25 g skin	408	10	2	1		1	1		4				1				
Meat from broilers - fresh	at catering	single	25 g	11	0															
	at cutting plant	single	25 g	64	0															
	at retail	single	25 g	278	22	3	4	2	3						1	4	1	2	1	1
		single	100 cm ² skin	6	1												1			
Meat from broilers - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail	single	25 g	180	10	6		2	2											
Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh	at processing plant	single	25 g	12	0															
	at retail	single	25 g	34	1		1													
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at catering	single	10 g	22	0															
	at processing plant	single	10 g	8	0															
	at retail	single	10 g	53	3	2		1												
		single	25 g	13	0															
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at catering	single	25 g	5	0															
	at processing plant	single	25 g	7	0															
	at retail	single	25 g	27	0															
Meat from turkey - fresh	at catering	single	25 g	7	1								1							
	at cutting plant	single	25 g	6	0															
	at retail	single	25 g	21	4		2				1				1					

Table 6 Salmonella spp. in red meat and products thereof

Categories	Sampling stage	Sampling unit	Sampling weight		Units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	S. group B, monophasic strain	S. Dublin	S. Infantis
Meat from bovine animals - fresh	at retail	single	25	g	15	0					
Meat from bovine animals - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	single	25	g	24	0					
Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at catering	single	10	g	10	0					
	at retail	single	10	g	28	0					
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	single	10	g	47	0					
Meat from deer (venison) - fresh	at retail	single	25	g	9	0					
Meat from other animal species or not specified	at catering	single	10	g	7	0					
	at processing plant	single	10	g	9	1					1
	at retail	single	10	g	18	1					1
Meat from pig - fresh	at catering	single	25	g	4	0					
	at processing plant	single	10	g	2	0					
	at retail	single	25	g	24	0					
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at catering	single	10	g	20	0					
	at processing plant	single	10	g	4	0					
	at retail	single	10	g	68	0					
		single	25	g	22	0					
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at catering	single	25	g	29	0					
	at processing plant	single	25	g	35	0					
	at retail	single	10	g	12	0					
		single	25	g	49	1			1		
Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at processing plant	single	25	g	5	0					
Meat from pig - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	single	10	g	8	0					
Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant	single	10	g	2	0					
	at retail	single	10	g	5	0					
Meat from rabbit - fresh	at game handling establishment	single	25	g	1	0					
Meat from sheep - meat preparation	at retail	single	10	g	8	0					
Meat from wild boar - fresh	at game handling establishment	single	25	g	1	0					

Salmonellosis

Categories	Sampling stage	Sampling unit	Sampling weight		Units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	S. group B, monophasic strain	S. Dublin	S. Infantis
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at catering	single	10	g	3	0					
	at processing plant	single	10	g	8	0					
	at retail	single	10	g	107	2		1		1	
		single	25	g	12	0					
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages	at catering	single	25	g	3	0					
	at farm	single	25	g	3	0					
	at processing plant	single	25	g	25	1	1				
	at retail	single	25	g	31	0					

Table 7 *Salmonella* spp. in milk and dairy products

Categories	Sampling stage	Sampling unit	Sampling weight		Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at farm	single	25	g	12	0
	at processing plant	single	25	g	153	0
	at retail	single	25	g	92	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at farm	single	25	g	15	0
	at processing plant	single	25	g	215	0
	at retail	single	25	g	31	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	single	25	g	15	0
	at retail	single	25	g	21	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	single	25	g	41	0
	at retail	single	25	g	24	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter	at processing plant	single	25	g	40	0
	at retail	single	25	g	27	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	at processing plant	single	25	g	103	0
	at retail	single	25	g	21	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream	at catering	single	25	g	207	0
	at farm	single	25	g	10	0
	at processing plant	single	25	g	446	0
	at retail	single	25	g	348	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - made from pasteurised milk (Campaign A-010-08)	at retail	single	25	g	130	0
Dairy products - cream	at retail	single	25	g	88	0
Dairy products - cream - made from pasteurised milk (Campaign A-029-08)	at catering	single	25	g	96	0
Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk	at processing plant	single	25	g	41	0
	at retail	single	25	g	6	0
Milk, cows' - raw	at farm	single	25	g	10	0
	at retail	single	25	g	4	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	at farm	single	25	g	2	0
	at processing plant	single	25	g	3	0
	at retail	single	25	g	3	0

Table 8 Salmonella spp. in other food

Categories	Sampling stage	Sampling unit	Sampling weight		Units tested.	Total units positive for Salmonella spp	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	S. Gustavia	S. Infantis
Bakery products - cakes	at retail	single	25	g	101	0				
Bakery products - pastry	at retail	single	25	g	160	0				
Chocolate	at retail	single	25	g	44	0				
Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea	at retail	single	25	g	17	0				
Crustaceans	at retail	single	25	g	22	0				
Egg products	at packing centre	single	25	g	4	0				
	at processing plant	single	25	g	18	0				
Egg products - dried	at retail	single	25	g	2	0				
Egg products - liquid	at retail	single	25	g	14	0				
	at processing plant	single	25	g	35	2	2			
Eggs - table eggs	at catering	single	25	g	4	0				
	at packing centre	single	25	g	14	0				
	at processing plant	single	25	g	4	0				
	at retail	single	25	g	53	0				
		single	5	eggs	14	0				
Fish - raw	at retail	single	25	g	15	0				
	at processing plant	single	25	g	2	0				
Fishery products, unspecified	at retail	single	25	g	14	0				
	at processing plant	single	25	g	10	0				
Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses	at retail	single	25	g	2	0				
Fruits	at retail	single	25	g	3	0				
Fruits - products	at retail	single	25	g	44	0				
Infant formula	at retail	single	25	g	12	0				
Juice - fruit juice	at processing plant	single	25	g	22	0				

Categories	Sampling stage	Sampling unit	Sampling weight		Units tested.	Total units positive for Salmonella spp	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	S. Gustavia	S. Infantis
Mushrooms	at retail	single	25	g	3	0				
Nuts and nut products	at retail	single	25	g	13	0				
Other food	at catering	single	25	g	323	0				
		single	50	g	42	0				
	at processing plant	single	25	g	74	0				
	at retail	single	25	g	139	2		1		1
Other food of non-animal origin	at retail	single	25	g	24	0				
	at processing plant	single	25	g	16	0				
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta	at retail	single	25	g	106	0				
	at processing plant	single	25	g	140	0				
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat - chilled (Campaign A-804-08)	at retail	single	25	g	105	0				
Ready-to-eat salads	at catering	single	50	g	7	0				
	at processing plant	single	25	g	16	0				
	at retail	single	25	g	33	0				
Sauces and dressings	at catering	single	25	g	6	0				
Spices and herbs	at retail	single	25	g	33	0				
Sweets	at retail	single	25	g	2	0				
Vegetables	at processing plant	single	25	g	9	0				
	at retail	single	25	g	20	1			1	
Vegetables - products	at retail	single	25	g	19	0				
	at processing plant	single	25	g	3	0				
Water	at catering	single	25	g	1	0				

4.1.4. Salmonella spp. in animals

A. Salmonella spp. in Gallus gallus - breeding flocks for egg production and flocks of laying hens

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are only parent flocks in Austria. The permanent monitoring plan performed by a national program takes place at hatcheries; each flock is tested regularly as well by the farmer as by the Veterinary Authorities.

If *S. Enteritidis*, *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Pullorum Gallinarum* or *S. Arizonae* is isolated from breeding flocks at the hatchery the flock is banned and a sample of 20 birds at random from within the incriminated flock has to be taken. The inner organs, such as ovaries, liver and the intestinal content is investigated.

If a parent flock tests positive for other salmonellas, official veterinarians are required to take pooled feces samples from the flock being investigated. In the event of a second positive result for *Salmonella* spp. within a two week period, then organs from a minimum of 20 chickens must be tested.

Since April 30, 2007 the EU-Regulation 2005/1003 is in force. Additional *Salmonella* serotypes have been included in the national program: *S. Infantis*, *S. Hadar* and *S. Virchow*.

Laying hens flocks

At the earliest 3 weeks prior to slaughter, two pairs of boot swabs must be taken from each flock. Since May 2007, every flock has been tested in accordance to regulation 1168/2006.

Frequency of the sampling

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Every flock is tested at day one

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

1. Routine testing: Every flock is tested at the age of 4 and 12 weeks and 2 weeks before the laying period starts.

2. Confirmation: If routine testing reveals positive *Salmonella* test results then follow-up test must be performed from the identical flock.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Monitoring by national program, takes place at hatchery, each flock is tested every two weeks at hatch by the farmer, and every 16 weeks by the Veterinary Authorities; additionally each flock is tested every 4 weeks by the farmer by boot swabs.

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Other: No legal requirements, e.g. at day one of each flock

Laying hens: Rearing period

3 times at day one, week 8 to 12 and 2 weeks before the laying period start

Laying hens: Production period

Each flock is tested every 15 weeks with two pairs of boot swabs; an official veterinarian is testing every flock once a year according to regulation 1168/2006.

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Other: 3 weeks before slaughter at farm with two pairs of boot swabs

Laying hens: At slaughter

Other: Not applicable. no sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Other: according to the program of the cooperatives voluntary surface swabs (e.g. every eight weeks)

Type of specimen taken

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Routine testing: drag swabs, pooled feces. For confirmation: organs as ovaries, liver and intestinal content from a minimum of 20 chickens.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Routine testing: Drag swabs, pooled feces and dust in the hatchery, meconium, broken eggshells and hatched eggs. For confirmation: 300 feces samples and up to inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Laying hens: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces

Laying hens: Production period

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces or drag swabs

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Other: two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: At slaughter

Other: no sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Other: Voluntary e.g. surface swabs

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Routine testing: 60 pooled droppings a 1gram per flock, collection of dust. For confirmation: Diagnostically killing of 20 random chickens from within the incriminated flock

Breeding flocks: Production period

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Routine testing: 1 drag swab, pooled feces, collection of dust. For confirmation: Diagnostically killing of 20 random chickens from within the incriminated flock

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Laying hens: Rearing period

2 pair of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: Production period

2 pair of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: At slaughter

No sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

No legal requirements, e.g. surface swabs

Case definition

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Routine testing: Salmonella spp. isolated from hatcher basket liners

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Salmonella spp. isolated from inner organs or from content of intestines of chickens killed for diagnosis

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Salmonella spp. isolated from inner organs or from content of intestines of chicken

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements, e.g. Salmonella spp. isolated from hatcher basket liners

Laying hens: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Laying hens: Production period

No legal requirements

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Laying hens: At slaughter

No sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Salmonella spp. isolated from surface swabs

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5 +/- 1°C for 24 or 48 hours. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are phage-typed according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

Other: See day old chicks

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

Other: See day old chicks

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Other: Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5 +/- 1 °C for 24 or 48 hours. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are phage-typed according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

Laying hens: Rearing period

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Laying hens: Production period

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Laying hens: At slaughter

Other: no testing

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Vaccination policy

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! The national program for parent flocks made vaccination against Salmonella mandatory for all flocks

Laying hens flocks

The national program made vaccination against Salmonella enteritidis mandatory for all flocks

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Nil

Laying hens flocks

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. I Nr. 6/2007, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 of April 30th, 2007). The Austrian program for monitoring and eradication of Salmonella in breeding flocks of poultry was again (already since 2000) approved for the year 2006 by Commission Decision 2005/887/EG of 12 December 2005.

Laying hens flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. I Nr. 6/2007, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 of April 30th, 2007).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Measures according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation:

- Banning of the incriminated sector of the holding
- Culling of the infected flock
- Disposal of the hatched eggs
- Abolishing of the restriction after cleaning and disinfection
- If necessary prescriptions of GMP to prevent re-infection

Laying hens flocks

No class A eggs

Notification system in place

All positive results from parent flocks must be reported to the local authorities and via the Austrian Poultry Health Service to the Federal Ministry of Health (BMG).

Results of the investigation

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2008, *Salmonella* spp. was not detected in any parent flock.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

B. *Salmonella* spp. in *Gallus gallus* - breeding flocks for meat production and broiler flocks

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are only parent flocks in Austria. The national permanent monitoring program takes place at a hatchery; each flock is tested regularly as well by the farmer as by the Veterinary Authority. If *S. Enteritidis*, *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Pullorum Gallinarum* and *S. Arizonae* is isolated from breeding flocks at the hatchery the flock is banned and a sample of 20 birds at random from within the incriminated flock has to be taken. The inner organs, such as ovaries, liver and the intestinal content is investigated. If a parent flock tests positive for other salmonellae, official veterinarians are required to take pooled feces samples from the flock being investigated. In the event of a second positive result for *Salmonella* spp. within a two week period, then organs from a minimum of 20 chickens must be tested.

Broiler flocks

Earliest 3 weeks prior to slaughter boot swabs have to be taken. Other programs are not foreseen, only voluntary sampling by the farmer or sampling according to private cooperatives is performed.

Frequency of the sampling

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Every flock is tested at day one.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
1. Routine testing: Every flock is tested at the age of 4 and 12 weeks and 2 weeks before the laying period starts; 2. Confirmation: If *Salmonella* was isolates from day old chicks.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Monitoring by national program, takes place at hatchery, each flock is tested every two weeks at hatch by the farmer, and every 6 weeks by the Veterinary Authority; additional each flock is tested every 4 weeks by the farmer by boot swabs.

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. at day one each flock

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: 3 weeks before slaughter at farm

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: No sampling

Type of specimen taken

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: drag swabs, pooled feces; for confirmation: organs as ovaries, liver and intestinal content from a minimum of 20 chickens.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: Drag swabs, pooled feces, dust in the hatchery, meconium, broken eggshells and hatched eggs; for confirmation: Inner organs as ovaries, liver and intestinal content from a minimum of 20 chickens. Inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: two pairs of boot swabs per flock per flock

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: No sampling

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

Routine testing: 60 pooled droppings a 1 gram per flock, collection of dust. For confirmation:

Diagnostically killing of 20 random chickens from within the incriminated flock.

Breeding flocks: Production period

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Routine testing: 1 drag swab, pooled feces, collection of dust For confirmation: Diagnostically killing of 20 random chickens from within the incriminated flock

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements, e.g. 60 pooled droppings a 1 gram per flock

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Case definition

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Routine testing: Salmonella spp. isolated from hatcher basket liners and dead chicks if available

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Salmonella spp. isolated from inner organs or from content of intestines of chickens killed for diagnosis.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Salmonella spp. isolated from inner organs or from content of intestines of chicken

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5 +/- 1 °C for 24 or 48 hours. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are phage-typed according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

Other: See day-old chicks

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

Other: See day-old chicks

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: See day-old chicks

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Other: See day-old chicks

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: See day-old chicks

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: no testing

Vaccination policy

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! The national program for parent flocks made vaccination against Salmonella mandatory for all flocks

Broiler flocks

Neither legal requirements nor recommendations

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Broiler flocks

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. I Nr. 6/2007, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 of April 30th, 2007). The Austrian program for monitoring and eradication of Salmonella in breeding flocks of poultry was again (already since 2000) approved for the year 2006 by Commission Decision 2005/887/EG of 12 December 2005.

Broiler flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. I Nr. 6/2007, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 of April 30th, 2007)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Measures according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation:

- Banning of the incriminated sector of the holding
- Culling of the infected flock
- Disposal of the hatched eggs
- Abolishing of the restriction after cleaning and disinfection
- If necessary prescriptions of GMP to prevent re-infection

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

See day-old chicks.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

See day-old chicks.

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Flocks were treated either with antimicrobials or competitive exclusion strategies takes place.

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Flocks were treated either with antimicrobials or competitive exclusion strategies takes place.

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Flocks were treated either with antimicrobials or competitive exclusion strategies takes place. Slaughtering was only permitted for Salmonella spp. negative flocks.

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No testing

Notification system in place

All positive findings in parent flocks had to be notified to the local authority and via the Austrian Poultry Health Service to the Federal Ministry of Health and Women.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2008, Salmonella spp. was not detected in any parent flock.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil.

C. Salmonella spp. in turkey - breeding flocks and meat production flocks

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are no breeding flocks in Austria

Meat production flocks

Earliest 3 weeks prior to slaughter boot swabs have to be taken. Other programs are not foreseen, only voluntary sampling by the farmer or sampling according to private cooperatives is performed.

Frequency of the sampling

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. at day one each flock

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: 3 weeks before slaughter at farm

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: No sampling

Type of specimen taken

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: two pairs of boot swabs per flock per flock

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: no sampling

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

No flocks in Austria

Day-old chicks

No legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

No legal requirements, e.g. 60 pooled droppings a 1 gram per flock

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

No sampling

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Case definition

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary) Rearing period

No flocks in Austria

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

No flocks in Austria

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5 +/- 1 °C for 24 or 48 hours.

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

Other: see day-old chicks

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: see day-old chicks

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: see day-old chicks

Vaccination policy

Meat production flocks

Neither legal requirements nor recommendations

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Meat production flocks

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Meat production flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. I Nr. 6/2007, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 of April 30th, 2007).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Notification not mandatory

Notification system in place

Notification not mandatory

D. Salmonella spp. in animal - Pigs - breeding animals - unspecified - at farm - animal sample - faeces - Survey - EU baseline survey

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Out of 2,866 breeding pig holdings 238 plus 10% were randomly chosen stratified by size according to the number of holdings in the different provinces.

Frequency of the sampling

The date of sampling was distributed equally over the year.

Type of specimen taken

Pooled feces samples per pen; 10 pens per holding.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Animals at farm

Feces was collected by the competent authority or under its supervision in accordance with the technical specifications

Case definition

Animals at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from one or more samples per holding

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Animals at farm

In accordance with the technical specifications

Vaccination policy

Neither legal requirements nor recommendations

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures in course of this survey

Notification system in place

No measures in course of this survey

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Very low prevalence of Salmonella spp. in Austrian breeding pigs holdings, only 15 out of 252 sampled holdings (6.0%)

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Due to the low prevalence pork plays a minor role as vehicle for salmonella infections in humans.

Table 9 *Salmonella* spp. in Poultry breeding flocks (*Gallus gallus*)

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Number of existing flocks	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	<i>S. Hadar</i>	<i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>S. Montevideo</i>	<i>S. Virchow</i>
Egg production line														
Breeding flocks														
	Elite													
	Grandparents													
	Parents	at farm - animal sample - faeces	control or eradication programmes - cofinanced by Community - official and industry sampling	QGV	flock	24	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Day-old chicks													
	Rearing period	at farm - animal sample - faeces	control or eradication programmes - cofinanced by Community - official and industry sampling	QGV	flock	7	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Production period	at farm - animal sample - faeces	control or eradication programmes - cofinanced by Community - official and industry sampling	QGV	flock	17	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat production line														
Breeding flocks														
	Elite													
	Grandparents													
	Parents	at farm - animal sample - faeces	control or eradication programmes - cofinanced by Community - official and industry sampling	QGV	flock	91	91	2	0	0	0	0	2	0
	Day-old chicks													
	Rearing period	at farm - animal sample - faeces	control or eradication programmes - cofinanced by Community - official and industry sampling	QGV	flock	56	56	2	0	0	0	0	2	0
	Production period	at farm - animal sample - faeces	control or eradication programmes - cofinanced by Community - official and industry sampling	QGV	flock	35	35	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

QGV = Austrian Health Poultry Service

Table 10 Salmonella spp. in other commercial poultry

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Source of information	Sampling unit	Numbr of existing flocks	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	<i>S. Agona</i>	<i>S. Braenderup</i>	<i>S. Hadar</i>	<i>S. Indiana</i>	<i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>S. Jerusalem</i>	<i>S. Kentucky</i>	<i>S. Kottbus</i>	<i>S. Lexington</i>	<i>S. Livingstone</i>	<i>S. London</i>	<i>S. Meleagridis</i>	<i>S. Montevideo</i>	<i>S. Ohio</i>	<i>S. Regent</i>	<i>S. Rissen</i>	<i>S. Saintpaul</i>	<i>S. Schwarzengrund</i>	<i>S. Senftenberg</i>	<i>S. Thompson</i>	<i>S. Worthington</i>	Paratyph. Java	<i>S. unspecified</i>
Gallus gallus																																
Laying hens																																
	Day-old chicks	at hatchery	Surveillance - official control - census sampling	QGV	batch	811	0	0	0																							
	Rearing period	at farm - animal sample - feces	Control or eradication programme - sampling by industry - census sampling	QGV	flock	657	470	12	5	1							1	1			1						3					
	Production period	at farm - animal sample - feces	Control or eradication programme - sampling by industry - census sampling	QGV	flock	1966	1966	49	23	4	2	1			8					1			5			1	1	1	1			2
	Production period	at farm - animal sample - feces	Control or eradication programme - official sampling - objective sampling	QGV	flock	1966	1088	33	16	7	1				5				1	1							1				1	
	Production period	at farm - animal sample - feces	Control or eradication programme - official sampling - suspect sampling	QGV	flock	1966	4	0																								
Broilers																																
	Day-old chicks	at hatchery	Surveillance - official control - census sampling	QGV	batch	1291	1291	3	2													1										
	Rearing period	at farm - animal sample - feces	Surveillance - official control - census sampling	QGV	flock	3099	3099	178	32	7	3	2	2	2	4	1	2	2				5	105				3	1	4	1	1	1
Ducks																																
	Breeding flocks																															
	Meat production flocks	at farm - animal sample - feces	Surveillance - official control - census sampling	QGV	flock	66	66	15	1	2				4			1					3		2	1		1					
Geese																																
	Breeding flocks																															
	Meat production flocks	at farm - animal sample - feces	Surveillance - official control - census sampling	QGV	flock	62	62	4	0	2				2																		
Turkeys																																
	Breeding flocks																															
	Meat production flocks	at farm - animal sample - feces	Surveillance - official control - census sampling	QGV	flock	325	325	30	2	0			2					1					6				16	3				

QGV = Austrian Health Poultry Service

Table 11 Salmonella in other animals

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	S. Bredeney	S. Derby	S. Dublin	S. Indiana	S. Infantis	S. Livingstone	S. Mbandaka	S. Montevideo	S. Muenchen	S. Suarez II	Salmonellen IIIb	S. Koketime	S. Tennessee	Monoph.Stamm d.S.B-Gr	
Cattle	animal sample - organ	clinical investigation	animal	3455	25	2	7			16												
	animal sample - feces	clinical investigation	animal	390	11	1				10												
Sheep	animal sample - organ	clinical investigation	animal	83	6					1									5			
Sheep	animal sample - feces	clinical investigation	animal	3	0																	
Goats	animal sample - organ	clinical investigation	animal	17	1							1										
Goats	animal sample - feces	clinical investigation	animal	2	0																	
Pigs																						
	Sampling in the framework of the breeding pig baseline survey	at farm - animal sample - feces	survey - EU baseline survey	holding	252	15	0	3	1	2		1	1	2	1	2	1					1
	pigs, unspecified	animal sample - organ	clinical investigation	animal	381	6		4		2												
	pigs, unspecified	animal sample - feces	clinical investigation	animal	143	18	1	7				1										9
Domestic solipeds				22	0																	
Other animal species (please add the relevant species)																						
	alpine chamois	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	6	0																
	badger	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	1	1		1														
	blackbird	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	1	0																
	capricorn	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	1	0																
	cat	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	51	1		1														
	common snipe	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	1	0																
	deer	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	28	0																
	dog	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	30	0																
	eagle	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	1	0																
	fallow deer	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	3	0																

Salmonellosis

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	S. Bredeney	S. Derby	S. Dublin	S. Indiana	S. Infantis	S. Livingstone	S. Mbandaka	S. Montevideo	S. Muenchen	S. Suarez II	Salmonellen IIIb	S. Koketime	S. Tennessee	Monoph. Stamm d.S.B-Gr	
finch	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	3	0																	
guinea pig	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	4	0																	
hare	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	1	0																	
monkey	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	1	0																	
mouse	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	3	0																	
parrot	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	6	0																	
rabbit	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	45	0																	
red deer	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	3	1		1															
reptile	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	2	0																	
saurian	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	2	2															1	1	
siskin	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	2	2		2															
sittich	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	5	0																	
snake	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	3	0																	
squirrel	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	1	0																	
turtle	animal sample	clinical investigation	animal	3	1							1										

4.1.5. Salmonella spp. in feedstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is performed without regional criteria. The sampling is carried out by competent authorities; the samples were taken on farms, slaughterhouses, processing plants, retailers. The sampling is part of the national permanent monitoring program.

Frequency of the sampling

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Other: The sampling plan is assigned and the tests are evenly distributed throughout the year. Every farm, processing plant, and retailer is sampled at least twice per year. The final product is then inspected. Discrepancies within reported batches lead to further testing.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Other: See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

Other: See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

Other: See above

Process control in feed mills

Other: See above

Compound feeding stuffs

Other: See above

Type of specimen taken

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Oil seed meals and cakes

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Fish meal, dried animal by-products for pets

Imported feed material of plant origin

Oil seed meals and cakes

Imported feed material of animal origin

Fish meal, dried animal by-products for pets

Process control in feed mills

Not applicable (n. a.)

Compound feeding stuffs

Feed for poultry

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Sampling is performed according EC-Directive 76/371/EEC applying special hygiene requirements or sampling of original packaged products.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

See above

Process control in feed mills

See above

Compound feeding stuffs

See above

Definition of positive finding**Domestic feed material of plant origin**

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Imported feed material of plant origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Imported feed material of animal origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Process control in feed mills

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Compound feeding stuffs

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Diagnostic/analytical methods used**Domestic feed material of plant origin**

Bacteriological method: ISO 6579:2002; sample weight: 50 g; all isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are phage typed according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Other: as above

Imported feed material of plant animal

Other: as above

Imported feed material of animal origin

Other: as above

Process control in feed mills

Other: as above

Compound feeding stuffs

Other: as above

Control program/mechanisms**The control program/strategies in place**

National legislation: BGBl. Nr. 139/1999 (Futtermittelgesetz 1999, § 3) and BGBl. Nr. 93/2000 (Futtermittelverordnung 2000, as amended) containing general requirements for feedingstuffs and BGBl. II Nr. 243/2000 (Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2000).

EC: VO (EG) 183/2005 (Futtermittelhygieneverordnung) and VO (EG) 882/2004 (Kontrollverordnung) with regard to salmonella monitoring, general requirements for feed material and compound feed, coordinated annual control program

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings**Domestic feed material of plant origin**

In the event of a positive result, the notification results in the confiscation of the infected feedingstuffs according to official measures. This includes the withdrawal of the feedingstuffs from the market, the recall of feed, decontamination of the feed, disposal or other use of the feed, exploration and elimination of the sources of contamination and operational measures to prevent future contaminations.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

See above

Process control in feed mills

See above

Compound feeding stuffs

See above

Notification system in place

The Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) notifies the local authorities and the system has been in place since 1979. The legal basis of the RASFF is Regulation EC/178/2002.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the last 20 years, the quality of feed has improved due to the increase of numbers of farms, processing plants and retailer using HACCP concepts, traceability of contaminated feed/components of feed and palletizing feed/contaminated feed.

Additional information

Nil

Table 12 Salmonella spp. in other feed matter

Categories	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	<i>S. Montevideo</i>	<i>S. Putten</i>	<i>S. Lexington</i>	<i>S. Mbandaka</i>	
Feed material of cereal grain origin															
Barley and derived															
Wheat and derived	retail domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	3	0							
Maize															
Maize derived															
Other															
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin															
Groundnut derived															
Rape seed derived															
---Rape seed derived	retail domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	19	0							
---Rape seed derived	feed mill domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	2	0							
---Rape seed derived	process plant	1)		2)	batch	50 g	1	0							
Palm kernel derived															
Soya (bean) derived															
---Soya (bean) derived	retail domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	68	4			1	1	1	1	
---Soya (bean) derived	feed mill domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	7	0							
---Soya (bean) derived	process plant	1)		2)	batch	50 g	4	0							
Cotton seed derived															
Sunflower seed derived															
---Sunflower seed derived	retail domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	1	0							
---Sunflower seed derived	process plant	1)		2)	batch	50 g	1	0							
Linseed derived															
---Linseed derived	retail domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	9	0							
---Linseed derived	feed mill domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	1	0							
Other oil seeds derived															
---Other oil seeds derived	retail domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	7	0							
---Other oil seeds derived	feed mill domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	1	0							
Other feed material of plant origin															
Legume seeds, ...															
Tubers, roots, ...	retail domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	1	0							
Other seeds and fruits															
Forages and roughage	retail domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	2	0							
Other plants, ...	retail domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	1	0							

1) Control or eradication programmes: national programmes (no Community co-financing), official sampling

2) Compulsory monitoring programmes (Futtermittel-Gesetz 1999)

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Table 13 Salmonella spp. in compound feeding stuff

Categories	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	S. Livingstone	S. Cerro	S. Derby	S. Bredeney	S. Montevideo	S. Jerusalem	Monoph. Stamm d. S. B-Gruppe	S. enterica subsp. Enterica, rough
Compound feedingstuffs for cattle																		
Process control																		
Final product	retail domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	19	0										
Final product	feed mill domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	5	0										
Final product	at Farm	1)		2)	batch	50 g	6	0										
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs																		
Process control																		
Final product	retail domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	47	0										
Final product	feed mill domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	10	0										
Final product	at Farm	1)		2)	batch	50 g	6	1							1			
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry																		
Poultry (not specified)																		
Process control																		
Final product	retail domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	10	0										
Final product	feed mill domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	2	0										
Final product	at Farm	1)		2)	batch	50 g	1	0										
Poultry - Breeders																		
Process control																		
Final product	retail domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	6	0										
Final product	feed mill domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	2	0										
Poultry - Laying hens																		
Process control																		
Final product	retail domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	71	0										
Final product	feed mill domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	5	0										
Final product	at Farm	1)		2)	batch	50 g	51	1								1		
Poultry - Broiler																		
Process control																		
Final product	retail domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	33	0										
Final product	feed mill domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	7	0										
Final product	at Farm	1)		2)	batch	50 g	16	0										
Pet food																		
Compound feedingstuffs	retail domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	3	0										
Dog snacks (pigs ears, chewing bones)																		
--- Dog snacks (pigs ears, chewing bones)	retail domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	31	6	1	1	1			1			1	1
--- Dog snacks (pigs ears, chewing bones)	retail imported	1)		2)	batch	50 g	1	0										
--- Dog snacks (pigs ears, chewing bones)	process plant	1)		2)	batch	50 g	4	1					1					
Other compound feedingstuffs (please specify the categories)																		
fish feed	retail domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	3	0										
other feed	retail domestic	1)		2)	batch	50 g	19	0										

1) Control or eradication programmes: national programmes (no Community co-financing), official sampling

2) Compulsory monitoring programmes (Futtermittel-Gesetz 1999)

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Table 14 *Salmonella* spp. in feed material of animal origin

Categories	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>S.</i> Enteritidis	<i>S.</i> Typhimurium	<i>S.</i> Montevideo	
Milk products												
Feed material of land animal origin												
Meat meal	process plant	1)	2)	batch	50 g		1	1			1	
Meat and bone meal												
Bone meal												
Greaves												
Poultry offal meal												
Feather meal												
Blood meal												
Animal fat												
Feed material of marine animal origin												
Fish meal												
--- Fish meal	retail domestic	1)	2)	batch	50 g		9	0				
--- Fish meal	feed mill domestic	1)	2)	batch	50 g		1	0				
Fish oil												
Fish silage												
Other fish products												

1) Control or eradication programmes: national programmes (no Community co-financing), official sampling

2) Compulsory monitoring programmes (Futtermittel-Gesetz 1999)

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4.1.6. Salmonella serovars and phage type distribution

The methods of collecting, isolating and testing of the Salmonella isolates are described in the chapters above respectively for each animal species, foodstuffs and in humans. The serotype and phage type distributions can be used to investigate the sources of the Salmonella infections in humans. Findings of same serovars and phagetypes in human cases and in foodstuffs or animals may indicate that the food category or animal species in question serves as a source of human infections. However, as information is not available from all potential sources of infections, conclusions have to be made with caution.

Table 15 Salmonella serovars in food

Serovars	N=	Bovine meat	Pig meat	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus)	turkey meat
Source of isolates					
Number of isolates in the laboratory	N=	2	4	83	33
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped	N=	2	4	83	33
Number of isolates per serovar					
S. Enteritidis				26	1
S. Infantis				24	3
S. Saintpaul				1	9
S. Montevideo				9	
S. Hadar				2	6
S. Typhimurium			3	1	4
S. Bredeney				2	2
S. Gallinarum				4	
S. Group L H- (21 : - : -)				3	
S. Senftenberg				3	
Monophasic S.Group C1 (6,7 : - : 1,2)				1	1
Monophasic S.Group B (1,4,12 : d : -)					2
S. Agona				2	
S. Banana					1
S. Blockley				1	
S. Derby					1
S. Indiana				1	
S. Kottbus					1
S. Livingstone				1	
S. Newport					1
S. Ohio				1	
S. Panama					1
S. Paratyphi B var. Java				1	
Monophasic S.Group B (1,4,5,12 : i : -)		2	1		

Table 16 Salmonella serovars in animals

Serovars	Cattle		Pigs		Gallus gallus, fowl		Turkey	
	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical
Number of isolates in the laboratory	N=	51	69	570	128			
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped	N=	51	69	570	128			
Number of isolates per serovar								
S. Enteritidis	4	1	234	14				
S. Montevideo	1	2	128	10				
S. Saintpaul	2	3	16	68				
S. Typhimurium	8	20	38					
S. Infantis		3	38					
S. Dublin	32							
S. Senftenberg			22	5				
S. Hadar			8	19				
S. Bredeney		1	11					
Monoph.Stamm d.S.B-Gruppe			12					
S. Derby			11					
S. Livingstone			9					
S. Agona			9					
S. Kottbus			5	4				
S. I Rauhform			8					
S. Meleagridis			8					
S. Kentucky			7					
S. Indiana	1	2	4					
S. Newport				7				
S. Braenderup			5					
S. Thompson			5					
S. IIIb 38 : r : z			3					
S. Regent			3					
Geißell. Stamm d. B-Gr.			2					
S. London			2					
S. Paratyphi B var. Java			2					
S. IIIb 61 : k : 1,5,7			1					
S. Jerusalem			1	1				
S. Mbandaka			1	1				
S. Tennessee			1	1				
S. Worthington	1		1					
S. Mikawasima	2							
S. Muenchen			2					
S. Anatum			1					
S. Liverpool			1					
S. Ohio			1					
S. Rissen			1					
S. Schwarzengrund			1					
S. Virchow			1					

Table 17 S. Enteritidis phage types in humans

Phagetypes <i>S. Enteritidis</i>		humans	
Source of isolates		monitor.	clinical
Number of isolates in the laboratory	N=	2200	
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped	N=	2200	
Number of isolates per type			
PT4		772	
PT8		524	
PT21		412	
PT6		125	
PT1		80	
PT13a		46	
PT14b		45	
RDNC		44	
PT2		20	
PT6a		18	
PT1b		15	
PT12		14	
PT5		13	
PT13		11	
PT4b		11	
PT3		9	
PT7		9	
PT35		5	
PT11		4	
PT1c		4	
PTU		4	
PT23		3	
PT29		2	
PT11b		2	
PT6b		2	
PT34		1	
PT44		1	
PT1d		1	
PT5a		1	
PT6c		1	
PT7a		1	

Table 18 S. Enteritidis phage types in food

Phagetypes <i>S. Enteritidis</i>		Bovine meat	Pig meat	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus)	turkey meat	other (please specify)
Source of isolates						
Number of isolates in the laboratory	N=			26	1	
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped	N=			26	1	
Number of isolates per type						
	PT4			10		
	PT8			10		
	PT23			3		
	PT1			1		
	PT6			1		
	PT21				1	
	PT13a			1		

Table 19 S. Enteritidis phage types in animals

Phagetypes <i>S. Enteritidis</i>		Cattle		Pigs		Gallus gallus (fowl)		Turkey	
Source of isolates		monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical
Number of isolates in the laboratory	N=	4		1		234		14	
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped	N=	4		1		234		14	
Number of isolates per type									
	PT4	1		1		97			
	PT8	1				46		10	
	PT21					28			
	PT7					21			
	PT1					15			
	PT6	2				6			
	RDNC					7			
	PT23					3		2	
	PT14b					1		2	
	PT5					2			
	PT6a					2			
	PT6b					2			
	PTU					2			
	PT12					1			
	PT21c					1			

Table 20 S. Typhimurium definitive types in humans

S. Typhimurium definitive types	Humans	
	monitor.	clinical
Source of isolates		
Number of isolates in the laboratory		374
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped		374
Number of isolates per type		
DT8		3
DT1		9
RDNC		64
DT12		3
DT3		7
DTU		8
DT41		61
DT43		1
DT85		22
DT99		1
DT120		71
DT125		1
DT129		1
DT135		1
DT136		1
DT166		3
DT193		21
DT208		2
DT104H		16
DT104L		70
DT193A		1
DTU302		7

Table 21 S. Typhimurium definitive types in food

S. Typhimurium definitive types	N=	Bovine meat	Pig meat	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus)	turkey meat
Source of isolates					
Number of isolates in the laboratory		0	3	1	4
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped		0	3	1	4
Number of isolates per type					
DT104L			1		2
RDNC			1	1	1
DT U					1
DT120			1		

Table 22 S. Typhimurium definitive types in animals

S. Typhimurium definitive types	Cattle		Pigs		Gallus gallus, (fowl)		Turkey	
	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical	monitor.	clinical
Number of isolates in the laboratory	N=	8	20	38				
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped	N=	8	20	38				
Number of isolates per type								
DT1		3						
RDNC		1	2	4				
DTU			3					
DT41				8				
DT46		1						
DT85				3				
DT166				7				
DT193				1				
DT104H				15				
DT104L		3	15					

4.1.7. Antimicrobial resistance in *Salmonella* spp. isolates

Antimicrobial resistance is the ability of certain microorganisms to survive or grow in the presence of a given concentration of antimicrobial agent that usually would kill or inhibit the microorganism species in question. Antimicrobial resistant *Salmonella* strains may be transferred from animals or foodstuffs to humans.

A. Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. in humans

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The overall resistance-rates against antibiotics remained stable over the past years.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Although in 2008 an increase had been observed. This can be attributed on the one hand to a higher number of multiresistant *S. Typhimurium* strains on the other hand to an increase of *S. Enteritidis* resistant to nalidixic acid. High level resistances against Ciprofloxacin and third generation cephalosporins (Cefotaxime) were still extremely rare in comparison to rates reported within the EU.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional informationNil

B. Antimicrobial resistance of Salmonella spp. in animals and food

Sampling strategy used in monitoring**Frequency of the sampling**

There currently is no monitoring program in Austria but all Salmonella spp. isolated in veterinary and food laboratories, as well as all primary isolates from humans were sent to the NRC-S where the susceptibility testing was performed using the disk diffusion method.

Salmonella isolates from control programmes or baseline surveys although are subjected to MIC-testing; all strains isolated in the course of a survey and all unique strains (from one epidemiological unit) from control programmes.

Type of specimen taken

Clinical samples from humans; for animals and food see chapters Salmonella spp. in animal species and Salmonella spp. in food.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Clinical samples from humans; for animals and food see chapters Salmonella spp. in animal species and Salmonella spp. in food.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

All Salmonella spp. isolated in veterinary and food laboratories, as well as all primary isolates from humans were sent to the NRC-S where the susceptibility testing was performed using the disk diffusion method. All strains isolated in the course of a survey and all unique strains (from one epidemiological unit) of a control programm are used.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

See chapter salmonellosis in humans; for the MIC testing CLSI standards are used, applying EUCAST cut-off values.

Laboratory used for detection of resistance

National Reference Centre for Salmonella, AGES Graz

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

All Salmonella isolates were susceptibility tested (disc diffusion) according to CLSI. See corresponding tables! Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For Salmonella this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, Nalidixic acid, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazole.

Control program/mechanisms**Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses**

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

An EU standardized antimicrobial resistance monitoring system would be highly welcome.

Additional information

Nil

Table 23 Breakpoints for antibiotic resistance of Salmonella spp.

Test method used		Number of reporting laboratory:		1	
Disc diffusion	X CLSI				
E-test					
Agar dilution					
Broth dilution	X EUCAST				
Standards used for testing		The methods are used for investigation of isolates from			
CLSI	X	Feedingstuff		X	
other	X	Animals		X	
		Food		X	
		Humans		X	

<i>Salmonella</i>	Dilution method				Diffusion method				
	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Breakpoint concentration (µg/ml)		Range tested	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Disk content µg	Zone diameter (mm)		
		Resistant >	lowest	highest			Susceptible >=	intermediate	resistant <=
Tetracyclines									
Tetracycline	EUCAST	8	1	64	CLSI	30	15	12 - 14	11
Amphenicols									
Chloramphenicol	EUCAST	16	2	64	CLSI	30	18	13 - 17	12
Florfenicol	EUCAST	16	2	64					
Penicillins									
Ampicillin	EUCAST	4	0.5	32	CLSI	10	17	14 - 16	13
Cephalosporins									
Cefotaxim	EUCAST	0.5	0.06	4	CLSI	30	23	15 - 22	14
Ceftazidime	EUCAST	2	0.25	16					
Fluoroquinolones									
Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST	0.06	0.008	8	CLSI	5	21	16 - 20	15
Sulfonamides									
Sulfamethoxazol	EUCAST	256	8	1024	CLSI	300	17	13 - 16	12
Aminoglycosides									
Streptomycin	EUCAST	32	2	128	CLSI	10	15	12 - 14	11
Gentamicin	EUCAST	2	0.25	32	CLSI	10	15	13 - 14	12
Kanamycin	EUCAST	?	4	128	CLSI	30	18	14 - 17	13
Quinolones									
Nalidixic acid	EUCAST	16	4	64	CLSI	30	19	14 - 18	13
Polymyxine									
Colistin	EUCAST	8	8	16					
Trimethoprim	EUCAST	2	0.5	32	CLSI	5	16	11 - 15	10

Table 24 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* in humans, animals and food (diffusion method)

	S. Enteritidis																			
	Humans		broiler meat		turkey		bovine meat		pig meat		laying		broiler		turkeys		cattle		pigs	
Isolates out of a monitoring	no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no	
Number of isolates available in	2200		26		1		0		0		109		56		14		4		1	
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	%r	n	%r	n	%r	n	%r	n	%r	n	%r	n
Tetracyclines																				
Tetracycline	0,8	17	0	0	0	0					0	0	11	6	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amphenicols																				
Chloramphenicol	0,3	6	0	0	0	0					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Penicillins																				
Ampicillin	1,7	37	0	0	0	0					0	0	18	10	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cephalosporins																				
Cefotaxim	0,1	2	0	0	0	0					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fluoroquinolones																				
Ciprofloxacin	0,0	0	0	0	0	0					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sulfonamides																				
Sulfamethoxazol	0,6	13	0	0	0	0					0	0	13	7	0	0	0	0	0	0
Aminoglycosides																				
Streptomycin	0,4	8	0	0	0	0					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gentamicin	0,1	2	0	0							0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kanamycin	0,1	2	0	0	0	0					0	0	11	6	0	0	0	0	0	0
Quinolones																				
Nalidixic acid	13,8	304	27	7	0	0					6,4	7	80	45	0	0	0	0	0	0
Trimethoprim	0,5	10	0	0	0	0					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Number of multiresistant isolate	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n
fully sensitive	84,5	1860	73,1	19	100	1					93,6	102	19,6	11	100	14	100	4	100	1
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	14,0	308	26,9	7	0,0	0					6,4	7	51,8	29	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
resistant to 2 antimicrobial	0,7	15	0,0	0	0,0	0					0,0	0	5,4	3	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobial	0,5	11	0,0	0	0,0	0					0,0	0	14,3	8	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobial	0,1	2	0,0	0	0,0	0					0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobi	0,2	4	0,0	0	0,0	0					0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0

Table 25 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method)

	S. Typhimurium																			
	Humans		Broiler meat		Turkey meat		Bovine meat		Pig meat		Laying		Broiler		Turkeys		Cattle		Pigs	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	374		1		4		0		3		23		10		0		8		20	
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	%r	n	%r	n	%r	n	%r	n	%r	n
Tetracyclines																				
Tetracycline	44,9	168	0	0	75	3			100	3	0	0	0	0			38	3	90	18
Amphenicols																				
Chloramphenicol	27,3	102	0	0	50	2			100	3	0	0	0	0			38	3	80	16
Penicillins																				
Ampicillin	46,8	175	100	1	75	3			100	3	0	0	20	2			38	3	85	17
Cephalosporins																				
Cefotaxim	0,5	2	0	0	0	0			0	0	0	0	0	0			0	0	0	0
Fluoroquinolones																				
Ciprofloxacin	0,0	0	0	0	0	0			0	0	0	0	0	0			0	0	0	0
Sulfonamides																				
Sulfamethoxazol	43,9	164	100	1	75	3			100	3	0	0	0	0			0	0	85	17
Aminoglycosides																				
Streptomycin	39,6	148	0	0	75	3			100	3	0	0	0	0			38	3	85	17
Gentamicin	2,9	11	0	0	0	0			0	0	0	0	0	0			0	0	0	0
Kanamycin	3,2	12	0	0	0	0			33	1	0	0	0	0			0	0	10	2
Quinolones																				
Nalidixic acid	7,2	27	0	0	75	3			0	0	0	0	0	0			0	0	35	7
Trimethoprim	6,1	23	100	1	0	0			33	1	0	0	0	0			0	0	5	1
Number of multiresistant isolates*	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n
fully sensitive	48,7	182	0,0	0	25,0	1			0,0	0	100	23	80,0	8			62,5	5	10,0	2
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	5,6	21	0,0	0	0,0	0			0,0	0	0,0	0	20,0	2			0,0	0	5,0	1
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	2,1	8	0,0	0	0,0	0			0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0			0,0	0	0,0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	2,4	9	100	1	0,0	0			0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0			0,0	0	0,0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	9,6	36	0,0	0	0,0	0			0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0			0,0	0	0,0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	31,6	118	0,0	0	75,0	3			100	3	0,0	0	0,0	0			37,5	3	85,0	17

Table 26 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than Enteritidis and Typhimurium in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method)

	other serotypes than <i>S. Enteritidis</i> and <i>S. Typhimurium</i>																			
	Humans		Broiler		Turkey		Bovine meat		Pig meat		Laying		Broiler		Turkeys		Cattle		Pigs	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	622		56		28		2		1		50		99		114		39		48	
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n
Tetracyclines																				
Tetracycline	32,0	199	51,8	29	67,9	19	50,0	1	100	1	2,0	1	10,1	10	18,4	21	0,0	0	35,4	17
Amphenicols																				
Chloramphenicol	2,9	18	1,8	1	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	12,5	6
Penicillins																				
Ampicillin	24,0	149	8,9	5	28,6	8	50,0	1	100	1	0,0	0	22,2	22	16,7	19	0,0	0	31,3	15
Cephalosporins																				
Cefotaxim	0,3	2	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Fluoroquinolones																				
Ciprofloxacin	1,3	8	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Sulfonamides																				
Sulfamethoxazol	25,4	158	51,8	29	25,0	7	50,0	1	100	1	2,0	1	13,1	13	13,2	15	0,0	0	39,6	19
Aminoglycosides																				
Streptomycin	29,1	181	48,2	27	39,3	11	50,0	1	100	1	2,0	1	17,2	17	29,8	34	79,5	31	41,7	20
Gentamicin	1,1	7	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	5,1	5	8,8	10	0,0	0	0,0	0
Kanamycin	3,1	19	1,8	1	7,1	2	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	9,1	9	3,5	4	0,0	0	12,5	6
Quinolones																				
Nalidixic acid	19,9	124	55,4	31	46,4	13	0,0	0	0,0	0	2,0	1	22,2	22	30,7	35	5,1	2	2,1	1
Trimethoprim	5,5	34	8,9	5	10,7	3	0,0	0	0,0	0	2,0	1	6,1	6	0,9	1	0,0	0	14,6	7
Number of multiresistant isolates*	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n
fully sensitive	57,4	356	33,9	19	17,9	5	50,0	1	0	0	96,0	48	69,7	69	45,6	52	20,5	8	56,3	27
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	10,2	63	1,8	1	17,9	5	0,0	0	0	0	2,0	1	6,1	6	18,4	21	74,4	29	2,1	1
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	1,6	10	12,5	7	17,9	5	0,0	0	0	0	0,0	0	4,0	4	21,9	25	5,1	2	4,2	2
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	5,5	34	14,3	8	28,6	8	0,0	0	0	0	0,0	0	6,1	6	1,8	2	0,0	0	10,4	5
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	19,7	122	28,6	16	7,1	2	50,0	1	100	1	2,0	1	4,0	4	7,0	8	0,0	0	12,5	6
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	6,0	37	8,929	5	10,7	3	0,0	0	0	0	0,0	0	10,1	10	5,263	6	0,0	0	14,58	7

Table 27 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* spp. derived from broiler baseline study, carcasses (Dilution method)

		<i>Salmonella</i> spp. broiler carcasses BLS																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	11																					
Antimicrobials:			= < 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	%R	n	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																						
Gentamicin	0,0	0					8	3														
Kanamycin	0,0	0									11											
Streptomycin	0,0	0								2	3	5	1									
Cephalosporine																						
Cefotaxim	0,0	0			8	2	1															
Ceftazidime	0,0	0					7	3	1													
Folsäureinhibitoren																						
Sulfamethoxazol	0,0	0											2	8	1							
Trimethoprim	0,0	0						11														
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	18,2	2	6	2	1	2						6	3				2					
Nalidixinsäure	18,2	2																				
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	0,0	0							8	2	1											
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0									5	5	1									
Florfenicol	0,0	0									9	2										
Polymyxine																						
Colistine	0,0	0										11										
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	0,0	0							6	3	2											

Table 28 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* spp. derived from breeding pigs baseline study (Dilution method)

		<i>Salmonella</i> spp. breeding pigs BLS																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	15																				
Antimicrobials:		= < 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	> 2048
	%R	n	n																		
Aminoglykosid AB																					
Gentamicin	0,0	0				10	5														
Kanamycin	0,0	0								15											
Streptomycin	13,3	2							1	5	6		1	1		1					
Cephalosporine																					
Cefotaxim	0,0	0			14	1															
Ceftazidime	0,0	0				12	3														
Folsäureinhibitoren																					
Sulfamethoxazol	20,0	3										3	5	2	2						3
Trimethoprim	0,0	0					15														
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																					
Ciprofloxacin	0,0	0	8	7																	
Nalidixinsäure	0,0	0								15											
Penicilline																					
Ampicillin	13,3	2					3	10							2						
Phenicole																					
Chloramphenicol	13,3	2								7	6				2						
Florfenicol	13,3	2								13				2							
Polymyxine																					
Colistine	0,0	0									15										
Tetracycline																					
Tetracyclin	20,0	3						10	2				1	1		1					

Table 29 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method)

		<i>S. Enteritidis</i> laying hens, control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		40																				
		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:		< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	> 2048	
		n																				
Aminoglykosid AB																						
	Gentamicin	0,0	0				34	5	1													
	Kanamycin	0,0	0							39	1											
	Streptomycin	0,0	0							33	6	1										
Cephalosporine																						
	Cefotaxim	0,0	0		33	7																
	Ceftazidime	0,0	0				39	1														
Folsäureinhibitoren																						
	Sulfamethoxazol	0,0	0								4	10	25	1								
	Trimethoprim	0,0	0					38	1	1												
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																						
	Ciprofloxacin	5,0	2	24	14		1	1														
	Nalidixinsäure	5,0	2							38					2							
Penicilline																						
	Ampicillin	0,0	0						35	5												
Phenicole																						
	Chloramphenicol	0,0	0							3	31	6										
	Florfenicol	0,0	0							7	33											
Polymyxine																						
	Colistine	0,0	0								40											
Tetracycline																						
	Tetracyclin	0,0	0						26	14												

Table 30 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method)

		<i>S. Typhimurium</i> laying hens, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	16	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:		= < 0.008	0,015	0,03	0,06	0,12	0,25	0,5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	> 2048
	%R	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																					
Gentamicin	0,0	0				11	4	1													
Kanamycin	0,0	0								16											
Streptomycin	0,0	0								4	10	1	1								
Cephalosporine																					
Cefotaxim	0,0	0		16																	
Ceftazidime	0,0	0				16															
Folsäureinhibitoren																					
Sulfamethoxazol	0,0	0										3	11	2							
Trimethoprim	0,0	0					16														
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																					
Ciprofloxacin	0,0	0	4	12																	
Nalidixinsäure	0,0	0								16											
Penicilline																					
Ampicillin	0,0	0						15	1												
Phenicole																					
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0								11	5										
Florfenicol	0,0	0							5	11											
Polymyxine																					
Colistine	0,0	0									16										
Tetracycline																					
Tetracyclin	0,0	0						10	6												

Table 31 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than Enteritidis and Typhimurium derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method)

		<i>Salmonella</i> other than Enteritidis or Typhimurium laying hens, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	40	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:		= < 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	> 2048
	%R	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																					
Gentamicin	0,0	0				25	14	1													
Kanamycin	0,0	0								40											
Streptomycin	0,0	0							1	13	21	4	1								
Cephalosporine																					
Cefotaxim	0,0	0		19	18	2	1														
Ceftazidime	0,0	0				19	19		2												
Folsäureinhibitoren																					
Sulfamethoxazol	2,5	1									2	5	24	8						1	
Trimethoprim	2,5	1					39							1							
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																					
Ciprofloxacin	2,5	1	1	20	18		1														
Nalidixinsäure	2,5	1								39					1						
Penicilline																					
Ampicillin	0,0	0					5	32	3												
Phenicole																					
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0							2	14	24										
Florfenicol	0,0	0							4	36											
Polymyxine																					
Colistine	0,0	0									40										
Tetracycline																					
Tetracyclin	2,5	1						18	21						1						

Table 32 Qualitative table: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Salmonella spp., S. Enteritidis, S. Typhimurium and other serotypes than Enteritidis and Typhimurium derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method)

Gallus gallus laying hens, control program	Salmonella spp.	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	Salmonella other than Enteritidis or Typhimurium					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes	yes	yes	yes					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	96	40	16	40					
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	
Aminoglykosid AB									
Gentamicin	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	
Kanamycin	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	
Streptomycin	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	
Cephalosporine									
Cefotaxim	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	
Ceftazidime	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	
Folsäureinhibitoren									
Sulfamethoxazol	1,0	1	0,0	0	0,0	0	2,5	1	
Trimethoprim	1,0	1	0,0	0	0,0	0	2,5	1	
Quinolone and Quinoxalin									
Ciprofloxacin	3,1	3	5,0	2	0,0	0	2,5	1	
Nalidixinsäure	3,1	3	5,0	2	0,0	0	2,5	1	
Penicilline									
Ampicillin	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	
Phenicole									
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	
Florfenicol	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	
Polymyxine									
Colistine	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	
Tetracycline									
Tetracycline	1,0	1	0,0	0	0,0	0	2,5	1	
Number of multi-resistant isolates									
fully sensitive	96,9	93	95,0	38	100,0	16	97,5	39	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	2,1	2	5,0	2	0,0	0	0,0	0	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	1,0	1	0,0	0	0,0	0	2,5	1	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	

Table 33 Qualitative table: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* spp. derived from control program in laying hens, broiler carcasses BLS and breeding pigs BLS (Dilution method)

<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	Gallus Gallus, laying hens, control program	broiler carcasses, BLS	breeding pigs, BLS			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes	yes	yes			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	96	11	15			
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n
Aminoglykosid AB						
Gentamicin	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Kanamycin	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Streptomycin	0,0	0	0,0	0	13,3	2
Cephalosporine						
Cefotaxim	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Ceftazidime	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Folsäureinhibitoren						
Sulfamethoxazol	1,0	1	0,0	0	20,0	3
Trimethoprim	1,0	1	0,0	0	0,0	0
Quinolone and Quinoxalin						
Ciprofloxacin	3,1	3	18,2	2	0,0	0
Nalidixinsäure	3,1	3	18,2	2	0,0	0
Penicilline						
Ampicillin	0,0	0	0,0	0	13,3	2
Phenicole						
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0	0,0	0	13,3	2
Florfenicol	0,0	0	0,0	0	13,3	2
Polymyxine						
Colistine	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Tetracycline						
Tetracycline	1,0	1	0,0	0	20,0	3
Number of multiresistant isolates						
fully sensitive	96,9	93	81,8	9	80,0	12
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	2,1	2	18,2	2	0,0	0
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	0,0	0	0,0	0	13,3	2
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	1,0	1	0,0	0	6,7	1
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For *Salmonella* this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, Nalidixic acid, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazole

4.2. Campylobacteriosis

4.2.1. General evaluation of the national situation

A. Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2006, the number of notified human campylobacteriosis cases in Austria exceeded the number of notified salmonellosis cases for the first time. Since then, the gap between the number of human campylobacter cases and salmonella cases is widening.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In recent years, the number of notified cases of campylobacteriosis – with the exception of 2003 – steadily increased, reaching a new peak of 6,077 cases in 2007. In 2008 a reduction to 4,303 cases (Notification of single cases) could be observed. The reason for the reduction is not clear; attention must be paid to the future trends.

The sources of infection are still unclear. The few published outbreaks in Austria were due to contaminated cow's raw milk or chicken meat. Pets may be considered another possible source.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Feedings stuff has no obvious relevance. Animals are heavily infected: broiler flocks up to 50 %.The actual source of infection is unknown in most human cases, chicken meat may account for approx. 40% of human infections.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

On January 1st, 2006, the Federal Zoonoses Act (128. Bundesgesetz: Zoonosengesetz, published on 18th November 2005) was implemented. The subject of this Act is to ensure that zoonoses, zoonotic agents and related antimicrobial resistance are properly monitored, that food-borne outbreaks receive proper epidemiological investigation, to enable the collection of the information necessary in the EU. According to this Zoonoses Act, to survey and combat the zoonoses in Austria, a Federal Commission for Zoonoses (Zoonoses Commission) has been founded to advise the Federal Minister. The first meeting took place on May 3rd, 2006. The tasks of this Zoonoses Commission are

Securing of effective and continuous teamwork of special fields concerned

Cooperation based on free exchange of general information and where necessary, of specific data

Determination of measures in case of Austrian-wide food borne outbreaks (concerning several provinces by one outbreak)

Issues the annually report on trends and sources of zoonoses in Austria

Preparation of risk based, integrated monitoring and surveillance programmes

The Austria-wide monitoring program on the trends of campylobacter prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of campylobacter in broiler, pigs and bovine animals was continued for the fourth year according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 17 November 2003 and the Federal Zoonoses Act. The sampling was carried out from January to December 2008, and follow up programs will be implemented in the forthcoming years.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Continue to work for harmonization of monitoring programs

Additional information

Nil

4.2.2. Campylobacteriosis in humans

A. Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

Case definition

Clinical picture compatible with campylobacteriosis, e.g.: diarrheal illness of variable severity and isolation of *Campylobacter* spp. from stool.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Stool samples are plated on selective media and incubated in microaerobic atmosphere at 37 - 42 °C for a minimum of 36 hours (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 13). *Campylobacter* is confirmed by observing the typical colony morphology and characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope. For typing and differentiation of isolates to species level the production of catalase and oxidase, the reaction in hippurate and indoxylacetate-hydrolysis is performed. The differentiation to species-level is not performed in each laboratory.

Notification system in place

Notification of campylobacteriosis since 1996 according to the epidemic act (BGBl. 1950/186 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): Primarily the attending physicians have to notify. Since 2002, an order has been implemented (Meldepflicht infektiöser Erkrankungen für Labors GZ: 21.700/5- VIII/D/5/02), in which medical doctors specialised in Laboratory Diagnosis or Microbiology and Hygiene are subjected to notification.

As described in chapter 2, in 2008 additionally to the notification of aggregated data also single case data were collected in the AGES. These data presented in this report reflects the number of single human cases notified. Only for reasons of comparison with the last years, the number of cases notified as aggregated data used.

On July 24th 2006 the amendments of the epidemic act (114. Bundesgesetz: Änderung des Epidemiegesetzes 1950) has been published: Accordingly, all zoonotic agents that are isolated in a laboratory and that are notifiable have to be sent to the corresponding reference laboratory for speciation.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2006, the number of notified human campylobacteriosis cases in Austria exceeded the number of notified salmonellosis cases for the first time. Since that year campylobacteriosis has remained the most frequently reported bacterial enteritis in humans in Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Following the number of collected single cases per year, in 2008 campylobacteriosis (N=4,303) is the most frequently notified foodborne enteric disease. In comparison to 2007, a decrease of 26% of the notified cases (N=5,821) could be observed in 2008. The reason for the reduction is not clear; anyhow attention must be paid to the future trends.

It seems that the main source of infections is chicken meat and raw milk (Feierl G. 2007. Jahresbericht 2006 der Nationalen Referenzzentrale für *Campylobacter*. Mitteilungen der Sanitätsverwaltung 4/2007).

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In 2008, campylobacteriosis remained the most frequently notified food borne disease in Austria.

Additional information

On July 24, 2006, the amendment of the Epidemic Act (114. Bundesgesetz: Änderung des Epidemiegesetzes 1950) was published. According to the Act, all notifiable zoonotic agents that are isolated from humans in a laboratory have to be sent to the corresponding national reference laboratory/centre for speciation.

Additionally a sentinel surveillance program for Campylobacter isolates from human infections was installed in October 2006. On a monthly basis, the first 10 isolates collected at each of four diagnostic laboratories serving different provinces in Austria are sent to the National Reference Laboratory for Campylobacter for speciation analysis and antimicrobial resistance testing.

Annual report of the National Reference Centre

http://www.bmg.gv.at/cms/site/attachments/9/7/8/CH0954/CMS1237550818447/jb_campylobacter_revised.pdf

Data source of Tables 34 to 36: Notification of single cases

Table 34 Campylobacteriosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (single case notification)

	Cases	Notification rate/100.000	Autochtone cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
Campylobacteriosis	4,303	51.6	1,831	395	2,077
<i>C. jejuni</i>	2,975	35,7	1,126	248	1,601
<i>C. coli</i>	126	1,5	53	19	54
<i>C. lari</i>	1	0,0	1	0	0
<i>C. upsalensis</i>	1	0,0	0	0	1
<i>C. spp.</i>	1,200	14,4	651	128	421

Table 35 Campylobacteriosis in humans - age distribution (single case notification)

Age group	Campylobacter sp.			C. jejuni			C. coli		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	99	63	36	67	39	28	4	3	1
1 to 4 years	412	215	197	260	137	123	8	4	4
5 to 14 years	471	272	199	334	193	141	11	5	6
15 to 24 years	808	427	381	553	291	262	23	9	14
25 to 44 years	1,213	637	576	857	453	404	37	14	23
45 to 64 years	745	413	332	520	273	247	21	7	14
65 years and older	555	275	280	384	198	186	22	11	11
Age unknown									
All age groups	4,303	2,302	2,001	2,975	1,584	1,391	126	53	73

Table 36 Campylobacteriosis in humans - seasonal distribution (single case notification)

Month	Campylobacter Cases	C. jejuni Cases	C. coli Cases	C. lari Cases	C. upsalensis Cases	C. spp. Cases
January	333	231	8	0	0	94
February	268	187	5	0	0	76
March	236	160	6	0	0	70
April	330	230	6	0	0	94
May	314	212	11	0	0	91
June	364	263	7	0	0	94
July	436	291	15	0	1	129
August	502	344	13	0	0	145
September	527	360	19	1	0	147
October	399	280	13	0	0	106
November	336	233	15	0	0	88
December	258	184	8	0	0	66
not known	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	4,303	2,975	126	1	1	1,200

4.2.3. Campylobacter in foodstuffs

A. Campylobacter, thermotolerant in food - all foodstuffs - official food or feed controls

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2008 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2008“ (BMGFJ-75500/0247-IV/B/7/2007 von 08.01.2008) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2007-2010) according to Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2008, approximately 40,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 60% (24,000) of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-dept information. In 2008, eight relevant food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria (Schwerpunktprogramm 2008 BMGFJ-75500/0242-IV/B/7/2007). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Samples are cultured either according to ISO 10272: 1995 or preenriched in Bolton bouillon at 42 °C for 48 hours and subsequent plated on CCDA- or modified CCDA agar at 42 °C for 48 hours microaerophilic. Campylobacter-like colonies were identified serologically, observing their characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope and the production of catalase and oxidase. Not all isolates of Campylobacter spp. are differentiated.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

138 single samples of fresh broiler meat were tested and in 8% (=11 samples) thermotolerant Campylobacter was found. In 35 samples of pasteurised cows' milk, no sample was found positive and in 25 samples of raw cows' milk one sample was found positive for *C. coli* (4%).

Table 37 Thermophilic Campylobacter spp. in food

Categories	Sampling stage	Sampling unit	Sampling weight	Units tested	Total units positive for Campylobacter spp.	<i>C. coli</i>
Crustaceans	at catering	single	25 g	5	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	at processing plant	single	25 g	14	0	0
	at retail	single	25 g	12	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream	at retail	single	25 g	4	0	0
Fish - raw	at catering	single	25 g	2	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified	at catering	single	25 g	3	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - fresh	at processing plant	single	25 g	2	0	0
Meat from pig - fresh	at catering	single	25 g	3	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail	single	25 g	7	0	0
	at processing plant	single	25 g	15	0	0
Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk	at retail	single	25 g	20	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw	at retail	single	25 g	25	1	1
	at processing plant	single	25 g	17	0	0
Other food	at retail	single	25 g	12	0	0
Vegetables - products	at retail	single	25 g	4	0	0

Table 38 Thermophilic Campylobacter spp. in poultry meat

Categories	Sampling stage	Sampling unit	Sampling weight	Units tested	Total units positive for Campylobacter spp.	<i>C. jejuni</i>	<i>C. coli</i>	<i>C. lari</i>	<i>C. upsaliensis</i>	Campylobacter spp., unspecified
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh	at retail	single	25 g	138	11					11
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh (EU baseline surey)	at slaughterhouse	animal	1 g	408	320	217	98	0	0	5
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail	single	25 g	79	11					11

4.2.4. Campylobacter in animals

A. *Campylobacter* spp. in animal - Cattle (bovine animals) - at slaughterhouse - animal sample - faeces - Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Since 2004 monitoring plans on the prevalence of selected zoonotic agents and their antimicrobial resistance have been performed annually. Based on the prevalence of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* in cattle in 2007 the number of caecum samples was calculated (N=923) to obtain 170 thermotolerant *Campylobacter* for antimicrobial susceptibility testing. Caecal contents of slaughtered cattle of Austrian origin were sampled in slaughter houses where at least 80% of all cattle were slaughtered in 2007. The sampling had been stratified on the number of slaughtered animals by abattoirs all over Austria. The date of sampling was randomized over the period of the study.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at slaughter:

The sampling was distributed by randomization over the whole year 2008.

Type of specimen taken

Animals at slaughter: Caecum containing a minimum of 50 to 100 grams of content.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The sampling was performed by official veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration a part of the colon was ligated and wrapped in a sterile plastic bag. After cooling down to 4 °C the sample was sent in a hobbox or polystyrene box after adding cooling units to the Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz. In the laboratory some content of each colon was inoculated in selective bouillon suitable for *Campylobacter jejuni/coli*.

Case definition

A bovine animal is considered to be infected with thermotolerant *Campylobacter* following isolation of *Campylobacter jejuni* or *C. coli* from its caecum.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Approximately 1 gram of content of the colon was enriched in Preston bouillon in microaerophilic atmosphere for 24 hours at 42 °C. Subsequently the preenrichment was plated on modified CCD agar (mCCDA) and incubated in microaerophilic atmosphere at 42 ± 1 °C for 48 hours. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were identified by observing their characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope and the production of catalase and oxidase.

For typing and differentiating of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates, hippurate reaction and indoxylacetate-hydrolysis was performed. All *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates were frozen in proteose pepton solution containing 10% glycerol or thioglycolate-broth at -70 °C.

For quality control *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 and internal control isolates of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli*.

Statistical analysis was performed with EpiInfo version 3.3.2.

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not performed in Austria

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Emphasis should be placed on education of the people for a better care in kitchen hygiene.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None

Notification system in place

Findings of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* in animals must not be reported to authorities in Austria.

Results of the investigation

See respective tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 263 out of 923 (28.5%; CI 95% 25.6-31.5) caecum samples from slaughtered bovine animals thermotolerant *Campylobacter* were detected. There was no significant change in the prevalence compared to the previous years (25.4% in 2007). Due to the 47.8% prevalence of positive broiler slaughter batches for thermotolerant *Campylobacter*, there may be a higher risk for humans to get infected from poultry meat than from the consumption of beef or veal.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

Nil

B. *Campylobacter* spp. in animal – broiler - at slaughterhouse – baseline survey – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2008 a baseline survey on the prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of *Campylobacter* spp. in broiler flocks and on the prevalence of *Campylobacter* spp. and *Salmonella* spp. in broiler carcasses was carried out. The date of sampling was randomized over the whole year. Sampling was performed in the 5 broiler slaughter facilities with slaughter batches consisting of >2000 animals in Austria in 2007.

Frequency of the sampling

Rearing period: no program

Before slaughter at farm: no program

At slaughter: according to the randomized sampling plan

Type of specimen taken

Intestines of 10 animals.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Rearing period: no program

Before slaughter at farm: no program

At slaughter: The sampling was performed by official veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration the whole intestines of 10 animals were taken and wrapped in a sterile plastic bag. Additionally a carcass from the same slaughter batch was sampled. After cooling down to 4 °C the sample was sent in a hobbox or polystyrene box after adding cooling units to the Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz. In the laboratory a caecum of each intestinal convolute was identified, some content of each caecum pooled and plated on selective medium suitable for *Campylobacter jejuni/coli*. The carcass was immediately forwarded to the national Reference laboratory for *Campylobacter* and the national Reference laboratory for *Salmonella*.

Case definition

At slaughter: A slaughter batch is considered to be infected with thermotolerant *Campylobacter* following isolation of *Campylobacter jejuni* or *C. coli* from its caecum.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

At slaughter: The pooled samples were examined by direct inoculation on modified CCD agar (mCCDA) that was incubated in microaerophilic atmosphere at 42 ± 1 °C for 48 hours. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were identified by observing their characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope and the production of catalase and oxidase. For typing and differentiating of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates, hippurate reaction and indoxylacetate-hydrolysis was performed. All *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates were frozen in proteose peptone solution containing 10 % glycerol or thioglycolat-broth at -70 °C. For quality control *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 and internal control isolates *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* were used. Statistical analysis was performed with EpiInfo version 3.3.2.

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not performed in Austria.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Emphasis should be placed on education of the people for a better care in kitchen hygiene.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None.

Notification system in place

Findings of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* in animals must not be reported to authorities in Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the course of the baseline survey thermotolerant *Campylobacter* was detected in 195 out of 408 (47.8%; 42.9-52.8) of the tested slaughter batches. On 78.4% carcasses originating from the same

slaughter batches thermotolerant *Campylobacter* could be detected. Due to the fact that poultry is the animal species with the highest prevalence of *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli*, poultry meat seem to be the most risky food combined with mistakes in kitchen hygiene for humans acquiring an infection with *C. jejuni/coli*.

C. *Campylobacter* spp. in animal - Pigs - at slaughterhouse – monitoring programme – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2008, after three years break slaughtered pigs were again included in the monitoring for thermotolerant *Campylobacter*. Based on the prevalence of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* determined in 2005 and 2004 samples size was calculated with a Bayesian approach (Stüger HP, Fuchs K, Much P, 2007. Bayesian Methods for Sample Size Calculation. SVEPM Konferenz, 27.-30.03.2007). 286 caecum samples were sampled in slaughterhouses where at least 80% of all pigs were slaughtered in 2007. The sampling had been stratified on the number of slaughtered animals by abattoirs all over Austria. The date of sampling was randomized over the whole year.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at slaughter:

The sampling was distributed by randomization over the whole year 2008.

Type of specimen taken

Animals at slaughter: Caecum containing a minimum of 50 to 100 grams of content.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The sampling was performed by official veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration a part of the colon was ligated and wrapped in a sterile plastic bag. After cooling down to 4 °C the sample was sent in a hobbox or polystyrene box after adding cooling units to the Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz. In the laboratory some content of each caecum was and plated on selective medium suitable for *Campylobacter jejuni/coli*.

Case definition

A pig is considered to be infected with thermotolerant *Campylobacter* following isolation of *Campylobacter jejuni* or *C. coli* from its caecum.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

At slaughter: The pooled samples were examined by direct inoculation on modified CCD agar (mCCDA) that was incubated in microaerophilic atmosphere at 42 ± 1 °C for 48 hours. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were identified by observing their characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope and the production of catalase and oxidase. For typing and differentiating of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates, hippurate reaction and indoxylacetate-hydrolysis was performed. All *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates were frozen in proteose peptone solution containing 10 % glycerol or thioglycolat-broth at -70 °C. For quality control *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 and internal control isolates *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* were used. Statistical analysis was performed with EpiInfo version 3.3.2.

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not performed in Austria

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Emphasis should be placed on education of the people for a better care in kitchen hygiene.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None

Notification system in place

Findings of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* in animals must not be reported to authorities in Austria.

Results of the investigation

See respective tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

95 to 100% of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* in pigs are among *Campylobacter coli*. These *Campylobacter* species is of low importance as a human pathogen. In 143 out of 286 (50%; CI 95% 44.1-55.9) off tested samples thermotolerant *Campylobacter* were detected, all were typed as *C. coli*.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Minor importance.

Additional information

Nil

Table 39 Thermophilic *Campylobacter* spp. in animals

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for thermophilic <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<i>C. jejuni</i>	<i>C. coli</i>	<i>C. lari</i>	<i>C. upsaliensis</i>	<i>Campylobacter</i> spp., unspecified
Cattle	at slaughterhouse	monitoring-objective sampling			animal sample	923	263	232	31	0	0	0
Dairy cows												
calves (under 1 year)												
Sheep						0						
Goats						0						
Pigs	at slaughterhouse	monitoring-objective sampling			animal sample	286	143	0	143	0	0	0
Domestic solipeds						0						
Gallus Gallus												
Broilers - at farm						0						
Broilers - at slaughter	at slaughterhouse	baseline survey			slaughter batch	408	195	127	65	0	0	3
Turkeys						0						

Graz: AGES Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Graz

4.2.5. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter* spp.

A. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* in humans

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

A sentinel surveillance program for *Campylobacter* isolates from human infections was installed in October 2006. On a monthly basis, the first 10 isolates collected at each of four diagnostic laboratories serving different provinces in Austria are sent to the National Reference Laboratory for *Campylobacter* for speciation analysis and antimicrobial resistance testing.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Stool specimens were plated on *Campylobacter* blood-free selective media at 37°C or 42°C for 48 hours under micro aerobic conditions, and organisms were identified as *Campylobacter* spp. by oxidase testing and cell morphology. Isolates were speciated by hippurate hydrolysis, indoxyl acetate hydrolysis, katalase production, and species-specific real-time PCR.

Broth micro dilution susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter* spp. isolates was done using customised Sensititre® susceptibility micro titre plates (TREK Diagnostic Systems, Ltd., East Grinstead, West Sussex, and England). Briefly, *Campylobacter* spp. strains were subcultivated on Columbia blood agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerophilic atmosphere. Inocula from fresh cultures were prepared by suspension in physiological saline to obtain a turbidity equivalent to that of a McFarland standard 0.5. The suspension was added to Mueller Hinton bouillon for a final concentration of approximately 5x10⁵ cfu/ml and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerophilic atmosphere. *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560 was used as control.

The number of isolates that are fully sensitive and the number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 and > 4 antimicrobials for Campylobacter includes only resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, nalidixic acid, gentamicin, and streptomycin!

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The resistance rates against ciprofloxacin, tetracycline and erythromycin remained stable compared to 2007.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

The newly established sentinel surveillance system will be continued.

B. Antimicrobial resistance in Campylobacter jejuni and coli in animals

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant campylobacter in bovine animals, broilers and pigs

Type of specimen taken

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant campylobacter in bovine animals, broilers and pigs

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant campylobacter in bovine animals, broilers and pigs

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

Testing of all isolates will be performed in the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene in Graz. The randomized sampling plan was calculated to obtain approximately 170 Isolates per animal species. If less than 170 isolates were obtained, all isolates were tested. If more than 170 thermotolerant Campylobacter were isolated 170 were randomly chosen.

Methods used for collecting data

All informations concerning the tested animals, sampled slaughterhouses and results of the antimicrobial testing were entered and analysed in a Microsoft® Excel tables.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant campylobacter in bovine animals, broilers and pigs.

Broth micro dilution susceptibility testing of Campylobacter spp. isolates was done using customised Sensititre® susceptibility micro titre plates (TREK Diagnostic Systems, Ltd., East Grinstead, West Sussex, and England). Briefly, Campylobacter spp. strains were subcultivated on Columbia blood agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerophilic atmosphere. Inocula from fresh cultures were prepared by suspension in physiological saline to obtain a turbidity equivalent to that of a McFarland standard 0.5. The suspension was added to Mueller Hinton bouillon for a final concentration of

approximately 5×10^5 cfu/ml and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerophilic atmosphere. *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560 was used as control. MIC values have been entered in a Microsoft® Excel datasheet. The number of isolates that are fully sensitive and the number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 and > 4 antimicrobials for *Campylobacter* includes only resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, nalidixic acid, gentamicin, and streptomycin!

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Samples from food animals were monitored for antimicrobial residues according to a randomized sampling scheme (BMGF-74320/0003-IV/B/7/2008, Rückstandsuntersuchung-Durchführungserlass 2007).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A project has been started to assess the appropriate method for collecting data on antimicrobial usage in animals. Results of this study are expected in 2010.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Nil

Notification system in place

No notification system in place at this time.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not yet evaluated.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Additional information

Nil

Table 40 Breakpoints used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni*

Breakpoints used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i>								
Test method used		Number of reporting laboratory			1			
Disc diffusion								
E-test								
Agar dilution								
Broth dilution	x							
Standards used for testing		The methods are used for investigation of isolates from						
CLSI		Feedingstuff						
other	EUCAST	Animals			x			
		Food			x			
		Humans			x			
<i>Campylobacter jejuni</i>	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Breakpoint concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)			Dilution method Range tested (NLV73) concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)		Range tested (NLV48) concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	
		Susceptible \leq	Intermediate	Resistant $>$	lowest	highest	lowest	highest
Aminoglykosid AB								
Gentamicin	EUCAST			> 1	0,125	16	0,25	64
Neomycin	EUCAST			> 1	0,125	8	1	64
Streptomycin	EUCAST			> 2	0,5	32	1	64
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination								
Amoxicillin/Clavulan-säure	EUCAST			> 16	1	64	1	128
Quinolone und Quinoxalin								
Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST			> 1	0,06	32	0,06	32
Nalidixinsäure	EUCAST			> 16	2	256	2	128
Makrolide								
Erythromycin	EUCAST			> 4	0,25	128	0,25	128
Penicilline								
Ampicillin	EUCAST			> 8	0,5	64	1	128
Phenicol								
Chloramphenicol	EUCAST			> 16	2	64	2	32
Polymyxine								
Colistin	EUCAST			> 32	4	128	4	128
Tetracycline								
Tetracyclin	EUCAST			> 2	0,125	64	0,25	128

Table 41 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in humans, quantitative data (test plate NLV48)

<i>C. jejuni</i> human																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	129		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	%R	n	<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0,03	0,06	0,12	0,25	0,5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512		
			n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																						
Gentamicin	0,0	0							106	23												
Neomycin	0,8	1								128									1			
Streptomycin	1,6	2								127						2						
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																						
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:	0,0	0									56	69	4									
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	57,4	74					31	14	10				3	58	5	7	1					
Nalidixinsäure	55,0	71										19	32	7		1	9	43	18			
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	0,0	0							54	29	28	17	1									
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	22,5	29										11	24	39	26	2	6	13	4	4		
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0											94	33	2							
Polymyxine																						
Colistin	0,0	0												109	17	3						
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	28,7	37							83	9					1	1	4	10	13	8		

Table 42 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in humans, quantitative data (test plate NLVC73)

<i>C. jejuni</i> human																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	261		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	%R	n	<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0,03	0,06	0,12	0,25	0,5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512		
			n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																						
Gentamicin	0,0	0						218	43													
Neomycin	0,4	1						31	146	79	4				1							
Streptomycin	1,5	4								244	13			2	1	1						
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																						
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:	0,0	0									208	52	1									
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	50,2	131					67	54	7	2		4	8	73	30	9	7					
Nalidixinsäure	50,2	131										28	88	11	3	1	5	56	69			
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	0,4	1							31	126	92	11								1		
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	16,1	42								2	8	65	109	35	6	14	17	5				
Phenicol																						
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0										186	61	10	4							
Polymyxine																						
Colistin	0,0	0											241	20								
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	23,0	60					69	90	33	7	2	3		1	10	18	28					

Table 43 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in broiler meat [Dilution method], test plate NLV48

<i>C. jejuni</i> broiler meat (LM NLV48)																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	33		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																	
Antimicrobials:	%R	n	<= 0,0039	0,007	0,015	0,03	0,06	0,12	0,25	0,5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512
			n																	
Aminoglykosid AB	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gentamicin	0,0	0							22	11										
Neomycin	0,0	0									33									
Streptomycin	0,0	0									32	1								
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																				
Amoxicillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	0,0	0									16	17								
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																				
Ciprofloxacin	66,7	22					4	7					2	11	8	1				
Nalidixinsäure	66,7	22										3	7	1			4	14	4	
Makrolide																				
Erythromycin	0,0	0							21	9	2	1								
Penicilline																				
Ampicillin	33,3	11									6	8	7	1		10				1
Phenicol																				
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0										32	1							
Polymyxine																				
Colistin	0,0	0											31	2						
Tetracycline																				
Tetracyclin	12,1	4							27	2							2	2		

Table 44 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in broiler meat [Dilution method], test plate NLVC73

<i>C. jejuni</i> broiler meat (LM NLVC73)																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	4		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																	
Antimicrobials:	%R	n	<= 0,0039	0,007	0,015	0,03	0,06	0,12	0,25	0,5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512
			n																	
Aminoglykosid AB	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gentamicin	0,0	0						3	1											
Neomycin	0,0	0						1	3											
Streptomycin	0,0	0								4										
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																				
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	0,0	0									2	2								
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																				
Ciprofloxacin	50,0	2					2						1	1						
Nalidixinsäure	50,0	2										1	1						2	
Makrolide																				
Erythromycin	0,0	0								3	1									
Penicilline																				
Ampicillin	50,0	2										2				1	1			
Phenicol																				
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0										4								
Polymyxine																				
Colistin	0,0	0											4							
Tetracycline																				
Tetracyclin	75,0	3							1									1	2	

Table 45 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in cattle (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], test plate PLVC73

<i>C. jejuni</i> cattle			Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	152																			
Antimicrobials:	%R	n	<= 0,0039	0,007	0,015	0,03	0,06	0,12	0,25	0,5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512
			n																	
Aminoglykosid AB	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gentamicin	0,0	0					143	9												
Neomycin	0,0	0					41	91	19	1										
Streptomycin	2,6	4							146	2					3		1			
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																				
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	0,0	0								135	17									
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																				
Ciprofloxacin	34,2	52				87	9	4					4	38	6	4				
Nalidixinsäure	34,2	52										43	47	10			2	26	24	
Makrolide																				
Erythromycin	0,0	0						28	64	56	3	1								
Penicilline																				
Ampicillin	7,9	12							12	8	48	60	12	1	7	3	1			
Phenicole																				
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0									131	15	6							
Polymyxine																				
Colistin	0,0	0										144	8							
Tetracycline																				
Tetracyclin	21,7	33					47	58	9	5			1		4	10	18			

Table 46 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in broiler flocks - at slaughter (BLS) - EU baseline survey - quantitative data [Dilution method], test plate PLVC73

<i>C. jejuni</i> Gallus gallus																					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	115		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																		
Antimicrobials:	%R	n	<= 0,0039	0,007	0,015	0,03	0,06	0,12	0,25	0,5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
			n																		
Aminoglykosid AB																					
Gentamicin	0,0	0						108	6	1											
Neomycin	0,9	1						34	64	16						1					
Streptomycin	1,7	2								111	2					1		1			
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																					
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	0,0	0									94	20	1								
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																					
Ciprofloxacin	49,6	57					38	14	6			1	2	43	9	1	1				
Nalidixinsäure	48,7	56										22	29	6	2	1		35	20		
Makrolide																					
Erythromycin	0,0	0							25	55	32	3									
Penicilline																					
Ampicillin	15,7	18								2	18	31	37	9		9	6	3			
Phenicol																					
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0										88	21	5	1						
Polymyxine																					
Colistin	0,0	0											113	2							
Tetracycline																					
Tetracyclin	26,1	30						33	42	5	3	2		2	2	2	10	14			

Table 47 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter jejuni in humans, broiler meat, broiler slaughter batches (BLS), pigs and cattle

C. jejuni	human	broiler meat	Gallus gallus	pigs	cattle					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	390	37	115	0	152					
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n
Aminoglykosid AB										
Gentamicin	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0			0,0	0
Neomycin	0,5	2	0,0	0	0,9	1			0,0	0
Streptomycin	1,5	6	0,0	0	1,7	2			2,6	4
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination										
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0			0,0	0
Quinolone und Quinoxalin										
Ciprofloxacin	52,6	205	64,9	24	49,6	57			34,2	52
Nalidixinsäure	51,8	202	64,9	24	48,7	56			34,2	52
Makrolide										
Erythromycin	0,3	1	0,0	0	0,0	0			0,0	0
Penicilline										
Ampicillin	18,2	71	35,1	13	15,7	18			7,9	12
Phenicole										
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0			0,0	0
Polymyxine										
Colistin	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0			0,0	0
Tetracycline										
Tetracyclin	24,9	97	18,9	7	26,1	30			21,7	33
Number of multiresistant isolates										
fully sensitive	41,0	160	29,7	11	40,0	46			55,3	84
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	40,5	158	56,8	21	43,5	50			30,9	47
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	17,4	68	13,5	5	16,5	19			13,8	21
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	1,0	4	0,0	0	0,0	0			0,0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0			0,0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0			0,0	0

Number of multiresistant isolates: For Campylobacter this includes resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, Nalidixic acid, gentamicin, and streptomycin

Table 48 Breakpoints used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli*

Breakpoints used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>Campylobacter coli</i>								
Test method used		Number of reporting laboratory						1
Disc diffusion								
E-test								
Agar dilution								
Broth dilution		x						
Standards used for testing		The methods are used for investigation of isolates from						
CLSI				Feedingsstuff				
other	EUCAST			Animals		x		
				Food		x		
				Humans		x		
<i>Campylobacter coli</i>	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Dilution method						
		Breakpoint concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)			Range tested (NLV73) concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)		Range tested (NLV48) concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	
		Susceptible ≤	Intermediate	Resistant >	lowest	highest	lowest	highest
Aminoglykosid AB								
Gentamicin	EUCAST			> 2	0,125	16	0,25	64
Neomycin	EUCAST			> 2	0,125	8	1	64
Streptomycin	EUCAST			> 4	0,5	32	1	64
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination								
Amoxicillin/Clavulan-säur	EUCAST			> 16	1	64	1	128
Quinolone und Quinoxalin								
Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST			> 1	0,06	32	0,06	32
Nalidixinsäure	EUCAST			> 32	2	256	2	128
Makrolide								
Erythromycin	EUCAST			> 16	0,25	128	0,25	128
Penicilline								
Ampicillin	EUCAST			> 16	0,5	64	1	128
Phenicole								
Chloramphenicol	EUCAST			> 16	2	64	2	32
Polymyxine								
Colistin	EUCAST			> 32	4	128	4	128
Tetracycline								
Tetracyclin	EUCAST			> 2	0,125	64	0,25	128

Table 49 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in humans quantitative data (test plate NLV48)

<i>C. coli</i> human (plate48)		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	13																			
Antimicrobials:	%R	n	<= 0,0039	0,007	0,015	0,03	0,06	0,12	0,25	0,5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512
			n																	
Aminoglykosid AB																				
Gentamicin	0,0	0							6	6	1									
Neomycin	0,0	0									13									
Streptomycin	15,4	2									6	5			1				1	
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																				
Amoxicillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	0,0	0									2	6	3	2						
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																				
Ciprofloxacin	76,9	10					2	1					4	4	1	1				
Nalidixinsäure	76,9	10											3				4	5	1	
Makrolide																				
Erythromycin	7,7	1							4	1	4	3								1
Penicilline																				
Ampicillin	15,4	2										2	1	7	1		1			1
Phenicol																				
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0										9	2	2						
Polymyxine																				
Colistin	0,0	0											13							
Tetracycline																				
Tetracyclin	46,2	6							6		1					1	1	3	1	

Table 50 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in humans quantitative data (test plate NLVC73)

<i>C. coli</i> human																					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	32		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																		
Antimicrobials:	%R	n	<= 0,0039	0,007	0,015	0,03	0,06	0,12	0,25	0,5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
			n																		
Aminoglykosid AB																					
Gentamicin	3,1	1						13	17	1						1					
Neomycin	3,1	1						2	12	16	1				1						
Streptomycin	6,3	2								22	8			1		1					
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																					
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	0,0	0										15	16	1							
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																					
Ciprofloxacin	62,5	20					9	2	1				8	9	2	1					
Nalidixinsäure	62,5	20											10	1	1		3	14	3		
Makrolide																					
Erythromycin	18,8	6							6	15	2	2		1						6	
Penicilline																					
Ampicillin	6,3	2										1	11	17	1	1	1				
Phenicole																					
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0										12	17	2	1						
Polymyxine																					
Colistin	0,0	0											31	1							
Tetracycline																					
Tetracyclin	37,5	12						5	14	1							1	11			

Table 51 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in cattle - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], (test plate NLVC73)

<i>C. coli</i> cattle																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	17		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																	
Antimicrobials:	%R	n	<= 0,0039	0,007	0,015	0,03	0,06	0,12	0,25	0,5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512
			n																	
Aminoglykosid AB	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gentamicin	0,0	0					5	11	1											
Neomycin	0,0	0					2	5	9	1										
Streptomycin	52,9	9							3	5				1	5	1	2			
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																				
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	0,0	0									6	7	4							
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																				
Ciprofloxacin	58,8	10				4	2	1					4	6						
Nalidixinsäure	58,8	10											3	3	1		3	6	1	
Makrolide																				
Erythromycin	11,8	2						1	4	4	4	2								2
Penicilline																				
Ampicillin	0,0	0									3	3	3	5	3					
Phenicole																				
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0										8	6	3						
Polymyxine																				
Colistin	0,0	0											16	1						
Tetracycline																				
Tetracyclin	76,5	13					2	1		1					1	1	2	9		

Table 52 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in broiler slaughter batches (BLS) – EU-baseline survey - quantitative data [Dilution method], (test plate NLVC73)

<i>C. coli</i> <i>Gallus gallus</i>		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	53																				
Antimicrobials:	%R	n	<= 0,0039	0,007	0,015	0,03	0,06	0,12	0,25	0,5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
			n																		
Aminoglykosid AB																					
Gentamicin	0,0	0						22	31												
Neomycin	1,9	1						3	18	31					1						
Streptomycin	28,3	15								25	12	1			7	4	4				
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																					
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	0,0	0									11	20	16	5	1						
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																					
Ciprofloxacin	50,9	27					17	9				2	11	10	4						
Nalidixinsäure	50,9	27									2	18	6			3	20	4			
Makrolide																					
Erythromycin	7,5	4							7	17	14	5	5	1		1	1			2	
Penicilline																					
Ampicillin	11,3	6									2	4	14	25	2		3	3			
Phenicole																					
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0										18	31	3	1						
Polymyxine																					
Colistin	0,0	0											53								
Tetracycline																					
Tetracyclin	43,4	23						10	15	3	2					1	5	17			

Table 53 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in pigs - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], (test plate NLVC73)

<i>C. coli</i> pigs																					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	137		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																		
Antimicrobials:	%R	n	<= 0,0039	0,007	0,015	0,03	0,06	0,12	0,25	0,5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
			n																		
Aminoglykosid AB																					
Gentamicin	0,0	0						54	76	7											
Neomycin	0,7	1						2	56	70	8		1								
Streptomycin	82,5	113								8	11	5		19	58	26	10				
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																					
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	0,0	0									34	66	26	11							
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																					
Ciprofloxacin	32,1	44					66	27					12	25	7						
Nalidixinsäure	32,1	44										1	37	50	5		6	16	20	2	
Makrolide																					
Erythromycin	13,1	18							2	19	52	28	14	4		1		2	15		
Penicilline																					
Ampicillin	12,4	17								2	4	22	31	53	8	2	13	2			
Phenicole																					
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0										61	59	17							
Polymyxine																					
Colistin	0,0	0											133	4							
Tetracycline																					
Tetracyclin	78,1	107						9	10	5	6		1	2	5	4	13	82			

Table 48 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter coli in humans, broiler meat, broiler slaughter batches (BLS), pigs and cattle

C. coli	human		broiler meat		Gallus gallus		pigs		cattle	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes		yes		yes		yes		yes	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	45		too low number		53		137		17	
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n
Aminoglykosid AB										
Gentamicin	2,2	1			0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Neomycin	2,2	1			1,9	1	0,7	1	0,0	0
Streptomycin	8,9	4			28,3	15	82,5	113	52,9	9
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination										
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	0,0	0			0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Quinolone und Quinoxalin										
Ciprofloxacin	66,7	30			50,9	27	32,1	44	58,8	10
Nalidixinsäure	66,7	30			50,9	27	32,1	44	58,8	10
Makrolide										
Erythromycin	15,6	7			7,5	4	13,1	18	11,8	2
Penicilline										
Ampicillin	8,9	4			11,3	6	12,4	17	0,0	0
Phenicole										
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0			0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Polymyxine										
Colistin	0,0	0			0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Tetracycline										
Tetracyclin	40,0	18			43,4	23	78,1	107	76,5	13
Number of multiresistant isolates										
fully sensitive	33,3	15			28,3	15	2,2	3	5,9	1
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	26,7	12			28,3	15	18,2	25	17,6	3
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	20,0	9			30,2	16	55,5	76	52,9	9
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	15,6	7			11,3	6	19,7	27	17,6	3
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	2,2	1			1,9	1	4,4	6	5,9	1
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	2,2	1			0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0

Number of multiresistant isolates: For Campylobacter this includes resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, Nalidixic acid, gentamicin, and streptomycin

4.3. Listeriosis

4.3.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Listeriosis can be regarded as a relatively rare infectious disease in Austria with an annual incidence between 0.1 and 0.25 cases per 100,000 inhabitants in the years 1996 to 2007. In 2008 a record total of 31 culturally verified human cases of listeriosis were recorded for Austria (incidence 0.38 per 100,000 inhabitants), four of them were associated with pregnancy –The incidences are similar to those of most other western European countries (0.2-0.9). Lethality was high with 19% (6 out of 31) in 2008. This (usually) high rate and the sometimes severe permanent disabilities demand every effort to ascertain potential food-associated outbreaks as early as possible. In Austria an outbreak of febrile gastroenteritis associated with jellied pork contaminated with *Listeria monocytogenes* was documented in 2008 (Pichler J, Much P, Kasper S, Fretz R, Auer B et al. 2009: An outbreak of febrile gastroenteritis associated with jellied pork contaminated with *Listeria monocytogenes*. Wien. Klin. Wochenschr. (2009)121: 149-156).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Listeriosis is a rare disease, but not a rare bacterium, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, including pregnancy and immunosuppression. Although dairy products and salmon are likely candidates, the source of an infection often remains unclear. Ready-to-eat meat and meat products harbour listeria in 0–7 % and ready-to-eat smoked fish in 9 %.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A monthly report is sent to the Ministry of Health by the National Reference Center, whereas outbreaks are reported immediately.
Restrictions tightened to sell unpasteurised milk in remote areas (Alps).

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

More widespread information for pregnant and immunocompromised persons should be provided.

Additional information

The National Reference Center from the AGES (Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety) Vienna coordinates the confirmation, subtyping and comparison of isolates.

4.3.2. Listeriosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

A monthly report is sent to the Ministry of Health by the National Reference Center, whereas outbreaks are reported immediately.

Case definition

A clinically compatible case that is laboratory confirmed after isolation of *L. monocytogenes* from a normally sterile site or vaginal swabs.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriology: Smears of the samples are Gram stained. Specimen from normally sterile sites are inoculated in blood culture broth or thioglycollate broth and Columbia blood agar plates, vaginal swabs are plated only directly on Columbia blood and colistin-nalidixic acid (CNA) agar. *L. monocytogenes* is identified by catalase and Api Listeria test.

Stool samples were examined after cold enrichment in Fraser enrichment broth and streaked onto selective chromogenic agar plate and Columbia blood-agar. All isolates obtained in Austria are sent to the National Reference Center for confirmation, subtyping and comparison.

Notification system in place

Medical doctors specialised in Laboratory Diagnosis or Microbiology and Hygiene and the attended physicians are subjected to notification. Infections, fatal cases and suspected cases of listeriosis have to be notified according to the National Regulation 254/2004 (BGBl. II, 254/2004, Anzeigepflichtige übertragbare Krankheiten 2004).

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

See 2.3.1. History of the disease

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See 2.3.1. History of the disease

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Listeriosis is a rare disease, but not a rare bacterium, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, including pregnancy and immunosuppression.

Although dairy products and salmon are likely candidates, the source of an infection often remains unclear.

Additional information

The National Reference Center at AGES, Vienna, coordinates the confirmation, subtyping and comparison of isolates.

Annual report of the National Reference Centre

http://www.bmg.gv.at/cms/site/attachments/4/4/2/CH0954/CMS1237532053435/jb_listerien_2008_02.02.09_b.pdf

Data source of Tables 54 and 55: Primary isolates from patients typed in the national reference centre for listeria

Table 54 Listeriosis in humans - species/serotype distribution

	Cases	Inc.
Listeriosis	31	0,37
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> 1/2a	13	0,16
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> 1/2b	5	0,06
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> 4b	13	0,16
Congenital cases	4	0,05
Deaths	6	0,07

Table 55 Listeriosis in humans - age distribution

Age group	<i>Listeriosis</i>			<i>L. monocytogenes</i>		
	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	3	0	3	3	0	3
1 to 4 years	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	0	0	0	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	0	0	0	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	3	1	2	3	1	2
45 to 64 years	8	6	2	8	6	2
65 years and older	17	7	10	17	7	10
Age unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0
All age groups	31	14	17	31	14	17

4.3.3. *Listeria* spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2008 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2008“ (BMGFJ-75500/0247-IV/B/7/2007 von 08.01.2008) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2007-2010) according to Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2008, approximately 40,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 60% (24,000) of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2008, eight relevant food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria (Schwerpunktprogramm 2008 BMGFJ-75500/0242-IV/B/7/2007). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs; a folder was created by the AGES in cooperation with the Austrian Medical Chamber: Pregnancy – infections transmitted via food (Schwangerschaft – Infektionen durch Nahrungsmittel, http://www.ages.at/uploads/media/AGES_Folder_Schwangerschaft_Web.pdf). This folder was

distributed to all gynaecologists. The folder contains advices to prevent food-borne infections during pregnancy, including listeriosis, toxoplasmosis, campylobacteriosis and salmonellosis as well as mycotoxicosis.

Campaign A-804-08: L. monocytogenes in food - Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - chilled - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: April - June

Type of specimen taken

Other processed food products and prepared dishes

Methods of sampling

Detection and enumeration method, sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of L. monocytogenes in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs.

Results of the investigation

105 samples tested, 3-times positive for L. monocytogenes (all <10 cfu/g); 2-times positive for Listeria innocua

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Salmonella spp.

Campaign A-029-08: L. monocytogenes in food - Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream - made from pasteurised milk - at catering - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September – November

Type of specimen taken

Cream, made from pasteurised milk

Methods of sampling

Detection and enumeration method, sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *L. monocytogenes* in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

96 samples tested, 0-times positive for *L. monocytogenes*.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Salmonella* spp.

Campaign A-803-08: *L. monocytogenes* in food - Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - at retail - imported - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: October - December

Type of specimen taken

cheeses made from pasteurised milk

Methods of sampling

Detection and enumeration method, sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *L. monocytogenes* in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

166 samples tested, 3-times positive for *L. monocytogenes* (1-time quantitative not detectable, 1-time 100 KBE/g, 1-time 13.900 KBE/g)

Campaign A-805-08: *L. monocytogenes* in food - Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: January - March

Type of specimen taken

cheeses made from raw or low heat-treated milk

Methods of sampling

Detection and enumeration method, sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *L. monocytogenes* in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

71 samples tested, Results: 1-time positive for *L. monocytogenes* (340 KBE/g); 1-time positive for *Listeria ivanovii*

Diagnostic/analytical methods used at the production plant or at retail

Qualitative detection of *Listeria* spp. is performed according to ISO 11290: Part 1 (1996). Quantification of *Listeria* spp. content in food is conducted either according to ISO 11290: Part 2 (1998) with following modifications: *Listeria monocytogenes* are confirmed on Ottaviani Agosti Agar, ALOA Agar, RapidLmono agar, using Gram stain, motility testing and catalase production or by the Api *Listeria* test or Vidas LMO II.

Results of the investigation

See tables below.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

Listeria monocytogenes was detected in samples of cheeses from pasteurised cows' milk – soft and semi-soft (Campaign A-803-08) in 1.8% (3/166) – one-time the content of *L. monocytogenes* was >100 cfu/g. In all the 292 tested samples of cheeses made from raw or low heat-treated cows' milk 6 samples were found positive for *L. monocytogenes*, 3-times the content was higher than 100 cfu/g. Additionally 3 samples were positive for *L. innocua*. In 15 out of 197 (7.6 %) single samples of cooked pig meat products, ready-to-eat, *Listeria monocytogenes* was detected and one-time the content was higher than 100 cfu/g. 6.3 % of samples from fishery products (6/96) revealed a contamination with *L. monocytogenes* lower than 100 cfu/g and also with *L. innocua* for 3-times.

Table 56 Listeria monocytogenes in milk and milky products

Categories	Sampling stage	Sampling unit	Sampling weight	Units tested	Total units positive for L. monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in 25 g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but ≤100 cfu/g	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g	L. innocua
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - imported (Campaign A-803-08)	at retail	single	25g	166	3	166	3	166	0	1	
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at farm	single	25g	12	0	12	0	0	0	0	
	at processing plant	single	25g	297	0	268	0	0	0	0	
	at retail	single	25g	242	0	233	0	162	0	0	
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at farm	single	25g	22	0	22	0	0	0	0	
	at processing plant	single	25g	201	2	193	2	0	0	0	
	at retail	single	25g	69	4	67	4	60	0	3	3
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at farm	single	25g	3	0	2	0	0	0	0	
	at processing plant	single	25g	40	0	34	0	0	0	0	
	at retail	single	25g	41	0	39	0	26	0	0	
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at farm	single	25g	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	
	at processing plant	single	25g	38	0	38	0	0	0	0	
	at retail	single	25g	26	0	25	0	26	0	0	
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk (Campaign A-805-08)	at retail	single	25g	71	1	71	1	71	0	1	1
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter	at processing plant	single	25g	44	0	44	0	0	0	0	
	at retail	single	25g	42	2	41	2	21	0	0	
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy desserts	at processing plant	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	
	at retail	single	25g	5	0	4	0	0	0	0	
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	at farm	single	25g	5	0	2	0	0	0	0	
	at processing plant	single	25g	126	0	103	0	0	0	0	
	at retail	single	25g	133	0	133	0	16	0	0	
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream - made from pasteurised milk (Campaign A-029-08)	at catering	single	25g	96	0	96	0	96	0	0	
Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk	at processing plant	single	25g	72	0	61	0	0	0	0	
	at retail	single	25g	15	0	10	0	12	0	0	
Milk, cows' - raw	at retail	single	25g	19	0	19	0	18	0	0	
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	at processing plant	single	25g	5	0	5	0	0	0	0	
	at retail	single	25g	3	1	3	1	0	0	0	

Table 57 *Listeria monocytogenes* in other foods

Categories	Sampling stage	Sampling unit	Sampling weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in 25g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but ≤100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g	<i>L. innocua</i>	<i>L. spp.</i> (non <i>monocytogenes</i>)	<i>L. ivanovii</i>	<i>L. seeligeri</i>
Bakery products	at processing plant	single	25g	9	0	9	0	0	0	0				
Bakery products - cakes	at retail	single	25g	69	0	69	0	67	0	0				
Bakery products - pastry	at retail	single	25g	62	0	62	0	61	0	0				
Crustaceans	at retail	single	25g	11	2	11	2	7	0	1				
Fish - raw	at retail	single	25g	12	0	9	0	4	0	0				
Fish - smoked fish	at retail	single	25g	94	4	12	3	12	0	0				
Fishery products, unspecified	at retail	single	25g	68	4	66	4	62	0	0	3			
	at processing plant	single	25g	28	2	2	2	0	0	0				
Fruits	at retail	single	25g	10	0	10	0	0	0	0				
Fruits - products	at retail	single	25g	24	0	24	0	0	0	0				
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh	at retail	single	25g	1	0	0	0	0	0	0				
Meat from deer (venison) - fresh	at retail	single	25g	2	1	1	1	0	0	0				
Meat from bovine - fresh	at retail	single	25g	5	1	5	1	5	0	0				
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	single	25g	1	0	0	0	0	0	0				
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail	single	25g	140	13	136	13	61	0	1				
	at processing plant	single	25g	57	2	56	2	54	0	0	2			
Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at processing plant	single	25g	5	0	0	0	0	0	0				
	at retail	single	25g	7	0	0	0	0	0	0				
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail	single	25g	13	0	13	0	13	0	0				
Meat, red meat - meat products - fermented sausages	at processing plant	single	25g	25	0	25	0	14	0	0				
	at retail	single	25g	22	1	1	1	0	0	0		1		
Mushrooms	at retail	single	25g	1	0	0	0	0	0	0				
Nuts and nut products	at retail	single	25g	1	0	0	0	0	0	0				
Other food	at catering	single	25g	20	0	18	0	0	0	0				
	at processing plant	single	25g	25	0	25	0	25	0	0				
	at retail	single	25g	27	1	1	1	0	0	0				1
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta	at catering	single	25g	18	0	18	0	0	0	0				
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - chilled (Campaign A-804-08)	at retail	single	25g	105	3	105	3	105	0	0	3			
	at processing plant	single	25g	6	0	0	0	0	0	0				
Ready-to-eat salads	at retail	single	25g	16	0	14	0	0	0	0				
	at processing plant	single	25g	16	0	14	0	0	0	0				
Spices and herbs	at retail	single	25g	1	0	0	0	0	0	0				
Vegetables	at retail	single	25g	2	0	0	0	0	0	0				

4.3.4. *Listeria* spp. in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

There is no active surveillance system and detection of cases is based on clinical observations.

Frequency of the sampling

When there is a suspected case.

Case definition

A case may be defined with positive histopathology and/or positive bacteriology. The animal is the epidemiological unit.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The diagnostic methods used include histopathology and bacteriology.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None

Notification system in place

No notification system of listeriosis in animal species available at this time.

Results of the investigation

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

As *Listeria* spp are present in the environment and also to a small degree in food-producing animals, a risk of contracting domestic listeriosis does exist.

Table 58 *Listeria* spp. in animals

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Listeria</i> spp.	<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	<i>L. innocua</i>	<i>Listeria</i> spp., unspecified
Cattle	at farm - animal sample - organ tissue	clinical investigations	animal	24	14	13	1	
dairy cows								
sheep	at farm - animal sample - milk	clinical investigations	animal	30	0			
sheep	at farm - animal sample - organ tissue	clinical investigations	animal	32	20	19		1
goats	at farm - animal sample - organ tissue	clinical investigations	animal	17	15	15		
Pigs				0				
Gallus gallus (fowl)				0				
Turkeys				0				
horses	at farm - animal sample - organ tissue	clinical investigations	animal	1	0			
alpine chamois	from hunting	clinical investigations	animal	1	0			
fallow deer	from hunting	clinical investigations	animal	1	0			

VET: all Institutes for Veterinary Disease Control

4.4. Verotoxic *Escherichia coli*

4.4.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In the year 2008, 893 samples were investigated at the Austrian Reference Center for *Enterohemorrhagic Escherichia coli* (EHEC). Thereby, 251 isolates (from 97 human [three humans with two different isolates each], 114 veterinary and 37 food samples) were confirmed, comprising 72 human EHEC and 28 human LP-STECS (Shiga toxin producing *E. coli* without *eae*-gene) isolates. In addition, 6 serologically identified EHEC cases were diagnosed (103 human cases in total). As in the year before, the ratio of EHEC O157 (31 isolates and 6 serologic cases) to EHEC non-O157 (41) was similar. Among the 103 diagnosed human EHEC and STEC cases in 2008, 17 cases were diagnosed with hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS) as post infectious complication (9 caused by O157, 2 by O26:H11, 2 by O111:H-, 1 by ONT:H11, and, interestingly, another 3 cases by STEC (O183:H18, O119:H4, O2:H6)). The incidence of HUS in children in Austria due to EHEC and STEC was about one HUS-case per 100.000 children (13 children) of age between 0 and 14 years in the year 2008. The number of EHEC/STEC cases varied markedly between the different provinces, led by the province Tyrol with 39 confirmed human EHEC/STEC cases. The reason for that may lie in a new EHEC screening program initiated in 2004.

There were no big outbreaks in Austria in 2008, only 10 small family outbreaks and one small outbreak involving a small village.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

The prevalence of isolated VTEC from calves but also from other cattle increased to more than 10%, but we hypothesize that this is due to a higher sensitivity of the new ELISA and the sampling material (rectum-anal swabs). Concerning the most important VTEC serotypes for humans (O157, O26, O103, O111 and O145) Serotype O157 could not be detected only one strain of VTEC O111 and one VTEC O145 could be found.

The relevance of findings of VTEC in feces seems to be low because VTEC are found only in a very low prevalence on meat samples from bovines and sheep.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

An Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of VTEC prevalence in bovine animals and sheep was implemented according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 17 November 2003 in the National Orders. The sampling was carried out throughout 2008 and follow up programs will be implemented in the forthcoming years.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Increased awareness and information should be made available for parents, paediatricians and general practitioners in regard to food safety and the prevention of infection.

Additional information

The National Reference Center at the Innsbruck Medical University coordinates the confirmation, subtyping and comparison of isolates. In addition, the Reference Center is involved in outbreak investigations. When EHEC is diagnosed in a patient, the patient as well as their family are interviewed using a questionnaire. The questionnaire helps obtain the necessary information in regard to the characteristics of the illness and potential exposure 6 days prior to onset. Thus, the

Reference Center contributes to finding the source of infection. The Reference Center also reports EHEC cases and coordinates environmental investigations with the Local and Regional Health Authorities.

4.4.2. Verocytotoxic Escherichia coli in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The National Reference Center provides a monthly report discussing recent outbreaks to the Ministry of Health.

Case definition

Clinical description: Clinical picture compatible with EHEC infection, e.g. diarrhoea (often bloody) and abdominal cramps. Illness may be complicated by haemolytic uraemic syndrome (HUS) or thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura (TTP).

Laboratory criteria for diagnosis: Detection of genes coding for Stx1/Stx2 production.

For probable cases: Isolation of E. coli belonging to a serogroup known to cause enterohaemorrhagic disease.

Serological confirmation in patients with HUS or TTP (only in selected cases).

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

1. Detection of E. coli O157 (most prominent serotype in HUS cases):

- Bacteriology: Isolation of O157 colonies on Sorbitol-MacConkey agar after incubation for 24 hours at 37 °C. O157 is confirmed via the E. coli O157 Latex Test.

- Serology: This method is constantly used at the German HUS-"Konsiliarlabor"; anti-O157 antibodies of IgG and IgM types can be distinguished.

2. Detection of Verotoxin (VTEC) -producing strains (used at the National Reference Center for EHEC/VTEC/STEC in Innsbruck): Stools are enriched overnight in a medium containing mitomycin C (EHEC Direct Medium, Heipha, Heidelberg, Germany). Enriched cultures are investigated for presence of Shiga toxins by commercial EIA (e.g. Premier, Novitec). Isolate identification is confirmed by conventional biochemical tests (API 20 E, bioMerieux, Marcy-l'Etoile, France).

Enrichments are plated on Sorbitol-MacConkey agar and incubated for 24 hours at 37 °C. Detection of stx1 and stx2 genes and of the genes encoding EHEC hemolysin (hlyA) and intimin (eae) is done by PCR (Gerber et al. (2002) J Infect Dis 186:493-500).

All EHEC/STEC/VTEC isolates obtained in Austria are sent to the National Reference Center for confirmation, subtyping and comparison. All Shiga toxin producing E. coli are serotyped with E. coli antisera (E. coli antisera, Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark). Comparison of the isolates is done by Pulsed-Field-Gel-Electrophoresis and Ribotyping.

Notification system in place

Medical doctors specialised in Laboratory Diagnosis or Microbiology and Hygiene and the attended physicians are required to report all notifiable diseases. Notification of bacteriological food-borne illness according to the epidemic act has been mandatory since 1950 (BGBl. 1950/186 Epidemiegesezt, as amended).

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

See History of the disease

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease

Relevance as a zoonotic disease

HUS is a rare complication of E.coli infection, however EHECs themselves are not rare, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, most of which are currently unknown. Although raw or undercooked meat and unpasteurised dairy products are likely candidates to transfer the bacterium to humans, the actual source of infection often remains unclear.

Additional information

The National Reference Center at Innsbruck Medical University coordinates the confirmation, subtyping and comparison of isolates.

Annual Report of the National Reference Center 2007 (2008 not available yet):

http://www.bmgfj.gv.at/cms/site/attachments/3/5/9/CH0951/CMS1214392137719/ehec_jb_2007.pdf

Data source of Tables 59 and 60: Primary isolates from patients typed in the national reference centre for EHEC (VTEC)

Table 59 Verocytotoxic Escherichia coli infections in man - species/serotype distribution

	Cases	Inc.	Autochtone	Imported	Unknown
HUS					
- clinical cases	17	0,20	17		
- lab. confirmed cases	17	0,20	17		
- caused by O157 (VT+)	9	0,11	8	1	
- caused by other VTEC	8	0,10	8		
E.coli infect. (except HUS)					
- clinical cases	86	1,03	86		
- laboratory confirmed	86	1,03	86		
- caused by O157 (VT+)	28	0,34	28		
- caused by other VTEC	58	0,70	57		1

Table 60 Verocytotoxic Escherichia coli infections in man - age distribution

Age group	Verotoxigenic <i>E.coli</i> (VTEC)			<i>E.coli</i> infections O157			<i>E.coli</i> infections non-O157		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	11	7	4	3	2	1	8	5	3
1 to 4 years	51	32	19	20	12	8	31	20	11
5 to 14 years	12	6	6	6	4	2	6	2	4
15 to 24 years	6	2	4	4	2	2	2	0	2
25 to 44 years	11	7	4	3	2	1	8	5	3
45 to 64 years	4	1	3	0	0	0	4	1	3
65 years and older	8	5	3	1	1	0	7	4	3
Age unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
All age groups	103	60	43	37	23	14	66	37	29

4.4.3. Pathogenic Escherichia coli in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2008 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2008“ (BMGFJ-75500/0247-IV/B/7/2007 von 08.01.2008) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the

multi-annual national control plan (2007-2010) according to Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2008, approximately 40,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 60% (24,000) of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2008, eight relevant food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria (Schwerpunktprogramm 2008 BMGFJ-75500/0242-IV/B/7/2007). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Results of the investigation

Campaign A-014-08: Verotoxigenic E. coli (VTEC) in food - Fruits - non-precut - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at restaurants by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: May - June

Type of specimen taken

Fruits, non-precut (strawberries)

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of VTEC in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

96 samples tested, 0-times positive for VTEC

Campaign A-802-08: Verotoxigenic E. coli (VTEC) in food - Meat from sheep - fresh - chilled - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system**Sampling strategy**

Sampling is done according to the monitoring plan from the Ministry of Health for food items of special interest for defined parameters. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: February - April

Type of specimen taken

Meat from sheep, fresh

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of VTEC in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

59 samples tested, 4-times positive for VTEC (O6:H-; ONT:H2; O166:H28; 3 serotypes in one sample O75:H-, O128:H-, ONT:H14)

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Table 61 Verocytotoxic Escherichia coli in food

Categories	Sampling stage	Sampling unit	Sampling weight	Units tested	Total units positive for VTEC	VTEC O6: H-	VTEC ONT: H2	VTEC O166: H28	VTEC O75: H-	VTEC O128: H-	VTEC ONT: H14
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	single	25g	4	0						
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail	single	25g	7	0						
Meat from sheep - fresh - chilled (A-802-08)	at retail	single	25g	59	4*	1	1	1	1	1	1
Meat, red meat, meat products - fermented sausages	at retail	single	25g	7	0						
Milk, cows' - raw	at retail	single	25g	2	0						
Fruits - non-precut (Campaign A-014-08)	at retail	single	25g	96	0						

*3 serotypes in one sample

4.4.4. Pathogenic Escherichia coli in animals

A. Verotoxigenic Escherichia coli in cattle (bovine animals)

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

The monitoring program on the prevalence of VTEC in slaughtered animals: In the previous years, a higher prevalence of VTEC in calves could be observed compared to cattle of other age groups. In 2008, two monitoring programs were implemented, one on calves and one on cattle older than 6 months. Therefore, 50 slaughtered calves and 50 slaughtered cattle older than 6 months had to be tested in 2008; this was based on the approx. 86,000 calves and 590,000 cattle (except calves) slaughtered in 2007.

The sampling was stratified based on the number of processed animals per abattoir in Austria. The date of sampling was randomized over the 2008. Sampling was performed in the 22 abattoirs which processed more than 80 % of Austria's cattle in 2007.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at slaughter

The sampling was distributed randomly over the period of the study from January to December 2008.

Type of specimen taken

Animals at slaughter

A portion of the caecum containing a minimum of 50 to 100 grams and rectum-anal tissue from the same animal.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Animals at slaughter

The sampling is performed by qualified veterinarians who carry out the post – mortem inspection. At time of evisceration, a portion of the caecum was ligated and wrapped in a sterile plastic bag; additionally a part of rectum and anus in a separate bag. After cooling down to 4 °C, the samples have been sent to the AGES Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz the same day, in a hobbox or polystyrene box along with cooling packs. In the laboratory, a portion content of each caecum was inoculated into broth as well as a swab from a rectum-anal mucosal swab in a second broth.

Case definition

Animals at slaughter

An animal is considered to be infected with VTEC following the isolation of VTEC (verotoxin producing E. coli irrespective of intimin) from its intestine/ rectum-anal mucosa.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Animals at slaughter

In a first step the samples are screened for verotoxins by ELISA, secondly the positive samples are investigated for VTEC isolates.

At first approximately 1 g of content of the caecum and one swab was pre-enriched in two test tubes using modified tryptic soy broth containing novobiocin (mTSB + n) for 5 hours at 37 °C on a shaker. Then 1 ml of each pre-enrichment was inoculated into mTSB + n containing mitomycin C for 18-20 hours at 37 °C on a shaker too. The process was followed by testing the enrichment for the occurrence of verotoxin in an enzyme linked immuno sorbent assay (ELISA, Premier TM EHEC).

Positive enrichments were plated on MacConkey (MAC) - and on cefixime tellurite sorbitol MAC (CTSMAC) agar and incubated for 24 hours at 37 °C. 2-4 colonies from each of the plates were subcultured on MAC as well as on CTSMAC. Afterwards the genomes of subcultured E. coli were investigated in a real time PCR for harboring the genes for Verotoxin 1, Verotoxin 2, Intimin and Enterohemolysin (Reischl U. et al. 2002: Real-Time Fluorescence PCR Assays for Detection and Characterization of Shiga Toxin, Intim and Enterohemolysin Genes from Shiga Toxin-Producing Escherichia coli. Journ. of Clin. Microb., 40, p. 2555-2565).

The serotyping was carried out by the National Reference Centre for EHEC in Innsbruck.

Statistical analysis was performed with EpiInfo version 3.5.1.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Harmonization of methods, although not only a method for the five most important important serotypes.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen

Notification system in place

No notification system in place at this time.

Results of the investigation

Calves: 50 caeca and 36 rectum-anal tissue from 50 slaughtered calves were sampled; in 15 caeca (30%) and 18 rectum-anal swabs (50%) Verotoxin was detected by the ELISA. Although VTEC could be isolated only from 7 caeca (14.0%; CI 95% 5.8-26.7) and 7 swabs (19.4%; CI 95% 8.2-36.0). In several samples more than one VTEC serotype were identified.

Cattle (other than calves): 46 caeca and 34 rectum-anal tissue from 46 slaughtered cattle were sampled; in 8 caeca (17.4%) and 22 rectum-anal swabs (64.7%) Verotoxin was detected by the ELISA. Although VTEC could be isolated only from 7 caeca (15.2%; CI 95% 6.3-28.9) and 4 swabs (11.8%; CI 95% 3.3-27.5). In several samples more than one VTEC serotype were identified.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The prevalence of isolated VTEC from calves but also from other cattle increased to more than 10%, but we hypothesize that this is due to a higher sensitivity of the new ELISA and the sampling material (rectum-anal swabs).

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance of findings of VTEC in faeces seems to be low because VTEC are found only in a very low prevalence on meat samples from bovines.

Additional information

Nil

B. Verotoxigenic E. coli (VTEC) in animal - Sheep

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Monitoring program on the prevalence of VTEC in sheep at farm:

The monitoring in 2007 was directed towards sheep at farms. 50 sheep had to be tested, calculated on a population of sheep of 350,000 in Austria in 2007. The sampling had been stratified on the number and size of sheep holdings in Austrian provinces.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at farm:

The sampling of feces was done after blood sampling in course of the Brucella melitensis control program.

Type of specimen taken

Animals at farm: Feces.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Animals at farm:

Feces samples were wrapped in a sterile plastic bag. After cooling the sample down to 4 °C, it was sent in a hobbox or polystyrene box after adding cooling units to the AGES Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz. In the laboratory, a portion of the feces (ca. 1 g) was inoculated into broth.

Case definition

Animals at farm

An animal is considered to be infected with VTEC following the isolation of VTEC (verotoxin producing E. coli irrespective of intimin) from its feces.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Animals at farm

In a first step the samples are screened for verotoxins by ELISA, secondly the positive samples are investigated for VTEC isolates.

At first approximately 1 g of feces was preenriched in two test tubes using modified tryptic soy broth containing novobiocin (mTSB + n) for 5 hours at 37 °C on a shaker. Then 1 ml of the preenrichment was inoculated into mTSB + n containing mitomycin C for 18-20 hours at 37 °C on a shaker too.

More details see in chapter: Verotoxigenic Escherichia coli in cattle (bovine animals).

Statistical analysis was performed with EpiInfo version 3.3.2.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Harmonization of methods

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen

Notification system in place

No notification

Results of the investigation

38 feces samples from sheep were sampled. In 13 samples (34.2%) Verotoxin was detected by the ELISA. VTEC could be isolated from 10 (26.3%; CI 95% 13.4-43.1) samples. In one sample more than one VTEC serotype was identified.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The prevalence of isolated VTEC from sheep increased to more than 20%, but we hypothesize that this is due to a higher sensitivity of the new ELISA.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance of findings of VTEC in feces of sheep seems to be low because sheep meat is consumed well-done.

Additional information

Nil

Table 62 Verocytotoxic Escherichia coli in animals

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for VTEC	VTEC O157	VTEC O103:H2	VTEC O111:H-	VTEC O116:H-	VTEC O116:H12	VTEC O118:H16	VTEC O119:H-	VTEC O119:H4	VTEC O119:HNT	VTEC O125:H51	VTEC O128abc:H10	VTEC O145:H-	VTEC O146:H28	VTEC O174:H2	VTEC O177:H-	VTEC O5:H-	VTEC O5:H8	VTEC O55:H2	VTEC O78:H-	VTEC O8:H2	VTEC O8:H21	VTEC O84:H2	VTEC ONT:H-	VTEC ONT:H16	VTEC ONT:H19	VTEC ONT:H2	VTEC ONT:H21	VTEC ONT:H49	VTEC ONT:H8	VTEC NT	VTEC Orough:H-	VTEC Orough:H12	VTEC Orough:H29		
Calves, under 1 year	at slaughter house	monitoring-objective sampling	feces	I	animal	50	7	0	0	1	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
Calves, under 1 year	at slaughter house	monitoring-objective sampling	swab mucosa	I	animal	36	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	2	0
cattle older 1 year	at slaughter house	monitoring-objective sampling	feces	I	animal	46	7	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	1	2	0	0	0	1	
cattle older 1 year	at slaughter house	monitoring-objective sampling	swab mucosa	I	animal	34	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	
Sheep	at farm	monitoring-objective sampling	feces	I	animal	38	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	
Goats						0																																				

I – AGES Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Graz

4.5. Tuberculosis

4.5.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Human tuberculosis has steadily declined during the last decades. Commission Decision 1999/467/EC of 15 July 1999 established the officially tuberculosis-free status of bovine herds of Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Bovine tuberculosis poses no public health problem in Austria., sheep, goats and pigs are free of bovine tuberculosis. Although in spring 2008 in one slaughtered cattle infective lung tuberculosis was diagnosed caused by *M. caprae*. All cattle of that holding were culled following an intra cutan testing showing several positive reactors. Two more cattle holdings with several reagents were culled and some single reactors in contact holdings. In 21 cattle out of 14 holdings *M. caprae* was isolated. Since several years a reservoir of *M. caprae* in red deer in one Austrian region has been confirmed and cattle are exposed to the bacteria in the summertime grazing on contaminated pastures in the alps.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

No findings of *M. bovis* in animals, although *M. caprae* was detected.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A new national regulation has been implemented due to the finding of *M. caprae* in cattle from a certain region (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBL II 2008/322). This regulation obliges the intracutan testings (using simultaneously bovine and avium tuberculin) off all cattle and goats that are kept together with cattle in given districts due to the epidemiological situation.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Continuation of the existing control programs

Additional information

Nil

4.5.2. Tuberculosis in humans

A. Tuberculosis due to *Mycobacterium bovis* in humans

Case definition

Definite: A case with isolation of *M. tuberculosis* complex (except *M. bovis* BCG) from any clinical specimen.

Other than definite: A case that meets the clinical criteria above but does not meet the laboratory criteria of a definite case.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Definite: Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen, Auramin-Rhodamin stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material

- Culture: After decontamination of the homogenised sample material in NALC-NaOH and centrifugation, the sample material is transferred in parallel on Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing glycerol and PACT and Stonebrink agar containing PACT and MGITmedium. The media are incubated at 37 °C for up to 8 weeks. Confirmation of the species by Amplicor (Roche)
- Other than definite: A skin test and an X-Ray of the thorax are performed.

Notification system in place

The person who diagnoses (laboratory/hospital/general practitioner) has to notify definite (*M. tuberculosis* and *M. bovis*) and other than definite cases (this excludes radiologists) to the local health authority (Federal Law BGBl. 127/1968: Tuberkulosegesetz, as amended; Epidemiegesetz 1950, as amended). *M. bovis* is notifiable since 2004 (National Regulation BGBl. Nr. 254/2004: Anzeigepflichtige übertragbare Krankheiten 2004).

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis (NRL-T) has been nominated since 1995. Since 1998 all data are compiled in a national database.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Preliminary *M. bovis* was isolated from three cases and *M. caprae* from two human cases.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

The relevance is inconsiderable; in 2008 only five out of preliminary 498 human tuberculosis cases were caused by *M. bovis* or *M. caprae*.

Additional information

Annual report of the National Reference Center from 2007 (2008 not available yet):

http://www.bmgfi.gv.at/cms/site/attachments/3/5/9/CH0951/CMS1214392137719/tb_ib_2007.pdf

Data Source of Tables 63 and 64: national reference centre for tuberculosis, preliminary data (by 26.06.2009)

Table 63 Tuberculosis in humans - species/serotype distribution

	Cases	Incidence/ 100.000	Autochtone cases	Imported cases	unknown
Tuberculosis	631	7,53	337	209	85
<i>M. bovis</i>	3	0,04	1	2	0
<i>M. tuberculosis</i>	404	4,82	198	122	84
<i>M. caprae</i>	2	0,02	2	0	0
Reactivation of previous cases	38	0,45	23	12	3
Tuberculosis other than definitive	222	2,65	136	85	1

Table 64 Tuberculosis in humans - age distribution

Age group	Tuberculosis due to <i>M. bovis</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. caprae</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. tuberculosis</i>		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	4	3
5 to 14 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	3	2
15 to 24 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	53	29	24
25 to 44 years	1	0	1	0	0	0	142	85	57
45 to 64 years	1	0	1	1	1	0	108	86	22
65 years and older	1	1	0	1	1	0	89	51	38
Age unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
All age groups	3	1	2	2	2	0	404	258	146

4.5.3. Mycobacterium spp. in animals

A. *Mycobacterium bovis* in bovine animals

Status as officially free of bovine tuberculosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

According to Council Directive 64/432/EWG from June 26, 1964, Austria has the status Officially Tuberculosis Free Member State declared in the Commission Decision 1999/467/EC from July 15th, 1999, replaced by Commission Decision 2003/467/EC from June 23rd, 2003. The national surveillance programme is regulated Decree GZ 39.624/24-IX/A/8/2000. The monitoring programme is based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection in which all cattle and goats originating from an official tuberculosis free holding have to be tested for tuberculous alterations.

A new national Regulation has been implemented due to the finding of *M. caprae* in cattle from a certain region (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008). This Regulation includes provisions which apply for all Mycobacteria belonging to the Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex; therefore also a compulsory notification is existing.

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Specimen are taken from carcasses with macroscopically observable alterations, characteristic for tuberculosis. They are sampled in slaughterhouses and sent to the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals.

All cattle in holdings of designated regions given in annex 2 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 2008/322) were subjected to simultaneous intracutan testing.

Frequency of the sampling

Continuous post-mortem inspections of each slaughtered bovine and caprine animal.

Intracutan testing: All cattle in holdings of designated regions given in annex 2 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 322/2008).

Type of specimen taken

Organs/tissues: Tissues that are macroscopically altered due to tuberculosis, inclusive lymph nodes (according to Annex 4 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008).

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The alterations and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals.

Case definition

According to Order "Richtlinien für die veterinärbehördliche Überwachung zur Erhaltung der Freiheit der österreichischen Rinderbestände von Rindertuberkulose" und zur "Durchführung und Beurteilung der intrakutanen Tuberkulinprobe" (GZ 39.624/24-IX/A/8/2000): Tubercles pathogenomically for tuberculosis detected in course of the post-mortem inspection or Mycobacterium bovis or Mycobacterium tuberculosis isolated from suspected material.

Results of the intracutan test: Doubtful and positive reactions are defined (see Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 2008/322).

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Intracutan testing (simultaneous testing using bovine and avium tuberculin): The test is performed according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964, as amended and the national Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 322/2008).

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material.

Culture: After decontamination of the homogenised sample material in NALC and centrifugation, the sample material is transferred in parallel on Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing glycerol and PACT and Stonebrink agar containing PACT and Middlebrook medium. The media are incubated at 37 °C for up to 8 weeks.

Confirmation of the Mycobacterium species by PCR (De los Monteros et al. 1998: Journal of Clinical Microbiology 36: 239-242) in the National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals.

Vaccination policy

Due to the importance of the intracutan tests for diagnostic purposes, vaccinations are prohibited.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered bovine and caprine carcasses originating from official tuberculosis free holding and intracutan tests in animals of given regions according to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

The control programs are based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered bovine and caprine carcasses originating from an official tuberculosis free holding.

Intracutan tests are performed in animals in holdings of given regions according to the epidemiological situation, defined in the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The carcass is condemned.

Loss of the status OTF for the holding from which the animal was originated and for contact holdings. It is prohibited to bring bovines and goats in and out of the holding. Slaughtering of cows and goats can only be allowed by the official veterinarian and has to be performed using a special testing and slaughtering frame. Epidemiological investigations have to be done.

Prohibition of keeping these animals together with animals from OTF-holdings on pastures or market places etc.

Regaining the status OTF:

There must be no animals in the holding showing signs of clinical tuberculosis

All animals are recruited from an OTF-holding

Animals have to be tested according to the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 322/2008).

No reactors are identified after two intradermal testings of all animals in the holding older than 6 months examined earliest 60 days (first tuberculin test) and earliest 4 months (second tuberculin test) but latest 12 months after elimination of the last reactor.

Notification system in place

A suspected case of tuberculosis must be notified

Results of the investigation

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No findings of *M. bovis* in cattle. Due to the fact that *M. caprae* is endemic in wildlife deer in Western parts of Austria (and South-Western parts of Germany), cattle in this areas should be observed with higher sensitivity. The National Regulation concerning Bovine Tuberculosis has been revised and set into force on 1. September 2008 (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 2008/322).

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)
Nil

Additional information

M. caprae is differentiated in Austria.

B. *Mycobacterium bovis* in farmed deer

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Due to the identification of *M. caprae* in several cattle holdings new control programmes have been developed to be implemented in 2009.

Frequency of the sampling

Every shot farmed deer that is foreseen to be used as a food is subjected to pre and post mortem inspection. Pre mortem inspection can be performed by the livestock owner if the owner is trained in this special inspection and if the Veterinarian has assured himself of the physical health of the animal within the last month prior to slaughtering.

Type of specimen taken

Other: Macroscopically tuberculous alterations and lymph nodes

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The alterations and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals.

Case definition

Tubercles pathognomically for tuberculosis detected in course of the post-mortem inspection or Mycobacterium bovis or Mycobacterium tuberculosis isolated from suspected material

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stain is performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material

Culture: After decontamination of the homogenised sample material in NALC and centrifugation, the sample material is transferred in parallel on Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing glycerol and PACT and Stonebrink agar containing PACT and Middlebrook medium. The media are incubated at 37 °C up to 8 weeks.

Confirmation of the Mycobacterium species by PCR (De los Monteros et al. 1998: Journal of Clinical Microbiology 36: 239-242) in the National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is prohibited.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

The control programs are based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered carcasses originating from an official tuberculosis free holding

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

In 2009, new programmes will be implemented.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The carcass is condemned. Further measures according to Tierseuchengesetz RGBL. 1909/177 as amended.

Notification system in place

The suspicion and finding of tuberculosis is notifiable.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No cases of M. bovis in 2008.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

No cases of M. bovis in 2008.

Additional information

Nil

C. Mycobacterium spp. in animal - all animals - at slaughter – Control programme - mandatory - official sampling (all slaughtered animals except those mentioned above)

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Samples from suspected swine are taken in slaughterhouses. Sampling is performed when tissue of slaughtered animals is visibly altered, seen by the unaided eye.

Goats in defined regions that are kept together with cattle are subjected to intracutan testing (see chapter Mycobacterium bovis bovine animals; Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBL II 2008/322).

Frequency of the sampling

Continuous post-mortem inspections of each slaughtered animal

Type of specimen taken

Other: Macroscopic tuberculous alterations and lymphnodes

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The altered tissue and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the laboratory

Case definition

Tubercles pathognomically for tuberculosis detected in course of the post-mortem inspection or Mycobacterium bovis or Mycobacterium tuberculosis or Mycobacterium avium isolated from suspected material

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material

Culture: After decontamination of the homogenised sample material in NALC and centrifugation, the sample material is transferred in parallel on Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing glycerol and PACT and Stonebrink agar containing PACT and Middlebrook medium. The media are incubated at 37°C up to 8 weeks.

Confirmation of the Mycobacterium species by PCR (De los Monteros et al. 1998: Journal of Clinical Microbiology 36: 239-242) in the National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is prohibited.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

The control programs are based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered carcasses originating from an official tuberculosis free holding

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No need at the moment

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The carcass is condemned. Further measures are performed according to Tierseuchengesetz RGBL. 1909/177, as amended.

Notification system in place

The detection of tuberculosis is notifiable.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No cases in Austria in 2008.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

No cases in Austria in 2008.

Additional information

Nil

Table 65 Bovine tuberculosis in countries and regions that do not receive Community co-financing for eradication programme

Member State: Austria..... Date of the report: 25.05.2009..... Year: 2008.....											
The official post-mortem examination for all slaughtered bovine animals is implemented: Yes											
Region (1)	Total number of existing bovine		Officially free herds		Infected herds * all M. capra		Routine tuberculin testing		Number of tuberculin tests carried out before the introduction into the herds (Annex A(I)(2)(c) third indent (1) of Directive 64/432/EEC)	Number of animals with suspicious lesions of tuberculosis examined and submitted to histopathological and bacteriological examinations	Number of animals detected positive in bacteriological examination *all M. caprae
	Herds	Animals	Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Interval between routine tuberculin tests (2)	Number of animals tested			
Austria	76845	1999866	76831	99,982*	14*	0,018	a)	20222	5	119	21*
Total	76845	1999866	76831	99,982*	14*	0,018	a)	20222	5	119	21*

* all "M. caprae": Same measures for control and eradication as for M.bovis

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Use the following letter codes: (a) no routine tests; (b) tests once a year; (c) tests every two years; (d) tests every three years concerning 24 month-old animals; (f) tests every 4 years; (g) others (please give details).

Table 66 Tuberculosis in other animals

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Mycobacteriaspp.</i>
Sheep	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante- mortem and post- mortem inspection	CVS	animal	318,921	0
Goats	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante- mortem and post- mortem inspection	CVS	animal	45,036	0
Pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante- mortem and post- mortem inspection	CVS	animal	5,556,508	0

CVS: Central Veterinary Service

4.6. Brucellosis

4.6.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In Austria, human brucellosis cases are considered to be an imported infectious disease. Austria has the status Officially Brucellosis Free (OBF).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Five human cases were identified in 2008; all cases were imported.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A new national regulation has been implemented concerning the examination of milk- and bloodsamples in cattle (Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305).

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Continuation of the existing control programs

Additional information

Nil

4.6.2. Brucellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

Notification of cases according to EU case definitions.

Case definition

Clinical description: Clinical picture compatible with brucellosis, e.g. acute or insidious onset of fever, night sweats, fatigue, anorexia, weight loss, headache and arthralgia.

Laboratory criteria for diagnosis

- Demonstration of a specific antibody response
- Isolation of *Brucella* spp. from a clinical specimen
- Identification and confirmation of the species by PCR.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Serological examination: Serum samples are tested in the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) with reference standard antisera from CVL-Weybridge. Participation in international ring trials: Brucellosis European Ring Trial 2000 and 2002 (VLA Weybridge) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and SAT.

- Bacteriological: Multiple blood samples are inoculated in blood culture broth over several consecutive days. The incubation lasted 4 to 6 weeks, once per week medium is transferred on brucella agar and incubated 5-10 % CO₂ atmosphere (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123- 126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 56).

- The genus is identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using brucella serum. The species is identified by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific sera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.)

Notification system in place

Medical doctors specialised in Laboratory Diagnosis or Microbiology and Hygiene and the attended physicians are required to report all new cases. Notification of brucellosis according to the epidemic act has been mandatory since 1950 (BGBl. 1950/186 Epidemiegesetz, as amended).

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Austria is OBF and OBmF. All cases reported in Austria are epidemiologically linked to travel in endemic countries or to foreign workers from endemic countries.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

This zoonosis has no relevance in Austria.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Nil

Data source of Tables 67 and 68: Notification of single cases

Table 67 Brucellosis in humans - species/serotype distribution

	Cases	Notification rate/100.000	Autochtone cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
Brucellosis	5	0,1	0	5	0
<i>B. abortus</i>	1	0,0	0	1	0
<i>Brucella spp.</i>	4	0,0	0	4	0

Table 68 Brucellosis in humans - age distribution

Age group	<i>Brucellosis</i>			<i>B. abortus</i>			<i>Brucella spp.</i>		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
25 to 44 years	2	1	1	0	0	0	2	1	1
45 to 64 years	2	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
65 years and older	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Age unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
All age groups	5	2	3	1	1	0	4	1	3

4.6.3. Brucella in foodstuffs

Due to the fact that Austria is OBF and OBmF, food is not investigated for *Brucella spp.*

4.6.4. **Brucella spp. in animals**

A. *Brucella abortus* in Bovine Animals

Status as officially free of bovine brucellosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

Upon the request of the Commission Decision of July 15th 1999, CD 1999/466/EC, as amended, by the Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964, Austria achieved the status: officially brucellosis-free for bovine herds.

A new national regulation has been implemented concerning the examination of milk- and bloodsamples in cattle (Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305). This means that in the case of dairy herds, the examination of milk samples in accordance with Annex C of Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964 can be performed.

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Nationwide all bovine milk producing holdings were subjected to bulk milk testing.

In non-milk producing holdings a risk based sampling plan was performed.

Abortion or premature birth: Abortive material and blood of the cow is sampled

Frequency of the sampling

Bulk milk sampling: All milk producing holdings had been sampled minimum once per year according to the new regulation (§6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305). In case of not-negative bulk milk samples, blood samples in the affected holding were investigated.

Holdings without milk production: A risk based sampling plan has been calculated stratified according to the different provinces (§6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305). If blood serology does not show a definitive negative result diagnostic slaughtering of the affected animal has to be carried out.

- Abortion or premature birth: Tissue and blood from the cow is sampled immediately post abortion. If the result of the first serological examination was negative, a second blood sample was taken 2 weeks post abortion for serological testing. If this result was negative again, sampling and testing was repeated after two weeks.

Type of specimen taken

Bulk milk

Blood samples

Diagnostic slaughtering: organs and lymph nodes of the genital tract; udder and accessory lymph nodes; fetus (stomach, lungs); retropharyngeal lymph node.

Abortion or premature birth: Tissue and blood samples from the animal that had an abortion.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Bulk milk sampling: §6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305.

Holdings without milk production: According to the sampling plan individual blood samples are taken in the holdings and sent to the laboratories (§6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305).

Diagnostic slaughtering: §6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305.

Abortion or premature birth: Aborted tissue and blood samples sent to a veterinary laboratory.

Case definition

An animal is considered to be positive for *Brucella abortus*, in case of positive blood-serological test result and the epidemiological situation of the herd indicates the possibility that a brucella infection has been introduced to the herd or in case of bacteriological isolation. If a single animal reactor is detected in the holding, tracing back is an important tool to get more information about the animal.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bulk milk: Testings according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and the manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals of the OIE.

Blood samples: Testings according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and the manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals of the OIE: Routinely single serum samples or serum pools (5 sera in one pool) were tested in the Indirect-ELISA (I-ELISA) using the three OIE ELISA *Brucella* Standard Sera (OIE ELISAwpsS, OIE ELISAspS, OIE ELISAnSS) and the OIE *Brucella abortus* Positive International Standard Antiserum (OIEISS) to calibrate the method (Commission Regulation 535/2002/EC of 21 March 2002 amending Annex C to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and amending Decision 2000/330/EC). Following a positive or suspected test result in the IELISA single serum samples were also tested in the Complement Fixation Test (CFT), Rose Bengal test (RBT) and Competitive ELISA (C-ELISA). Participation in international ring trials:

Participation in international ring trials (Weybridge, AFSSA and other) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and Serum Agglutination Test (SAT). The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all Veterinary Institutes.

Abortion or premature birth: Aborted material was tested bacteriologically and serologically as described above. **Bacteriology:** Smears of the samples are stained by Stableforth's method. *Brucella* agar and Columbia agar (Merck) containing selective additives were used (Oxoid). After inoculation the media were incubated for 4-10 days at 37°C in an atmosphere containing 10% CO₂. The genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using *brucella* serum. The species was differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific sera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not allowed (BGBl. 1957/147, Bangseuchengesetz, § 13 Impfung)

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Control programme according to the National Regulation (Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305). Abortion or premature birth: Compulsory notification according BGBl 1957/147, Bangseuchengesetz, as amended, §11 Anzeigepflicht;

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No actions, because OBF

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to BGBl 1957/147, Bangseuchengesetz, as amended, and BGBl 1909/177, Tierseuchengesetz, as amended

Notification system in place

Abortion or premature birth: Notification of abortions: The livestock owner has to notify each abortion within 24 hours to the mayor (Gemeinde). The mayor has to forward the notification to the local authority (Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde) (BGBl. 1957/147, Bangseuchengesetz, § 11 Anzeigepflicht). If the cow is being treated by a veterinarian or the veterinarian has been informed about the abortion, then the veterinarian has to notify to the official authority (Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde).

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

OBF

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

Nil

B. Brucella melitensis in Sheep and Goats

Status as officially free of ovine brucellosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

According to Commission Decision Nr. 93/52/EWG, as amended, Austria has the status officially brucellosis (B. melitensis) free (ObmF).

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

To maintain the status officially brucellosis (B. melitensis) free, according to BGBl. 2002/184 (Brucella melitensis-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002) a representative number of samples were examined with a confidence level of 95 % to detect infected holdings at a target prevalence of 0.2 %. Sampling was performed by the competent authority or under its supervision, by bodies to which it had delegated this responsibility. Samples were taken in the holdings. Aborted material and blood samples from the animal were also investigated.

Frequency of the sampling

Principally the sampling was performed during the cold season, between November and May when the animals were kept in the stables.

Type of specimen taken

- Monitoring: Blood samples according to a sampling plan.
- Clinical cases: Aborted material and blood samples from the affected animal.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Individual blood samples and aborted material are taken within the holdings and sent to the laboratories.

Case definition

An animal is considered to be infected with *B. melitensis* in case of bacteriological isolation or positive serological test result.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Routinely single serum samples were tested in the Indirect ELISA. Confirmation of suspected or positive results was performed by the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) with reference standard antisera from CVL-Weybridge. Participation in international ring trials on Brucellosis (Weybridge and other) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and SAT. The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all national Veterinary Institutes.

Bacteriology: Smears of the samples were stained by Stableforth's method.

Brucella agar and Columbia agar (Merck) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media are incubated for 4 - 10 days at 37 °C in an atmosphere containing 10 % CO₂. The genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using brucella serum. The species were differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific sera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

According to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002, §4, Impfverbot) vaccination is not allowed.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Monitoring program and investigation of abortions

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

To maintain the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free, according to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002) a representative number of samples have to be examined with a confidence level of 95 % to detect infected holdings at a prevalence of 0.2 %. Sampling is performed by the appropriate authority or under its supervision, by bodies to which it has delegated this responsibility. Samples are taken in the holdings.

Notification and clarification of each clinical case by bacteriology and serology.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

ObmF

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002, §3, Ausmerzung von Reagenten) reactors have to be culled, the carcasses have to be incinerated in an incineration plant.

Notification system in place

Notification of brucellosis or a suspicion of brucellosis according to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002).

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

ObmF

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

Nil

D. *Brucella suis* in animal – Pigs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

According to Guideline 64/432/EEC as amended.

Frequency of the sampling

Targeted, following abortion and in positive cases contact holdings.

Type of specimen taken

- Monitoring: Blood samples;
- Clinical cases: Abortion material and blood samples from the affected animal; tissues: according to decree 74700/0132-IV/B/5/2008

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Individual blood samples and abortion material are taken from animals in the holdings and sent to the laboratories.

Case definition

An animal is considered to be serologically positive for brucellosis following one/more positive CFT Complement Fixation Test (CFT) and RBT Rose Bengal test (RBT) results (B. abortus used antigen). A bacteriological isolation may also be possible as in the case of B. suis.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Due to the fact that a *Brucella suis* antigen is not available, the B. abortus antigen is used for the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) and the Rose Bengal test (RBT) because B. abortus shows cross reactions with B. suis antibodies.
 - ELISA and CFT is not available, the B. abortus ELISA and CFT are used because these tests show cross reactions with B. suis antibodies.
 - Participation in international ring trials: Brucellosis European Ring Trial 2000 and 2002 (VLA Weybridge) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and Serum Agglutination Test (SAT). The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all Veterinary Institutes.
- Bacteriology: Quality control: Laboratory strains
- Smears of the samples are stained by Stableforth's method
 - *Brucella* agar and Columbia agar (Merck) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media are incubated for 4-10 days at 37 °C in an atmosphere containing 10 % CO₂. The genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using brucella serum. The species were differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with
-

monospecific sera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No mandatory measures but notification is required.

Notification system in place

B. suis has been a notifiable disease since 1993 according to BGBl 1993/756, Tierseuchen-Anzeigepflichtverordnung, as amended.

Results of the investigation

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Due to the results of the passive monitoring in pigs (no cases of *B. suis*) we conclude that there is no need for an active monitoring program.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

Nil

Table 69 Bovine Brucellosis data from countries and regions that do not receive Community co-financing (non co-financed)

Member State: Austria Date of report: 19.05.2009..... Year: 2008.....																					
Region (1)	Total number of existing bovine		Officially free herds		Infected herds		Surveillance (2)						Investigations of suspect cases								
			Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Serological tests			Examination of bulk milk samples			Information on abortions			Epidemiological investigation					
	Herds	Animals					Number of bovine herds tested	Number of animals tested	Number of infected herds	Number of bovine herds tested	Number of animals or pools tested	Number of infected herds	Number of notified abortions whatever cause	Number of isolations of <i>Brucella</i> infections	Number of abortions due to <i>Brucella abortus</i>	Number of animals tested with serological blood tests	Number of suspended herds	Number of positive animals		Number of animals examined microbologically	Number of animals positive microbologically
Austria	76845	1999866	76844	99,999	1	0,001	4254	36772	1	37858	37996	0	897	0	0	1045	163	0	0	4	0
Total	76845	1999866	76844	99,999	1	0,001	4254	36772	1	37858	37996	0	897	0	0	1045	163	0	0	4	0

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Please give details.

Table 70 Ovine and caprine brucellosis - data from countries that do not receive co-financing for control or eradication programme

Member State: Austria..... Date of report: Year: 2008.....														
Region (1)	Total number of existing ovine/caprines		Officially free herds		Infected herds		Surveillance (2)			Investigations of suspect cases				
	Herds	Animals	Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Number of herds tested	Number of animals tested	Number of infected herds	Number of animals tested with serological blood tests	Number of animals positive serologically	Number of animals examined microbiologically	Number of animals positive microbiologically	Number of suspended herds
Austria	51095	444685	51094	99.998	1	0.002	1580	13560	1	16	2	2	0	1
Total	51095	444685	51094	99.998	1	0.002	1580	13560	1	16	2	2	0	1

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services, Provincial Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Please give details.

4.7. Yersiniosis

4.7.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Yersiniosis is not considered a major food borne illness in Austria. The incidence of human disease is low when compared to salmonellosis or campylobacteriosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2008, a total of 116 human infections were reported as aggregated notified cases on a monthly basis. 104 primary isolates from patients were sent to the National Reference Laboratory for Yersinia. The sources of infections are unclear. Neither studies on sporadic cases nor scientific outbreak investigations were performed in Austria so far.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

Nil

4.7.2. Yersiniosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

Notification of cases according to EU case definitions. The numbers presented in this report reflect the number of primary isolates sent to the national reference lab for confirmation and typing.

Case definition

Clinical description: An illness of variable severity characterised by diarrhoea, fever, nausea, cramps and tenesmus.

Laboratory criteria for diagnosis: Isolation of *Yersinia enterocolitica* Serogroup O:3, O:9 or O:5 or *Y. pseudotuberculosis* from a clinical specimen.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Faecal (*Yersinia enterocolitica*) or resection (*Y. pseudotuberculosis*) sample material is plated directly on cefsulodin-irgasan-novobiocin (CIN) agar and incubated for 18 hours at 30 °C. Suspicious colonies are identified in an Api 20 E reaction and API 50 CHE reaction. *Y. enterocolitica* is agglutinated with sera against serogroups O:3, O:5, O:9 and O:8. Biovar and pathogenicity are defined.

Notification system in place

Medical doctors specialised in Laboratory Diagnosis or Microbiology and Hygiene and the attended physicians are required to report the disease. Notification of yersiniosis according to the epidemic act has been mandatory since 1950 (BGBl. 1950/186 Epidemiegesetz, as amended).

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Nil

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of human cases has been similar in the last years.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Compared to salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis, yersiniosis is not an important food borne pathogen.

Data source of Tables 71 to 73: Primary isolates from patients typed in the national reference centre for yersiniosis

Table 71 Yersiniosis in man - species/serotype distribution

	Cases	Incidence/ 100.000	Autochtone cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
Yersiniosis	104	1,2	not available	not available	104
<i>Y. enterocolitica</i>	104	1,2			104
<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:3	90	1,1			90
<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:5	1	0,0			1
<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:9	13	0,2			13

Table 72 Yersiniosis in humans - age distribution

Age group	Yersiniosis			<i>Y. enterocolitica</i>			<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:3			<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:5			<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:9		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	29	14	15	29	14	15	27	12	15	0	0	0	2	2	0
5 to 14 years	26	21	5	26	21	5	23	20	3	0	0	0	3	1	2
15 to 24 years	6	3	3	6	3	3	6	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	19	9	10	19	9	10	14	7	7	0	0	0	5	2	3
45 to 64 years	17	10	7	17	10	7	14	8	6	0	0	0	3	2	1
65 years and older	6	5	1	6	5	1	5	4	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
Age unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
All age groups	104	63	41	104	63	41	90	55	35	1	1	0	13	7	6

Table 73 Yersiniosis in humans - seasonal distribution

Month	Yersiniosis	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i>	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:3	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:5	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:9
	Cases	Cases	Cases	Cases	Cases
January	13	13	9	1	3
February	5	5	5	0	0
March	4	4	3	0	1
April	8	8	8	0	0
May	11	11	11	0	0
June	6	6	5	0	1
July	9	9	8	0	1
August	6	6	6	0	0
September	11	11	10	0	1
October	11	11	10	0	1
November	10	10	8	0	2
December	10	10	7	0	3
not known	0	0	0	0	0
Total	104	104	90	1	13

4.7.3. Yersinia in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2008 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2008“ (BMGFJ-75500/0247-IV/B/7/2007 von 08.01.2008) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2007-2010) according to Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2008, approximately 40,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 60% (24,000) of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-dept information. In 2008, eight relevant food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria (Schwerpunktprogramm 2008 BMGFJ-75500/0242-IV/B/7/2007). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Results of the investigation

see tables

Campaign A-801-08: *Y. enterocolitica* in food - Meat from pig - meat products - fermented sausages - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: March - April

Type of specimen taken

fermented sausages and pate

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Y. enterocolitica* in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

Out of 62 samples tested, 1 positive non-pathogenic strain was found (Biotype 1A, Serotype O:5)

Table 74 Yersiniosis in food

Categories	Sampling stage	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> , Biotype 1A non-pathogenic
Meat from pig - meat products - fermented sausages (Campaign A-801-08)	at retail	single	25g	62	1	1

4.7.4. *Yersinia* spp. in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not relevant in Austria therefore no testing.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination.

Other preventative measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

EU wide harmonized monitoring program.

Notification system in place:

Findings of Yersinia are not notifiable in animals.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No changes in recent years.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance has not been investigated.

Additional information

Nil

4.8. Trichinellosis

4.8.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

No documented human infections in 2008.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No documented human infections in 2008.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

No documented infections in food-animals in 2008.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No new measures implemented

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Reconsider the necessity of routine trichinella meat inspection in pig carcasses

Additional information

Nil

4.8.2. Trichinellosis in humans

Description of the positive cases detected during the reporting year

No cases identified in 2008.

Case definition

Clinical description: A disease caused by ingestion of *Trichinella* larvae. The disease has variable clinical manifestations. Common signs and symptoms include eosinophilia, fever, myalgia, and periorbital edema. Laboratory criteria for diagnosis: Demonstration of *Trichinella* larvae in tissue obtained by muscle biopsy, or positive serologic test for *Trichinella*

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

ELISA and Westernblot

Notification system in place

Notification of trichinellosis according to the epidemic act since 1950 (BGBI. 1950/186 Epidemiegesetz, as amended).

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The last autochthonous cases have been reported in 1970

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance as zoonotic disease

No relevance in Austria

Data source of Table 75: national reference laboratory for toxoplasmosis, echinococcosis, toxocarosis and other parasitic diseases

Table 75 Trichinellosis in man - species/serotype distribution

	Cases	Incidence per 100.000
Trichinellosis	0	0

4.8.3. Trichinella in animals

A. *Trichinella* spp. in pigs

Number of officially recognised *Trichinella*-free holdings

Categories of holdings officially recognised *Trichinella*-free

Officially recognised regions with negligible *Trichinella* risk

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

General

Targeted sampling of all slaughtered pigs except pigs slaughtered by the farmer for his own consumption; the sampling is performed by competent authorities; the samples are taken at slaughterhouses; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme.

Frequency of the sampling

General

Other: Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered pig

Type of specimen taken

General

Muscles: Diaphragm (crus), tongue, masseter and abdominal muscles.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

General

Appropriate muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition

General

When trichinosis is detected with one of the given methods

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005

Vaccination policy

Nil

Preventive measures in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Summary results of the inspections of Trichinella-free holdings including information on farmer compliance

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004, as amended.

The contingency plan in place

Notification system in place

Results of the investigation including description of the positive cases and the verification of the Trichinella species

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

Nil

B. Trichinella spp. in horses

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Targeted sampling of all slaughtered horses; the sampling is performed by competent authorities; the samples are taken at slaughterhouses; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme

Frequency of the sampling

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered horse

Type of specimen taken

Muscles from tongue, masseter, diaphragm and neck.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Appropriate muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition

When trichinosis is detected with one of the given methods.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

Results of the investigation

No findings in horses.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

Nil

C. Trichinella spp. in animal - Wildlife - wild boars

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Sampling of all hunted or harvested wild boars; the sampling is performed by hunters with special knowledge about trichinella investigation or by competent authorities; the sampling is stratified by geographical regions depending to the habitats of wild boar in Austria; samples are taken either

immediately after shooting the animal or at the cold storage depots; the sampling is part of a monitoring scheme.

Frequency of the sampling

All farmed wild boars are controlled for trichinella.

Type of specimen taken

Diaphragm muscles (crus), tongue, masseter and abdominal muscles.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Appropriate muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition

When trichinosis is detected with one of the given methods.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

Nil

Table 76 *Trichinella* spp. in animals

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Trichinella</i> spp.
Pigs							
fattening pigs raised under controlled housing conditions in integrated system							
fattening pigs not raised under controlled housing conditions in integrated system	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling			animal	5 491 872	0
breeding animals -unspecified - sows and boars							
Domestic solipeds							
horses	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling			animal	903	0
Wild boars							
farmed	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling			animal	546	0
wild							
Foxes							
Bears							
Rodents							
Rats							

CVS: Central Veterinary Services

4.9. Echinococcosis

4.9.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Austria is a low risk country for both forms of echinococcosis

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

We expect the future prevalence to be low. In 2008, 2 cases of *Echinococcus multilocularis* infestation were diagnosed in Austria, one autochtone case confirmed; in 2008 there were 7 patients with cystic echinococcosis.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Alveolar echinococcosis: Due to the infection rates of red foxes in Austria (0-40 %) there is a relatively elevated risk for hunters, cat owners and farmers.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Tools for preventive serological screening of hunters (and also other persons) have been established to detect *Echinococcus multilocularis* infections in an early stage. The early detection of the infection is the prerequisite for a successful curative treatment.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

Nil

4.9.2. Echinococcosis in humans

Case definition

Clinical apparent case (differentiation between alveolar and cystic echinococcosis necessary) with laboratory diagnostic confirmation: = histopathology or combination of imaging (ultrasound, X-ray, computed tomography or others) and positive serology or combination of specific DNA (by PCR) and positive serology).

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

ELISA and Westernblot technique, participant of the UK National External Quality Assessment Service for Microbiology, National Reference Laboratory for Echinococcosis.

Notification system in place

Echinococcosis is a notifiable disease since June 2004 according to the National Regulation 254/2004 (BGBl. II, 254/2004 of 18 June in 2004, Anzeigepflichtige übertragbare Krankheiten 2004)

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

- Alveolar echinococcosis has been known in Austria since 1897; annual incidence (1897- 2004): 0-6 cases, mean incidence: 2.4 cases/year (only autochthonous cases); geographic distribution in Austria: mainly in the western provinces (Vorarlberg, Tyrol, Salzburg), but cases have been reported in every province; outbreaks are not known.

- Cystic echinococcosis has been known in Austria at least since 1819; Cases of cystic echinococcosis have been registered in the Clinical Institute of Hygiene and Medical Microbiology (Medical University Vienna) regularly since the beginning of the 1980ies. Annual incidence (1984 - 2006): 20 - 60 cases; mean incidence: 31 cases per year, one third of patients are of Austrian origin; two thirds are from abroad. Geographic distribution in Austria is unknown; a few autochthonous infections could be observed mainly in the eastern and southern provinces (Lower Austria, Burgenland, Styria); outbreaks are not known.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

- Alveolar echinococcosis: We expect the future prevalence to be low; sources of infection: fox faeces (contaminated hands and fingers, vegetables, water).
- Cystic echinococcosis: We expect the future prevalence to be low; sources of infection: dog faeces, presumably in a very few foci (in or around farmers houses)

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Low prevalence of both forms of echinococcosis

Data source of Tables 77 and 78: national reference laboratory for toxoplasmosis, echinococcosis, toxocarosis and other parasitic diseases

Table 77 Echinococcosis in humans - species/serotype distribution

	Cases	Incidence/ 100,000	Autochtone cases	Imported cases
Echinococcosis	9	0,11		
Cystic echinococcosis	7	0,08	unknown	unknown
Alveolar echinococcosis	2	0,02	1	unknown

Table 78 Echinococcosis in humans - age distribution

Age group	<i>Echinococcus</i>			<i>E. granulosus</i>			<i>E. multilocularis</i>		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	2	1	1	2	1	1	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	4	3	1	4	3	1	0	0	0
45 to 64 years	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
65 years and older	2	1	1	0	0	0	2	1	1
Age unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
All age groups	9	6	3	7	5	2	2	1	1

4.9.3. Echinococcus in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Targeted sampling of all in abattoirs slaughtered animals; the sampling is performed by competent authorities in course of the post-mortem meat inspection; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme

Frequency of the sampling

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered animal

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

All organs and muscles that were used for human consumption

Case definition

Each carcass in which cystic or alveolar hydatids are detected in muscles or organs

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Other: All organs and muscles that were used for human consumption were visually inspected, palpated and cuttings were performed

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Post mortem meat inspection act according to BGBl. 1982/522, Fleischuntersuchungsgesetz, as amended

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Notification system in place

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Cystic or alveolar echinococcosis in animals that are used for food production do not play a role for the infection of humans; it is primarily a hygienic problem. Only when infected waste from animals is used as feed for carnivores the risk of infection for humans increases.

Additional information

Nil

Table 79 Echinococcus sp. in animals

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for Echinococcus spp.	<i>E. multilocularis</i>	<i>E. granulosus</i>	<i>Echinococcus</i> spp., unspecified
Cattle	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	610 304	297			297
Sheep	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	116 753	177			177
Goats	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	3 527	0			0
Pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	5 491 872	30			30

x ... Central Veterinary Services, Provincial Veterinary Services

4.10. Toxoplasmosis

4.10.1. General evaluation of the national situation

No data available

4.10.2. Toxoplasma in humans

Not notifiable in Austria, therefore no data available

4.10.3. Toxoplasma in animals

Zoonotic agent/zoonoses: *Toxoplasma gondii*

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

There is no official surveillance for *Toxoplasma* spp. in animals. Sampling of cattle, sheep, goats or pigs is performed depending on clinical suspicion of toxoplasmosis and in cases after abortion. Other species of animals are also occasionally sampled.

Frequency of the sampling

In case of clinical suspicion and abortion.

Type of specimen taken

Blood

Case definition

A case is defined as an animal that tests positive ($\geq 1:40$). The animal is the epidemiological unit.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The diagnostic methods used for serology is the microagglutination test.

Vaccination policy:

No vaccination

Other preventative measures than vaccination in place:

Control programme/ mechanisms:

The control programmes/ strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases:

Notification system in place:

Toxoplasmosis is not notifiable in animals.

Results of the investigation

No valid data available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection:

Nil

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection):**Additional information**

Nil

Table 80 Toxoplasmosis in animals

Animal species	sampling stage	sampling context	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for Toxoplasma gondii
Cattle	at farm - animal sample - blood	clinical investigations		animal	13	0
Sheep	at farm - animal sample - blood	clinical investigations		animal	20	4
Goats	at farm - animal sample - blood	clinical investigations		animal	19	8
Pigs	at farm - animal sample - blood	clinical investigations		animal	25	1

4.11. Rabies

4.11.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Rabies in humans was a major public health issue in the 1960s.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2008, there was no case of rabies detected in animals in Austria.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

In 2008, vaccination programmes were carried out in fox populations in areas of higher risk. Additionally, a brochure was published by AGES and BMG: Recommendations for prophylaxis in humans (http://www.ages.at/uploads/media/Tollwut_01.pdf).

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

Nil

4.11.2. Rabies in humans

Case definition

Laboratory criteria for diagnosis

Detection by direct fluorescent antibody of viral antigens in a clinical specimen (preferably the brain or the nerves surrounding hair follicles in the nape of the neck)

Detection of rabies nucleic acid in clinical specimen

Isolation (in cell culture or in a laboratory animal) of rabies virus from saliva, cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), or central nervous system tissue

Identification of a rabies-neutralising antibody titre (complete neutralization) in the serum or CSF of an unvaccinated person.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Liquor, smears from pharynx, swab from conjunctivae biopsy at the nape of the neck and serum were examined in the fluorescent antibody test (FAT), immunohistochemistry and RT-PCR (Ito M., Itou T., Sakai T., et al. (2001). Detection of Rabies Virus RNA isolated from several species of animals in Brazil by RT-PCR. Journal of Veterinary medicine Science 63(12): 1309-1313.).

Notification system in place

Rabies and bite of an infected animal or an animal suspected to be infected according to the epidemic act (BGBl. 1950/186 Epidemiegesetz, as amended).

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Nil

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Nil

Data source of Table 81: national reference laboratory for rabies

Table 81 Rabies in humans

	Cases	Incidence/1 00,000	Autochtone cases	Imported cases
Rabies	0	0	0	0
Human expose	0	0	0	0

4.11.3. Lyssavirus (rabies) in animals

A. Rabies virus in animal - Wildlife - foxes

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

According to (GZ:39.642/14-VII/B/03): 8 foxes per 100km² in rabies infested and rabies endangered areas, 4 foxes per 100km² in not endangered and free areas (definition of areas: GZ 30.517/35-IV/12/03).

Frequency of the sampling

8 foxes per 100 km² in rabies infested and rabies endangered areas, 4 foxes per 100km² in not endangered and free areas.

Type of specimen taken

Other: Brain (brain stem or hippocampus)

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Whole animals or heads of the dead animals are sent to the laboratories; sometimes brain tissue (derived from other laboratories). Brain tissue (e.g. 1 cm²) is examined.

Case definition

An animal is considered positive if the fluorescent antibody test (FAT) shows a positive signal.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The routine test was the fluorescent antibody test (FAT).

RTCIT (rabies tissue culture infection test) was performed on mouse neuroblastoma cells.

MIT (mouse inoculation test) will be only performed on demand, not for routine confirmation

Vaccination policy

Oral vaccination of foxes twice a year according to GZ: 30.517/52-IV/12/03

2008; additionally emergency vaccination in Carinthia according GZ. 74.10070105-IV/B572008.

Figure 1 Vaccination areas in Austria, spring 2008

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Fuchs-Tollwutbekämpfungsverordnung BGBl II 2001/75, Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42, Tierseuchengesetz-Durchführungsverordnung 1909/178 as amended: BGBl 1955/76 TSG-DVO zum IV. Abschnitt Wutkrankheiten

Control of vaccination: Detection of tetracycline in jaw bones of randomly chosen foxes from the vaccination area; additionally an ELISA is performed to proof seroconversion.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

In 2008, vaccination programmes were carried out (due to rabies in a fox in 2006).

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Probably the reduction of the number of the animals (foxes) for investigation

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42, and vaccination of the Fox Population

Notification system in place

According to Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Austria is declared as rabies free since 28.9.08. Note the additional emergency vaccination in Carinthia according GZ. 74.10070105-IV/B572008

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

B. Rabies virus in animal - all animals except foxes

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Sampling is targeted when animals are observed with central nervous symptoms or after biting a person. The suspicious animal is killed or euthanized and the carcass or head is sent to the laboratory.

Frequency of the sampling

If a case is suspected

Type of specimen taken

Other: Brain (hippocampus and brain stem)

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Routinely a sample will be taken from one site of the brain: a part from the hippocampus, brain stem or cerebellum. If an animal has bitten a person then 2 parts from the brain will be taken: hippocampus and brain stem.

Case definition

An animal is considered positive if the fluorescent antibody tests (FAT) or the rabies tissue culture infection test or the mouse inoculation test show a positive result.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The routine test was the fluorescent antibody test (FAT).

RTCIT (rabies tissue culture infection test) was performed on mouse neuroblastoma cells.

MIT(mouse inoculation test) will be only performed on demand, not for routine confirmation

Vaccination policy

Voluntary vaccination of pets.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RgBl 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42;

Tierseuchengesetz-Durchführungsverordnung 1909/178 as amended: BGBl 1955/76

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RgBl 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42. If a rabies suspicious pet bites a person, the person is treated.

Notification system in place

According to Tierseuchengesetz TSG RgBl 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

On 28th of September 2008, Austria has been declared free of rabies.

Vaccination areas, rabies endangered and rabies free areas were redefined.

Table 82 Rabies in animals

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling unit	Units tested	
				Units tested	Total units positive for Lyssa virus (rabies)
Cattle	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	animal	6	0
Sheep	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	animal	2	0
Goats	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	animal	57	0
Domestic solipeds	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	animal	2	0
Dogs	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	animal	57	0
stray dogs					
Cats	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	animal	80	0
stray cats					
other animals	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	clinical investigation	animal	4	0
Wildlife					
Bats	found dead	monitoring - official sampling - selective sampling	animal	68	0
Foxes- wild	from hunting	selective sampling - official sampling - Control and eradication programmes	animal	8,244	0
Badgers - wild	from hunting	selective sampling - official sampling - Control and eradication programmes	animal	81	0
Martens - wild	from hunting	selective sampling - official sampling - Control and eradication programmes	animal	866	0

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for Lyssa virus (rabies)
Wild boars - wild	from hunting	clinical investigation	animal	1	0
roe deer - wild	from hunting	clinical investigation	animal	18	0
Other farm, wild or pet animals (please add the relevant species)					
other mustelidae	from hunting	selective sampling - official sampling - Control and eradication programmes	animal	19	0
other animals (wildlife)	from hunting	selective sampling - official sampling - Control and eradication programmes	animal	29	0

4.12. Q-Fever

4.12.1. General evaluation of the situation

No data available

4.12.2. Q-fever in humans

Not notifiable in Austria, therefore no data available

4.12.3. *Coxiella burnetii* in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

There is no official surveillance for *Coxiella burnetii* in animals. Sampling of cattle, sheep or goats is performed in case of clinical suspicion of Q-fever and after abortion.

Frequency of the sampling

In case of clinical suspicion and abortion.

Type of specimen taken

Blood

Case definition

A case is defined as an animal showing a titre $\geq 1:20$ or a positive PCR reaction. The animal is the epidemiological unit.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The diagnostic method is the complement fixation reaction, detecting phase 1 and phase 2 antigen. Organs and swabs are tested by real time PCR.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination.

Other preventative measures than vaccination in place:

Nil

Control programme/ mechanisms

The control programmes/ strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Notification system in place

Q-fever in animals is not a notifiable disease

Results of the investigation

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Q-fever in humans is not a notifiable disease.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Additional information

Table 83 Q-fever in animals

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Coxiella burnetii</i>
Cattle	clinical investigations	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	Coxiella burnetii		animal	3	1
Cattle	clinical investigations	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	Coxiella burnetii		animal	2	1
Cattle	clinical investigations	at farm - animal sample - blood	Coxiella burnetii Ak		animal	1142	11
Sheep	clinical investigations	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	Coxiella burnetii		animal	2	0
Sheep	clinical investigations	at farm - animal sample - blood	Coxiella burnetii Ak		animal	25	0
Goats	clinical investigations	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	Coxiella burnetii		animal	3	0
Goats	clinical investigations	at farm - animal sample - blood	Coxiella burnetii Ak		animal	106	11

VET: all AGES Institute for Veterinary Disease Control

5. Information on Specific Indicators of Antimicrobial Resistance

5.1. E. coli Indicators

5.1.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Resistance monitoring of faeces isolates from slaughtered animals was started in Austria in 2004 and continued in 2008.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of antimicrobial resistance of E. coli in broiler slaughter batches, bovine animals and pigs was implemented according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 17 November 2003 in the National Order GZ: BMGF-74600/0092-IV/B/8/2005 (Überwachungsprogramme 2005 zu ausgewählten Zoonosen und Antibiotikaresistenzen). The sampling was carried out from January to December 2008 in slaughterhouses.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Europe wide harmonized standards for antimicrobial resistance monitoring would be highly welcome.

Additional information

Nil

5.1.2. Antimicrobial resistance in Escherichia coli isolates

A. Antimicrobial resistance of E. coli in animal - All animals - farmed - at slaughterhouse - Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

A sampling plan was created according to the federal surveillance program „Überwachung ausgewählter Zoonosen und Antibiotikaresistenzen 2008 (GZ BMGFJ GZ 74600/0355-IV/B/5/2007)“ and the baseline survey on the prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of Campylobacter spp. in broiler flocks and on the prevalence of Campylobacter spp. and Salmonella spp. in broiler carcasses (CD 2007/516/EC). The sampling plan for E. coli includes cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches.

Type of specimen taken

E. coli is isolated from the caecum of slaughtered cattle, pigs and broiler. 170 E. coli strains are tested for their antimicrobial susceptibility. The caecum from one cow or pig or the whole intestines from ten slaughtered broilers within a single slaughter batch at each slaughterhouse are collected.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The intestines were refrigerated to 4 °C and samples were sent to the Institute of Veterinary Disease Control (IVET) in Graz, where each pathogen was isolated and further characterized. The Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz performed the antimicrobial susceptibility testing for all strains.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

The number of samples was calculated by experts of the Division for Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment of the AGES based on the expected prevalence of E. coli among the different animal species (cattle, pigs, broiler flocks). All isolated strains of E. coli were sent to the IMED Graz for antimicrobial susceptibility testing.

Methods used for collecting data

All information concerning the tested animals and the sampled slaughterhouses were recorded in a questionnaire. In the laboratory, the data were entered into a database and later analysed in Microsoft® Excel tables.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The intestinal contents are streaked onto the MacConkey- Agar plates (Merck Nr. 1.05465) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. The process is repeated for colonies which are suspected for E. coli. These colonies are streaked onto a blood-agar (Oxoid Nr. CM0055, 5% Sheep blood) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. The confirmation of the identification of E. coli is done with an oxidase- (Merck Nr. 1.13300.0001) and spot indol test (Firma Biomedica, Nr. 1069).

Laboratory used for detection for resistance**Antimicrobials included in monitoring**

E. coli samples isolated from cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches are tested for antimicrobial susceptibility against gentamicin, kanamycin, streptomycin, ceftotaxim, sulfamethoxazol, trimethoprim, ciprofloxacin, nalidixin acid, ampicillin, chloramphenicol and tetracycline.

Breakpoints used in testing

See respective tables

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms**The control program/strategies in place**

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

None

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None

Notification system in place

None

Results of the investigation

See respective tables. National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection is not available yet; a census on the use of antimicrobials in veterinary medicine is planned.

Additional information

None

Table 84 Breakpoints used for antibiotic resistance testing of E. coli in animals

Test method used		Number of reporting laboratory	
Disc diffusion			1
E-test			
Agar dilution			
Broth dilution	x		

Standards used for testing		The methods are used for investigation of isolate	
CLSI	x	Feedingstuff	
other		Animals	x
		Food	
		Humans	

<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Dilution method				
		Breakpoint concentration (µg/ml)			Range tested	
		Susceptible ≤	Intermediate	Resistant >	lowest	highest
Aminoglykosid AB						
Gentamicin	EUCAST			> 2	0,25	32
Kanamycin	EUCAST			> 8	0,25	32
Streptomycin	EUCAST			> 16	2	256
Cephalosporine						
Cefotaxim	EUCAST			> 0,25	0,06	128
Folsäureinhibitoren						
Sulfamethoxazol	EUCAST			> 256	8	1024
Trimethoprim	EUCAST			> 2	0,25	16
Quinolone and Quinoxalin						
Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST			> 0,03	0,008	8
Nalidixinsäure	EUCAST			> 16	2	256
Penicilline						
Ampicillin	EUCAST			> 8	0,5	64
Phenicol						
Chloramphenicol	EUCAST			> 16	2	256
Tetracycline						
Tetracyclin	EUCAST			> 8	0,5	64

Table 85 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in animals (qualitative tables)

<i>E.coli</i>	Gallus gallus		Cattle		Pigs	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes		yes		yes	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	170		170		170	
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n
Aminoglykosid AB						
Gentamicin	2,9	5	0,0	0	0,6	1
Kanamycin	5,3	9	0,0	0	3,5	6
Streptomycin	31,2	53	4,1	7	55,3	94
Cephalosporine						
Cefotaxim	2,9	5	0,0	0	0,6	1
Folsäureinhibitoren						
Sulfamethoxazol	27,6	47	4,1	7	30,0	51
Trimethoprim	14,7	25	0,6	1	15,3	26
Quinolone and Quinoxalin						
Ciprofloxacin	68,8	117	2,9	5	0,6	1
Nalidixinsäure	68,2	116	1,2	2	0,6	1
Penicilline						
Ampicillin	24,1	41	2,4	4	14,1	24
Phenicole						
Chloramphenicol	5,3	9	0,0	0	5,9	10
Tetracycline						
Tetracyclin	26,5	45	6,5	11	64,1	109
Number of multiresistant isolates						
fully sensitive	17,1	29	89,4	152	24,1	41
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	28,8	49	5,3	9	21,8	37
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	25,9	44	2,4	4	26,5	45
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	10,6	18	2,9	5	8,8	15
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	7,1	12	0,0	0	9,4	16
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	10,6	18	0,0	0	9,4	16

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For E. coli this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, Nalidixic acid, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazol

Table 86 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in Cattle (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method]

		<i>E. coli</i> CATTLE																					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	170	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
Antimicrobials:	%R	n	= < 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
			n																				
Aminoglykosid AB																							
Gentamicin	0,0	0						69	88	13													
Kanamycin	0,0	0								9	100	58	3										
Streptomycin	4,1	7									41	103	18	1	4	2	1						
Cephalosporine																							
Cefotaxim	0,0	0				159	10	1															
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
Sulfamethoxazol	4,1	7												48	70	39	5	1					7
Trimethoprim	0,6	1						76	72	20	1					1							
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
Ciprofloxacin	2,9	5	40	117	8	3	1	1															
Nalidixinsäure	1,2	2									143	23	2			1	1						
Penicilline																							
Ampicillin	2,4	4								9	77	77	3				4						
Phenicole																							
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0									4	70	89	7									
Tetracycline																							
Tetracyclin	6,5	11								50	101	7	1		1	2	8						

Table 87 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in broiler - at slaughter - monitoring programme – active monitoring (slaughter batch) - quantitative data [Dilution method]

		<i>E. coli</i>																			
		GALLUS GALLUS																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	170	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:		= < 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	%R	n	n																		
Aminoglykosid AB																					
Gentamicin	2,9	5				62	94	9				1	1	2	1						
Kanamycin	5,3	9						3	100	55	3				9						
Streptomycin	31,2	53							23	62	16	16	24	12	8	7	2				
Cephalosporine																					
Cefotaxim	2,9	5			145	19	1		1	2		2									
Folsäureinhibitoren																					
Sulfamethoxazol	27,6	47										40	62	19	2						47
Trimethoprim	14,7	25				62	68	15						25							
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																					
Ciprofloxacin	68,8	117	13	38	2	2	12	61	14	12	1	2	10	3							
Nalidixinsäure	68,2	116								45	8		1	2	28	37	13	36			
Penicilline																					
Ampicillin	24,1	41							7	70	46	6				41					
Phenicole																					
Chloramphenicol	5,3	9								1	54	92	14			3	5	1			
Tetracycline																					
Tetracyclin	26,5	45					4	30	86	5					13	32					

Table 88 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in Pigs - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method]

		<i>E.coli</i>																						
		PIGS																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																							
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	170	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																						
Antimicrobials:	%R	n	= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	> 2048		
			n																					
Aminoglykosid AB																								
Gentamicin	0,6	1					57	100	10	2						1								
Kanamycin	3,5	6							7	79	73	5				6								
Streptomycin	55,3	94								13	46	10	7	21	43	14	13	3						
Cephalosporine																								
Cefotaxim	0,6	1			165	4									1									
Folsäureinhibitoren																								
Sulfamethoxazol	30,0	51											40	54	21	2	2					51		
Trimethoprim	15,3	26					66	66	12						26									
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																								
Ciprofloxacin	0,6	1	39	126	4		1																	
Nalidixinsäure	0,6	1									143	24	2				1							
Penicilline																								
Ampicillin	14,1	24						1	8	70	66	1				24								
Phenicole																								
Chloramphenicol	5,9	10								7	60	90	3	5		2	3							
Tetracycline																								
Tetracyclin	64,1	109							20	40	1				2	40	67							

5.2. Enterococcus Indicators

5.2.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Resistance monitoring of faeces isolates from slaughtered animals was started in Austria in 2004 and continued in 2008.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of antimicrobial resistance of enterococci in broiler slaughter batches, bovine animals and pigs was implemented according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 17 November 2003 in the National Order GZ: BMGF-74600/0092-IV/B/8/2005 (Überwachungsprogramme 2005 zu ausgewählten Zoonosen und Antibiotikaresistenzen). The sampling was carried out from January to December 2008 in slaughterhouses.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Europe wide harmonized standards for antimicrobial resistance monitoring would be highly welcome.

Additional information

Nil

5.2.2. Antimicrobial resistance in Enterococcus spp. isolates

A. Antimicrobial resistance of Enterococcus spp. in animal - All animals - farmed - at slaughterhouse - Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

A sampling plan was created according to the federal surveillance program „Überwachung ausgewählter Zoonosen und Antibiotikaresistenzen 2008 (GZ BMGFJ GZ 74600/0355-IV/B/5/2007)“ and the baseline survey on the prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of Campylobacter spp. in broiler flocks and on the prevalence of Campylobacter spp. and Salmonella spp. in broiler carcasses (CD 2007/516/EC). The sampling plan for enterococci includes cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches.

Type of specimen taken

Enterococci are isolated from the caecum of slaughtered cattle, pigs and broiler. 170 E. faecalis or E. faecium strains are tested for their antimicrobial susceptibility. The caecum from one cow or pig or the whole intestines from ten slaughtered broilers within a single slaughter batch at each slaughterhouse are collected.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The intestines were refrigerated to 4 °C and samples were sent to the Institute of Veterinary Disease Control (IVET) in Graz, where each pathogen was isolated and further characterized. The Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz performed the antimicrobial susceptibility testing for all strains.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

The number of samples was calculated by experts of the Division for Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment of the AGES based on the expected prevalence of *Enterococcus faecalis* and *E. faecium* in the different animal species (cattle, pigs, broiler flocks). From each sample up to five enterococci were differentiated. Only *E. faecalis* and *E. faecium* strains were sent to the IMED Graz for antimicrobial susceptibility testing.

Methods used for collecting data

All information concerning the tested animals and the sampled slaughterhouses were recorded in a questionnaire. In the laboratory, the data were entered into a database and later analysed in Microsoft® Excel tables.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The samples are injected into the Citrate Azide Tween Carbonate Agar (CATC-AGAR, Merck Art.Nr. 1.10279) and incubated at 37 °C ± 1°C for 24 h. Then, the medium is left at room temperature for another 24 hrs. Potential colonies are subcultivated on blood agar (Oxoid Nr. CM0055, 5% Sheep blood) for 24 h at 37 ±1 °C which results in the differentiation of *E. faecalis* and *E. faecium* through Gram's method, Catalase Test, Arabinose- and Pyruvate-breakdown.

Laboratory used for detection for resistance

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

Enterococcus spp. samples isolated from cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches are tested for antimicrobial resistance against gentamicin, streptomycin, vancomycin, ciprofloxacin, erythromycin, nitrofurantoin, avilamycin, ampicillin, chloramphenicol, bacitracin, synergid and tetracycline.

Breakpoints used in testing

See respective tables

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

None

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None

Notification system in place

None

Results of the investigation

See respective tables. National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection is not available yet; a census on the use of antimicrobials in veterinary medicine is planned.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not yet available

Additional information

None

Table 89 Breakpoints used for antibiotic resistance testing of *Enterococcus faecalis* in animals

<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i> - Antimicrobial susceptibility - Breakpoints		Number of reporting laboratory	1
Test method used			
Disc diffusion			
E-test			
Agar dilution			
Broth dilution	x		
Standards used for testing		The methods are used for investigation of isolates from	
CLSI		Feedingstuff	
other	EUCAST	Animals	x
		Food	x
		Humans	x

<i>E. faecalis</i>	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Dilution method				
		Breakpoint concentration (µg/ml)			Range tested	
		Susceptible ≤	Intermediate	Resistant >	lowest	highest
Aminoglykosid AB						
Gentamicin	EUCAST			> 32	4	2048
Streptomycin	EUCAST			> 512	16	2048
Glycopeptide						
Vancomycin	EUCAST			> 4	1	64
Quinolone and Quinoxalin						
Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST			> 4	0,25	32
Makrolide						
Erythromycin	EUCAST			> 4	0,5	64
Nitrofurane						
Nitrofurantoin	EUCAST			> 64	8	512
Orthosomycine						
Avilamycin	EUCAST			> 8	1	128
Penicilline						
Ampicillin	EUCAST			> 4	0,25	32
Phenicole						
Chloramphenicol	EUCAST			> 32	4	256
Polypeptide						
Bacitracin	EUCAST			> 64	8	256
Streptogramine						
Synercid	EUCAST			> 32	0,5	128
Tetracycline						
Tetracyclin	EUCAST			> 2	0,5	64

Table 90 Breakpoints used for antibiotic resistance testing of *Enterococcus faecium* in animals

<i>Enterococcus faecium</i> - Antimicrobial susceptibility - Breakpoints			
Test method used		Number of reporting laboratory	
Disc diffusion			1
E-test			
Agar dilution			
Broth dilution	x		
Standards used for testing		The methods are used for investigation of isolates from	
CLSI		Feedingstuff	
other	EUCAST	Animals	x
		Food	x
		Humans	x

<i>E. faecium</i>	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Dilution method				
		Breakpoint concentration (µg/ml)			Range tested	
		Susceptible ≤	Intermediate	Resistant >	lowest	highest
Aminoglykosid AB						
Gentamicin	EUCAST			> 32	4	2048
Streptomycin	EUCAST			> 128	16	2048
Glycopeptide						
Vancomycin	EUCAST			> 4	1	64
Quinolone and Quinoxalin						
Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST			> 4	0,25	32
Makrolide						
Erythromycin	EUCAST			> 4	0,5	64
Nitrofurane						
Nitrofurantoin	EUCAST			> 256	8	512
Orthosomycine						
Avilamycin	EUCAST			> 16	1	128
Penicilline						
Ampicillin	EUCAST			> 4	0,25	32
Phenicole						
Chloramphenicol	EUCAST			> 32	4	256
Polypeptide						
Bacitracin	EUCAST			> 64	8	256
Streptogramine						
Synercid	EUCAST			> 1	0,5	128
Tetracycline						
Tetracyclin	EUCAST			> 2	0,5	64

Table 91 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in animals (qualitative tables)

<i>E. faecalis</i>	Gallus Gallus	Cattle	Pigs			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes	yes	yes			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	90	49	39			
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n
Aminoglykosid AB						
Gentamicin	1,1	1	0,0	0	0,0	0
Streptomycin	21,1	19	0,0	0	10,3	4
Glycopeptide						
Vancomycin	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Quinolone and Quinoxalin						
Ciprofloxacin	2,2	2	0,0	0	2,6	1
Makrolide						
Erythromycin	57,8	52	4,1	2	12,8	5
Nitrofurane						
Nitrofurantoin	0,0	0	0,0	1	0,0	0
Orthosomycine						
Avilamycin	3,3	3	0,0	0	2,6	1
Penicilline						
Ampicillin	0,0	0	2,0	1	0,0	0
Phenicole						
Chloramphenicol	2,2	2	0,0	0	2,6	1
Polypeptide						
Bacitracin	45,6	41	10,2	5	23,1	9
Streptogramine						
Synercid	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Tetracycline						
Tetracyclin	73,3	66	12,2	6	64,1	25
Number of multiresistant isolates						
fully sensitive	14,4	13	87,8	43	30,8	12
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	38,9	35	6,1	3	56,4	22
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	25,6	23	6,1	3	7,7	3
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	18,9	17	0,0	0	2,6	1
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	2,2	2	0,0	0	2,6	1
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For enterococci this includes resistance to streptomycin, gentamicin, chloramphenicol, ampicillin, vancomycin, erythromycin, synercid, tetracycline

Table 92 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in Cattle (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method]

		<i>E. faecalis</i>																		
		CATTLE																		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	49	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																		
Antimicrobials:	%R	n	<=0.06	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
			n																	
Aminoglykosid AB																				
Gentamicin	0,0	0								11	25	13								
Streptomycin	0,0	0										5	11	29	4					
Glycopeptide																				
Vancomycin	0,0	0						41	8											
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																				
Ciprofloxacin	0,0	0				14	15	19	1											
Makrolide																				
Erythromycin	4,1	2				30	9	8			2									
Nitrofurane																				
Nitrofurantoin	2,0	1									22	7	14	5	1					
Orthosomycine																				
Avilamycin	0,0	0						19	28	2										
Penicilline																				
Ampicillin	2,0	1				9	9	24	5	1		1								
Phenicole																				
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0								38	11									
Polypeptide																				
Bacitracin	10,2	5									16	8	6	14	4	1				
Streptogramine																				
Synercid	0,0	0					3	1	14	10	21									
Tetracycline																				
Tetracyclin	12,2	6					41	2		1			4	1						

Table 93 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in Pigs - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method]

		<i>E. faecalis</i> PIGS																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	39	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Aminoglykosid AB			n																		
Gentamicin	0,0	0							11	18	8	2									
Streptomycin	10,3	4									1	8	20	6				2	2		
Glycopeptide																					
Vancomycin	0,0	0					35	4													
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																					
Ciprofloxacin	2,6	1				6	15	17				1									
Makrolide																					
Erythromycin	12,8	5					18	10	4	2	2				3						
Nitrofurane																					
Nitrofurantoin	0,0	0									17	5	9	8							
Orthosomycine																					
Avilamycin	2,6	1						13	21	4						1					
Penicilline																					
Ampicillin	0,0	0				4	7	26	2												
Phenicole																					
Chloramphenicol	2,6	1								24	13		1	1							
Polypeptide																					
Bacitracin	23,1	9									6	3	9	12	6	1	2				
Streptogramine																					
Synercid	0,0	0							5	14	19	1									
Tetracycline																					
Tetracyclin	64,1	25				14						1	3	14	7						

Table 94 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in broiler - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method]

		<i>E. faecalis</i> GALLUS GALLUS																		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	90																			
Antimicrobials:	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
Aminoglykosid AB			n																	
Gentamicin	1,1	1								29	50	10								1
Streptomycin	21,1	19										2	3	58	8				10	9
Glycopeptide								71	18	1										
Vancomycin	0,0	0																		
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																				
Ciprofloxacin	2,2	2			2	29	52	4	1		2									
Makrolide																				
Erythromycin	57,8	52				20	6	7	5	5	4	4	3	36						
Nitrofurane																				
Nitrofurantoin	0,0	0								65	14	7	4							
Orthosomycine																				
Avilamycin	3,3	3					41	44	2		2					1				
Penicilline																				
Ampicillin	0,0	0				9	77	3	1											
Phenicole																				
Chloramphenicol	2,2	2							55	33			2							
Polypeptide																				
Bacitracin	45,6	41									2	1	6	40	8	2	31			
Streptogramine																				
Synercid	0,0	0							3	13	55	18	1							
Tetracycline																				
Tetracyclin	73,3	66				24						1	29	21	15					

Table 95 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecium* in animals (qualitative tables)

<i>E. faecium</i>	Gallus Gallus		Cattle		Pigs	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes		yes		yes	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	80		113		131	
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n
Aminoglykosid AB						
Gentamicin	1,3	1	0,0	0	0,0	0
Streptomycin	17,5	14	0,0	0	6,1	8
Glycopeptide						
Vancomycin	5,0	4	5,3	6	1,5	2
Quinolone and Quinoxalin						
Ciprofloxacin	1,3	1	0,9	1	1,5	2
Makrolide						
Erythromycin	71,3	57	5,3	6	41,2	54
Nitrofurane						
Nitrofurantoin	1,3	1	1,8	2	0,0	0
Orthosomycine						
Avilamycin	6,3	5	0,0	0	0,0	0
Penicilline						
Ampicillin	5,0	4	0,0	0	0,0	0
Phenicole						
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,8	1
Polypeptide						
Bacitracin	55,0	44	66,4	75	68,7	90
Streptogramine						
Synercid	77,5	62	76,1	86	90,1	118
Tetracycline						
Tetracyclin	70,0	56	9,7	11	16,0	21
Number of multiresistant isolates						
fully sensitive	3,8	3	19,5	22	5,3	7
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	16,3	13	65,5	74	43,5	57
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	27,5	22	14,2	16	45,8	60
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	33,8	27	0,9	1	2,3	3
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	18,8	15	0,0	0	1,5	2
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	0,0	0	0,0	0	1,5	2

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For enterococci this includes resistance to streptomycin, gentamicin, chloramphenicol, ampicillin, vancomycin, erythromycin, synercid, tetracyclin

Table 96 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecium* in Cattle (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method]

		<i>E. faecium</i>																		
		CATTLE																		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	113	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																		
Antimicrobials:	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
			n																	
Aminoglykosid AB																				
Gentamicin	0,0	0								50	58	4	1							
Streptomycin	0,0	0										31	32	49	1					
Glycopeptide																				
Vancomycin	5,3	6						73	9	25	4				2					
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																				
Ciprofloxacin	0,9	1				7	27	50	10	18	1									
Makrolide																				
Erythromycin	5,3	6					40	9	29	29	4	2								
Nitrofurane																				
Nitrofurantoin	1,8	2									32	21	17	39	2				2	
Orthosomycine																				
Avilamycin	0,0	0						6	71	34	2									
Penicilline																				
Ampicillin	0,0	0				12	48	39	14											
Phenicole																				
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0								42	69	2								
Polypeptide																				
Bacitracin	66,4	75									6	2	6	24	57	13	5			
Streptogramine																				
Synercid	76,1	86					18	9	23	62	1									
Tetracycline																				
Tetracyclin	9,7	11					70	29	3	3		1	3	4						

Table 97 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecium* in Pigs - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method]

		<i>E. faecium</i>																			
		PIGS																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	131	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	%R	n	<=0,06	0,06	0,12	0,25	0,5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
			n																		
Aminoglykosid AB																					
Gentamicin	0,0	0								47	76	8									
Streptomycin	6,1	8										5	34	83	1			3	1	4	
Glycopeptide																					
Vancomycin	1,5	2						122	3	4	2										
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																					
Ciprofloxacin	1,5	2				11	26	76	8	8	2										
Makrolide																					
Erythromycin	41,2	54					16		15	46	44	4			6						
Nitrofurane																					
Nitrofurantoin	0,0	0										9	10	13	95	4					
Orthosomycine																					
Avilamycin	0,0	0						7	98	23	2	1									
Penicilline																					
Ampicillin	0,0	0				7	23	83	16	2											
Phenicole																					
Chloramphenicol	0,8	1								63	67				1						
Polypeptide																					
Bacitracin	68,7	90										9	2	3	27	73	12	5			
Streptogramine																					
Synercid	90,1	118					7	6	41	73	4										
Tetracycline																					
Tetracyclin	16,0	21					103	7		1				2	11	7					

Table 98 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecium* in broiler - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method]

		<i>E. faecium</i>																	
		GALLUS GALLUS																	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		80																	
		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																	
Antimicrobials:																			
		n																	
		<= 0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		%R	n																
Aminoglykosid AB																			
	Gentamicin	1,3							43	33	3					1			
	Streptomycin	17,5									5	21	29	11	5	1	3	3	2
Glycopeptide																			
	Vancomycin	5,0					55	17	4					4					
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																			
	Ciprofloxacin	1,3			3	4	22	30	20	1									
Makrolide																			
	Erythromycin	71,3				8	5	7	3	3	1	1	1	51					
Nitrofurane																			
	Nitrofurantoin	1,3								7	15	18	27	12		1			
Orthosomycine																			
	Avilamycin	6,3					23	40	9	2	1	3			2				
Penicilline																			
	Ampicillin	5,0			11	24	13	12	16	4									
Phenicole																			
	Chloramphenicol	0,0							29	45	3	3							
Polypeptide																			
	Bacitracin	55,0								7	2	9	18	16	3	25			
Streptogramine																			
	Synercid	77,5				9	9	20	32	9	1								
Tetracycline																			
	Tetracyclin	70,0				19	4	1	2	2	3	6	33	10					

6. Foodborne outbreaks

Foodborne outbreaks are defined as two or more human cases of the same disease or infection where the cases are linked or are probably linked to the same food source. A situation in which the observed human cases exceed the expected number of cases and where a same food source is suspected, is also indicative of a foodborne outbreak.

A. Foodborne outbreaks

System in place for identification, epidemiological investigations and reporting of food borne outbreaks

Presently, every district (Austria = 98 + Vienna) is responsible for outbreak investigation. However, food borne outbreaks affecting more than one district or even more than one province (Austria = 9 provinces) are regulated by the Federal Zoonoses Act (Zoonosengesetz, BGBl. I, 128/2005 entered into force on 1. January 2006). The Federal Zoonoses Commission was founded to advise the Federal Minister to survey and combat the zoonoses in Austria. One target of the Zoonoses Act is to ensure that food-borne outbreaks receive proper epidemiological investigation. It regulates, in case of food borne outbreaks affecting more than one province, that the governors of the affected provinces provide operative units to investigate possible or confirmed food borne outbreaks. Data concerning epidemiological criteria, potential implicated food items and the source of an outbreak must be collected and adequate epidemiological and microbiological examinations must be conducted. Short reports summarize each outbreak and must be communicated to the Federal Commission for Zoonoses and to AGES.

Description of the types of outbreaks covered by the reporting:

Since there has not been a coordinated approach for outbreak investigation in most provinces, the large majority (305 of 368) of food borne outbreaks are classified as household outbreaks. Coordinated investigation of outbreaks affecting more than one province - unhampered by district limits - will drastically decrease the total number of outbreaks.

National evaluation of the reported outbreaks in the country:

In 2008, 368 food borne outbreaks (14 verified and 354 possible) affecting 1,376 persons were reported. 352 persons were hospitalized and no person died. The total number of food borne outbreaks decreased by 16% compared to 2007. The number of cases affected by an outbreak was 3.7 persons/outbreak. 18% (11% in 2007) of the reported outbreaks were acquired abroad. 32% of all food borne outbreaks acquired in Austria were caused by *Campylobacter* spp. (n=118), 60% by *Salmonella* spp. (n=223) and 78% thereof by serotype Enteritidis (n=174).

Relevance of the different causative agents, food categories and the agent/food category combinations

Salmonella and *Campylobacter* pose the most important agents causing 92% of all food borne outbreaks. The data quality does presently not allow conclusions on the relevance of different food categories.

Relevance of the different type of places of food production and preparation in outbreaks

The data quality does presently not allow conclusions on the relevance of different food categories.

Evaluation of the severity and clinical picture of the human cases

Hospitalized cases or cases that result in death are presently not ascertained in a valid way: Nevertheless, 25.6% of patients affected by these food borne outbreaks are reported as hospitalized (16.3% in 2007); there were no deaths (in 2007: 1 lethal case).

Descriptions of single outbreaks of special interest

Much P, Pichler J, Kasper S, Lassnig H, Kornschober C, Buchner A, König C, Allerberger F. 2008: A foodborne outbreak of Salmonella Enteritidis phage type 6 in Austria, 2008. Wien. Klin. Wochenschr. (2009)121: 132-136.

Pichler J, Much P, Kasper S, Fretz R, Auer B et al. 2009: An outbreak of febrile gastroenteritis associated with jellied pork contaminated with Listeria monocytogenes. Wien. Klin. Wochenschr. (2009)121: 149-156.

Kuo Hung-Wei, Kasper S, Jelovcan S, Höger G, Lederer I et al. 2009: A food-borne outbreak of Shigella sonnei gastroenteritis, Austria, 2008. Wien. Klin. Wochenschr. (2009) 121: 157–163.

Kasper S, Fretz R, Kornschober C, Allerberger F, Schmid D. 2009: Imported Salmonella Enteritidis cases: a multiphage outbreak among Austrian vacationers in Turkey, 2008
Wien. Klin. Wochenschr. (2009) 121: 144–148.

Wassermann-Neuhold M. 2009: Ausgewählte Erkrankungen und Ausbrüche im Jahr 2008 in der Steiermark, Jahresbericht zum Steirischen Seuchenplan 2008
http://www.verwaltung.steiermark.at/cms/dokumente/10039771_21212/f99f35af/Jahresbericht2008.pdf

Control measures or other actions taken to improve the situation

Improvement due to the implementation of the Federal Zoonoses Act e.g. the chain of command in terms of investigation of food borne outbreaks affecting more than one province was implemented.

Table 99 Foodborne outbreaks in humans

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
C. coli	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
C. jejuni	1	Household		3	2	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	2	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	2	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
C. jejuni	1	Household	Czech Republic	2	0	0	fish and fish products		Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad	Intra Community trade	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	fish and fish products		Restaurant/Hotel	Unknown	Domestic	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	fish and fish products		Household	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		Household	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	Bovine meat		Household	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household	Bali	2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Travel abroad		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	Broiler meat		Household	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household	Kosovo	2	1	0	unknown		unknown	Travel abroad		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	General		8	0	0	Broiler meat		Restaurant/Hotel	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household	Croatia	2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Travel abroad		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	1	0	Milk		Household	Farm		Inadequate heat treatment
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
C. jejuni	1	General		4					Restaurant/Hotel	Catering services/re	Unknown	

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
										staurant		
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	1				Household	Household	Unknown	Other
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	1		Milk	Laboratory characterisation of isolates from food and human samples	Household	Household	Unknown	unprocessed contaminated ingredient
C. jejuni	1	Household		2			Broiler meat		Household	Household	Unknown	Other
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	1				Household	Household	Unknown	Other
C. jejuni	1	Household		2			Milk		Household	Household	Unknown	Other
C. jejuni	1	General		5			Broiler meat		Restaurant/Hotel	Catering services/restaurant	Unknown	Other
C. jejuni	1	General		2	1		Broiler meat		Take-away	Take-away	Unknown	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2			pig meat		Household	Retail sale outlet	Unknown	
C. jejuni	1	Household		4	1				Household	Household	Unknown	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	1		Bovine meat		Household	Retail sale outlet	Unknown	Other
C. jejuni	1	General		2			mixed red meat		Restaurant/Hotel	Catering services/restaurant	Unknown	Other
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0			Household	Household	Unknown	
C. jejuni	1	General		2	0	0	mixed red meat		Mobile retailer		Domestic	
C. jejuni	1	General		3	0	0	Milk	Laboratory detection in human cases	Restaurant/Hotel	Processing plant	Domestic	unprocessed contaminated ingredient
C. jejuni	28	Household		58	7	0						

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	1	0	Other foods		Household			
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	Broiler meat		Take-away		Domestic	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	1	0	Other foods		Household			
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	mixed red meat		Household			
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	Other foods		Household		Intra Community trade	
C. jejuni	1	Household	Bosnia	2	0	0				Travel abroad	Imported from outside EU	
C. jejuni	1	General		2	0	0						
C. jejuni	1	Household	Turkey	2	0	0	Broiler meat			Travel abroad	Imported from outside EU	
C. jejuni	1	Household	Morocco	2	0	0	Broiler meat			Travel abroad	Imported from outside EU	
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	fish and fish products		Restaurant/Hotel			
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	mixed or buffet meals		Restaurant/Hotel			
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	Broiler meat		Take-away			
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	1	0	Broiler meat		unknown			
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	Broiler meat		Household			
C. jejuni	1	Household		2	0	0	Other foods		Household			
C. jejuni/coli	1	Household		2	1		unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases			Domestic	
C. jejuni/coli	1	Household		3	1		unknown				Domestic	
C. spp.	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown	Laboratory detection	Household			

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
								in human cases				
C. spp.	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Household			
C. spp.	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Household			
C. spp.	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Household			
C. spp.	1	Household		2			unknown		Household			
C. spp.	1	Household		2	1		Pig meat		Household			
C. spp.	1	Household		2	1		unknown		Household			
C. spp.	1	Household		2					unknown			
C. spp.	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown				Domestic	
C. spp.	1	Household		2	0	0	Broiler meat				Domestic	
C. spp.	1	Household		2	2	0	Broiler meat		Restaurant/Hotel			
EHEC O119:H4	1	Household		2	1						Unknown	Other
EHEC O157	1	Household		2	1		unknown		Household			
EHEC O157	1	Household	Cyprus	2	0	0			Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad		
EHEC O157:H7	1	Household		4	1		pig meat		Household	Retail sale outlet	Unknown	
EHEC O157:H7	1	Household		2	2				Household	Household	Unknown	
EHEC O157:H7	1	Household	Romania	3	1		tap water			Travel abroad		
EHEC O22:H8	1	General		3	1				Restaurant/Hotel	Catering services/restaurant	Unknown	
EHEC O26:H-	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown				Domestic	
EHEC O26:H11	1	Household		5	1		Milk		Household	Household	Unknown	
EHEC O26:H11, O157:H7	1	Household	Turkey	2	0	0	unknown			Travel abroad	Domestic	
EHEC ONT:H30	1	Household		4	1		unknown					

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
L.monocytogenes sv 4b	1	General		14	7	0	Pig meat	Laboratory characterisation of isolates from food and human samples, analytical epidemiological evidence	Restaurant/Hotel	Catering services/restaurant	Domestic	Cross-contamination
Norovirus	1	General		2	2	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
Norovirus	1	Household		2	2	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
Norovirus	1	Household		2	2	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
Norovirus	1	General		13	0	0	mixed or buffet meals		unknown	Unknown		
Norovirus	1	Household		3	2	0	unknown					
Norovirus	1	General		6	1	0	unknown		other			
Norovirus	1	General		10	2	0	unknown		other			
Norovirus	1	General		77	40	0	mixed or buffet meals	Laboratory detection in human cases, analytical epidemiological evidence	Canteen or workplace catering	Catering services/restaurant	Domestic	Cross-contamination
S. Abony	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown				Domestic	
S. Agona	1	Household		2	1	0						
S. Blockley	1	Household	Hungary	2	1	0	unknown		Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad		
S. Braenderup	1	Household		2	0	0						
S. Brandenburg	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Derby	1	Household	Burkina Faso	2	2	0	unknown		unknown	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis (PT21, PT6, PT7, PT3)	1	General	Turkey	103	18	0	eggs and egg products		Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis DT104L	1	Household		3	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
S. Enteritidis O:9	1	Household	Tunesia	2			unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases		Travel abroad	Unknown	
S. Enteritidis O:9	1	General		4			unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Residential institution		Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT1	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT1	1	General	Egypt	2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT1	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT1	1	Household		3			eggs and egg products		Household	Household	Unknown	unprocessed contaminated ingredient
S. Enteritidis PT1	1	General	Maedives	3	1				Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT1	1	General	Spain	2	0	0	mixed or buffet meals		Residential institution	Travel abroad	Intra Community trade	
S. Enteritidis PT12	1	Household	Croatia	2			unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases		Travel abroad	Unknown	
S. Enteritidis PT12	1	General	Hungary	2	2	0	eggs and egg products		Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad	Intra Community trade	
S. Enteritidis PT13	1	Household		3	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT13a	1	Household	Bosnia	3	0	0	unknown		unknown	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT13a	1	Household	Czech Republic	2	0	0	mixed or buffet meals		Household	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT13a	1	Household	Bosnia	2	0	0			Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad	Imported from outside EU	
S. Enteritidis PT13a	3	Household		6	2	0						
S. Enteritidis	1	Household	Italy	2			unknown		unknown	Travel		

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
PT14b										abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT14b	1	Household		3	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT14b	1	Household	Greece	2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT14b	1	Household		4	1	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT14b	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT14b	1	Household	Greece	2	1	0	eggs and egg products		Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad	Intra Community trade	
S. Enteritidis PT1b	1	Household		2	2	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	General		25	7		dairy products		Restaurant/Hotel		Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	Household	Hungary	2	1	0	mixed or buffet meals		unknown	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	Household	Greece	2			eggs and egg products		Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		Household	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	Household	Greece	2	2	0	unknown		unknown	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	Household		2	2	0	eggs and egg products		Household	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	Household		2	0	0	Broiler meat		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	General	Italy	4			eggs and egg products			Travel abroad	Unknown	
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	Household	Croatia	2			unknown			Travel abroad	Unknown	
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	General		25	7		unknown		Restaurant/Hotel	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	Household		4	1		eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in implicated food, laboratory detection in human cases	Household	Household	Unknown	Other
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	Household		3	2	0	unknown			Household	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	Household		5	2	0	eggs and egg products				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	Household		3	0	0	unknown				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	Household		3	0	0	eggs and egg products		unknown		Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	Household		2	0	0	eggs and egg products				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	Household		3	0	0	unknown				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	Household	Ukraine	3	0	0	unknown			Travel abroad	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT21	3	Household		6	4	0						
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Household			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		3	2	0	dairy		Household			

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
							products					
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		4	3	0	eggs and egg products		Household			Unprocessed contaminated ingredient
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	General		3	0	0	eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in implicated food, laboratory detection in human cases	Restaurant/Hotel			Unprocessed contaminated ingredient
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household	Bosnia	2	1		mixed or buffet meals		unknown	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	1		unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		3	1	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	2	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household	Czech Republic	2	0	0	dairy products		Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad	Intra Community trade	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		3	0	0	eggs and egg products		Household	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		Household	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	2	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		3	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household	Bosnia	2	1	0	Broiler meat		unknown	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	2	0	eggs and egg products		Household	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	General		7	5	0	eggs and egg products		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		3	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2			unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases			Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2			unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases			Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		4	1		eggs and egg products				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household	Greece	3			Broiler meat		Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad	Unknown	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		4			Broiler meat	Laboratory detection in implicated food, laboratory detection in human cases	Household	Farm	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	General		23	6		eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in implicated food, laboratory detection in human cases	Restaurant/Hotel	Catering services/restaurant	Unknown	unprocessed contaminated ingredient
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	General		6	2		Vegetables		Restaurant/Hotel	Catering services/restaurant	Unknown	Other

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		4	1		eggs and egg products		Household	Household	Unknown	Other
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	General	Turkey	2	2				Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		4	3		eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in implicated food, laboratory detection in human cases	Household	Household	Unknown	Other
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	1				Household	Household	Unknown	Other
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	General	Croatia	2			dairy products			Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2			Broiler meat		Household	Household	Unknown	Other
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown			Household	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		6	4	0	unknown				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		4	0	0	eggs and egg products				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	0	0	mixed or buffet meals				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	2	0	eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Household	Unknown	Unknown	inadequate heat treatment
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	0	0	dairy products	Laboratory detection in human cases	Mobile retailer	Unknown	Domestic	unknown
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	1	0	turkey meat	Laboratory detection in human cases	Household	Unknown	Unknown	unknown
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	General		17	0	0	eggs and egg products		Restaurant/Hotel	Catering services/restaurant	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	General		2	0	0	Other foods		Restaurant/Hotel	Catering services/restaurant	Domestic	

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		4	2	0	eggs and egg products				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	General		2	1	0	unknown		Restaurant/Hotel	Catering services/restaurant	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		6	4	0	eggs and egg products				Intra Community trade	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	General		4	1	0	unknown		Restaurant/Hotel		Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	General		5	1	0	bakery products				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	General		26	10	0	mixed or buffet meals		Restaurant/Hotel	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household	Turkey	4	2	0	pig meat		unknown	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household	Bosnia	2	1	0	mixed or buffet meals		Household	Travel abroad	Imported from outside EU	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	1	0	mixed or buffet meals		Restaurant/Hotel			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household	Serbia	2	1	0			Household	Travel abroad	Imported from outside EU	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	General		4	1	0			Restaurant/Hotel			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	0	0	eggs and egg		Household		Domestic	

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
							products					
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		3	0	0						
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	1	0	Broiler meat		Household			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	General		2	0	0	mixed or buffet meals		Residential institution			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	Household		2	1	0	pig meat		Restaurant/Hotel			
S. Enteritidis PT4b	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT5	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	General		9	0	0	eggs and egg products	Laboratory characterisation of isolates from food and human samples	Household	Farm	Domestic	inadequate heat treatment
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	General	Turkey	2			unknown		Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	Household		3	1	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	General	Turkey	3	1				Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	General	Croatia	3	2				Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	General	Russia	4						Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	Household	Turkey	2	0	0	Broiler meat			Travel abroad	Unknown	
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	Household	Turkey	3	1	0	unknown			Travel abroad	Unknown	
S. Enteritidis PT7	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household	Hungary	2	0	0	mixed or buffet		unknown	Travel abroad		

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
							meals					
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		2	1		unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		2	1		unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	General		13			unknown		School/Kindergarten			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		2	1		unknown		Restaurant/Hotel			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		2	1	0	Broiler meat		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		3	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		2	0	0	mixed or buffet meals		Restaurant/Hotel	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	General		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household	Turkey	2	0	0	unknown		Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	General		2	1	0	eggs and egg products		Restaurant/Hotel	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		3			unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases			Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		3	1		unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases			Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		3			unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases			Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		4	2		unknown				Domestic	

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		8	3		eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in implicated food, laboratory detection in human cases	Household	Household	Unknown	Other
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown			Household	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		2	2	0	unknown				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases	Household	Unknown	Unknown	unknown
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		2	1	0	eggs and egg products	Laboratory characterisation of isolates from food and human samples	Restaurant/Hotel	Catering services/restaurant	Unknown	inadequate heat treatment
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	General		3	0	0	unknown				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		2		0	unknown				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		Household			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		4	0	0	eggs and egg products		Household		Intra Community trade	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household		2	0	0			Household			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household	Slovakia	2	1	0	mixed or buffet meals		Household	Travel abroad	Intra Community trade	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	Household	Croatia	2	0	0	dairy products		Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad	Imported from outside EU	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	General		4	4	0			Residential institution		Domestic	Inadequate heat treatment
S. Enteritidis PT8 u. RDNC	1	Household		3	1	0	unknown				Domestic	
S. Enteritidis RDNC	1	Household		2	1		unknown	Laboratory detection in human cases			Domestic	

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
S. Enteritidis spp.	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Enteritidis spp.	1	Household		2	2	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		
S. Hadar	1	Household	Greece	4	0	0	unknown			Travel abroad	Domestic	
S. Haifa	1	Household	Dubai	2	0	0	unknown		Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad	Imported from outside EU	
S. Heidelberg	1	Household		2	1	0	eggs and egg products		Household	Unknown		
S. IIIb 48:z52:z	1	Household		2	0	0						
S. Indiana	1	Household		2	1	0						
S. Infantis	1	Household		2	1	0						
S. Javiana	1	Household		2	1				Household	Household	Unknown	Other
S. Kingabwa	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		Cross-contamination
S. Napoli	1	Household	Romania	2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Travel abroad		
S. Oranienburg	1	Household		3	3		mixed or buffet meals		Household	Retail sale outlet	Unknown	
S. paratyphi B	1	Household		2	0	0				Unknown	Domestic	
S. Rissen	1	General	France	4	1					Travel abroad		
S. Saintpaul	1	General		10	5		Broiler meat	Laboratory characterisation of isolates from food and human samples	Restaurant/Hotel	Catering services/restaurant	Unknown	Other
S. San Diego	1	Household	Kuba	2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Travel abroad		
S. Stanley	1	Household	Thailand	2	0	0	Broiler meat		Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad		
S. Stanleyville	1	Household	Croatia	2	1		mixed or		unknown	Travel		

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
							buffet meals			abroad		
S. Thompson	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown		
S. Typhimurium DT104H	1	General		2	1	0	unknown			Household	Domestic	
S. Typhimurium DT104L	1	Household		2	1	0	mixed or buffet meals		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Typhimurium DT104L	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Typhimurium DT104L	1	Household		3	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Typhimurium DT104L	1	Household		2	1	0						
S. Typhimurium DT120	1	Household		3	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Typhimurium DT120	1	General	Italy	2	2		mixed or buffet meals		Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad		
S. Typhimurium DT193	1	General	Italy	3	0	0	unknown		unknown	Travel abroad		
S. Typhimurium DT193	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown					
S. Typhimurium DT3 u. RDNC	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown			Household	Domestic	
S. Typhimurium DT41	1	General		6	5	0	eggs and egg products		Restaurant/Hotel	Unknown	Domestic	
S. Typhimurium DT41	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown		
S. Typhimurium DT41	1	Household		3	1	0	unknown					Cross-contamination
S. Typhimurium DT41	1	General		2	0	0	unknown		unknown	Unknown		

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
S. Typhimurium DT41	2	Household		4	2	0						
S. Typhimurium DT42	1	Household		2	0	0			unknown			
S. Typhimurium DT85	1	General		15	10		unspecified poultry meat		Residential institution	Catering services/restaurant	Intra Community trade	Other
S. Typhimurium RDNC	1	Household	Greece	2	0	0	eggs and egg products		unknown	Travel abroad		
S. Typhimurium RDNC	1	Household	Turkey	3	2	0	pig meat		Household	Travel abroad	Imported from outside EU	
S. Virchow	1	Household		2			Broiler meat	Laboratory detection in human cases	Restaurant/Hotel		Domestic	
S. Virchow	1	General	Egypt	2					Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad		
Salmonella group B	1	Household	Italy	3	1		tap water		Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad		
Salmonella group B monophasic strain, PT193	1	General		89	14	0	Pig meat		unknown			
Salmonella group C1	1	General	Greece	4	0	0	eggs and egg products		Restaurant/Hotel	Travel abroad	Unknown	
Salmonella group D	1	Household	Bali	2	1		Broiler meat		unknown	Travel abroad		
Shigella sonnei	1	General		53	1	0	Vegetables	Analytical epidemiological evidence	Restaurant/Hotel	Catering services/restaurant	Unknown	Cross-contamination
Shigella sonnei	1	General		2	2	0	mixed or buffet meals		Restaurant/Hotel			
TBE	1	General		6	4	0	Cheese	Laboratory characterisation of	Household	Household	Domestic	unprocessed

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
								isolates from food and human samples				contaminated ingredient
Yersinia enterocolitica O:3	1	Household		2	1	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
Yersinia enterocolitica O:3	1	Household		2	0	0	unknown		Household	Unknown	Domestic	
Yersinia enterocolitica O:3	1	General		4	1	0	Pig meat		School/Kindergarten	Catering services/restaurant		inadequate heat treatment
Yersinia enterocolitica O:3	1	Household		3	1	0			Restaurant/Hotel			
Total	368			1376	352	0						

7. Information on specific microbiological agents

7.1. Staphylococcal Enterotoxins

7.1.1. Staphylococcal enterotoxins general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Not available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Additional information

Not available

7.1.2. Staphylococcal enterotoxins in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Not available

Type of specimen taken

Not available

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Not available

Definition of positive finding

Not available

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Not available

Preventive measures in place

Not available

Control program/mechanisms**The control program/strategies in place**

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the hazard

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Notification system in place

Not available

Results of the investigation

See table below

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Table 100 Staphylococcal enterotoxins in food

	Sampling stage	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for Staphylococcal enterotoxins
Categories				
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	single	8	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	single	9	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	single	40	0
	at retail	single	10	0
Crustaceans	at catering	single	2	0
Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at catering	single	5	0
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at catering	single	2	0
Other food	at retail	single	27	0

7.2. Enterobacter sakazakii

7.2.1. Enterobacter sakazakii general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Not available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Additional information

Not available

7.2.2. Enterobacter sakazakii in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Not available

Type of specimen taken

Not available

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Not available

Definition of positive finding

Not available

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Not available

Preventive measures in place

Not available

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the hazard

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Notification system in place

Not available

Results of the investigation

Not available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See table below

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Table 101 Enterobacter sakazakii in food

	Sampling stage	Sampling unit	Sampling weight	Units tested	Total units positive for E. sakazakii
Categories					
Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses	at farm	single	25 g	1	0

7.3. Histamine

7.3.1. Histamine general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Not available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Additional information

Not available

7.3.2. Histamine in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Not available

Type of specimen taken

Not available

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Not available

Definition of positive finding

Not available

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Not available

Preventive measures in place

Not available

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the hazard

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Notification system in place

Not available

Results of the investigation

See table below

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Table 102 Histamine in food

Categories	Sampling stage	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units in non-conformity		
				<= 100 mg/kg	> 200 - <= 400 mg/kg	> 400 mg/kg
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at retail	single	3	1	2	1
Fish - raw	at catering	single	6	1	5	1
Fishery products, unspecified	at retail	single	72	3	69	2
Meat, red meat, meat products - fermented sausages	at retail	single	2	1	1	1

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